

**Investigations into non-destructive
biomarkers for endocrine disruption in
wild *Rana temporaria* (common frogs) in
Scotland**

Catherine Helen Whatley

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Front cover image description: A red adult common frog (*Rana temporaria*) photographed in Aviemore, Scotland. The red coloration of common frogs is more commonly found in Scotland compared to the rest of the UK.

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Author declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this Ph.D. thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Personal details withheld.

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Abstract

When last assessed in 2022, 40.7% of amphibian species were reported to be threatened with extinction (an increase of 2.8% since 2004), which is greater than for any other vertebrate group. Chemical pollution (such as from agriculture, pharmaceuticals, or industry) is the second most important threat impacting amphibians after habitat loss. Although chemical pollutant profiles in small freshwater bodies, where amphibians typically live and breed, are not well known, they are likely to contain high concentrations of chemicals, many of which are known or suspected endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs). Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are chemical substances that can alter the function of the endocrine system by interfering with hormone receptors, hormone synthesis, or the metabolism of hormones, and can cause adverse health effects. There is a need for biomonitoring tools for contaminant exposure, including EDCs, of wild amphibians that are preferably non-lethal in nature.

This thesis aimed to investigate non-lethal methods for identifying contaminant exposure effects in wild common frogs, *Rana temporaria*, that relate to reproductive health, growth and development. Firstly, the land use and water quality around the areas where *R. temporaria* adults and tadpoles were collected in central Scotland were used to determine if there was a relationship between frog/tadpole morphometry and water quality/land uses. Adult and tadpole mass, tadpole length, and adult male nuptial pad length were all influenced by changes in land use around ponds, as well as changes in some water quality parameters. Development of a cell based luminescence assay was attempted which would have allowed analysis of water from the same ponds to determine whether chemicals present were causing androgenic/anti-androgenic activity. However, this was unsuccessful. Expression of genes involved in sex differentiation and determination in the gonads of tadpoles collected from these ponds was examined using destructive techniques. No relationship was found between gonad morphology and expression of any of the genes investigated (*amh*, *cyp17*, *foxL2*, *cyp19*), although a small significant difference in *amh* expression was identified between two study sites. Finally, the non-destructive monitoring of *R. temporaria* tadpoles over time was carried out at six pond sites, focusing on the effects of a range of metal elements and water quality parameters on tadpole morphometrics. Different developmental stages of tadpoles were shown to be affected by different elements and water quality.

The most effective biomonitoring tool identified throughout this thesis was the use of tadpole measurements, with the mass and length of tadpoles showing particular promise as morphometrics affected by land use, water quality, and element concentrations. More work is now needed to refine the findings of this thesis to confirm the use of tadpole morphometrics as a field-based biomarker of endocrine disruption.

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Table of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACTH	Adrenocorticotrophic hormone
AIC	Akaike information criterion
ALAD	Aminolevulinic acid dehydratase
ALAN	Artificial light at night
AMP	Adenosine monophosphate
AMPA	Aminomethylphosphonic acid
ANCOVA	Analysis of covariance
ANOVA	Analysis of variance
APE	Alkylphenol polyethoxylates
AR	Androgen Receptor
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
BOD	Biological oxygen demand
CLC	Corine land cover
CRF	Corticotropin releasing factor (also corticotropin releasing hormone)
DH	Dihydrotestosterone
DHARMa	Residual diagnostics for hierarchical (multi-Level / mixed) regression models
DHT	Dihydrotestosterone
DMEM	Dulbecco's modified eagle medium
DMSO	Dimethylsulfoxide
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DO	Dissolved oxygen
DPX	Dibutylphthalate polystyrene xylene
EDC	Endocrine disrupting chemical
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid

EE ₂	17 α -Ethinylestradiol
EIA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group
ESD	Environmental sex determination
EU	European Union
FACS	Fluorescence-activated cell sorting
FBS	Foetal bovine serum
FETAX	Frog embryo teratogenesis assay: <i>Xenopus</i>
FSH	Follicle stimulating hormone
GC	Guanine/cytosine
GIS	Geographic information systems
GLMER	Generalised linear mixed effects model
GLMM	Generalised linear mixed model
GnRH	Gonadotropin releasing hormone
GPS	Global positioning system
GSH	Glutathione
HNO ₃	Nitric acid
HPA	Hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal axis
HPG	Hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal axis
HPI	Hypothalamo-pituitary-interrenal axis
HPT	Hypothalamo-pituitary-thyroid axis
HSD	Honest significant difference
HSV	herpes simplex virus
ICP-OES	Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy analysis
IUCN	International Union for the Conservation of Nature
LB	Lysogeny broth

LED	Light-emitting diode
LG	Linkage groups
LH	Luteinising hormone
LOD	Limit of detection
MANCOVA	Multivariate analysis of covariance
MDHT	Methyldihydrotestosterone
M-MLV	Moloney murine leukemia virus
MMTV	Mouse mammary tumour virus
MMU	Minimum mapping unit
MTT	Methyltestosterone or (3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide)
NBN	National biodiversity network
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
NF	Nieuwkoop-Faber staging
NRR	Neutral red release assay
OP	Octylphenol
OS	Ordnance Survey
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PBDE	Polybrominated diphenyl ethers
PBS	Phosphate buffered saline
PC	Principal component
PCA	Principal component analysis
PCB	polychlorinated biphenyls
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PPP	Plant protection products
PRL	Prolactin
RBG	Red green blue values
RNA	Ribonucleic acid

SD	Standard deviation
SEM	Standard error of the mean
SMG	Specialised mucous glands
SSC	Secondary sex characteristics
SVL	Snout vent length
T	Testosterone
T ₃	Triiodothyronine
T ₄	Thyroxine
TDS	Total dissolved solids
TDSD	Temperature dependent sex determination
TE	Tris-EDTA
TSH	Thyroid stimulating hormone (also thyrotropin)
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
US	United States
USA	United States of America
UV	Ultraviolet
UWS	University of the West of Scotland
VTG	Vitellogenin
WHO	World Health Organisation

Chapter one: Literature review - Biomonitoring techniques for pollution effects in wild anurans (with a focus on *Rana temporaria*)

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Introduction

The clade of amphibians consists of the Anura (frogs and toads), the Caudata (newts and salamanders), and the Gymnophiona (caecilians) (Pyron and Wiens, 2011). Amphibians are a group of animals whose ancestors evolved from a group of fishes, becoming the first vertebrates that colonised the land around 270 million years ago (Cogger, 2014). According to the website ‘Amphibians of the world’, as of October 2025 there are 8930 species of amphibian, with 7825 (88 %) belonging to the Anura (<https://amphibiansoftheworld.amnh.org>: Frost, 2021). Amphibians have been in decline for several decades, with over 40% currently threatened (40.7% according to the second Global Amphibian Assessment in 2023), and nearly 3% of known species already thought to be extinct (Monastersky, 2014; Bongaarts, 2019; Luedtke *et al.*, 2023). When last assessed over a decade ago, extinction rates for amphibians were estimated to be approximately 211 times the expected background rate (McCallum, 2007), with current rates of extinction unknown. This may be due to a variety of causes, including climate change, habitat loss and fragmentation, pollution, invasive species, emerging infectious diseases, and wildlife trafficking, and is exacerbated by the nature of their ecology that makes them particularly vulnerable to anthropogenic change. It is of note that many of these causes of decline often occur simultaneously, and may have compounding effects (Díaz *et al.*, 2019). It is also of note that research into amphibian declines and their potential causes has more than quadrupled in the past 40 years (Angelini, Bielby and Costa, 2020).

Like all biota to a greater or lesser extent, amphibians are integral to normal functioning of ecosystems. During their life cycle, amphibians undergo metamorphosis which allows them to inhabit both freshwater and terrestrial ecosystems and makes them important bioindicators for assessing the impacts of pollutants/ecological changes in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Whiles *et al.* (2006) reviewed the effect of amphibian declines on neotropical stream ecosystems, reporting evidence from field studies that primary production, nutrient cycling, leaf litter decomposition, and invertebrate populations change when tadpoles (Flecker, Feifarek and Taylor, 1999; Kiffney and Richardson, 2001; Ranvestel *et al.*, 2004), and frogs (Beard, Vogt and Kulmatiski, 2002) are removed or reduced in a system.

Amphibians are important as prey species for other taxa due to their large numbers, especially in larval form, and as their morphology is usually free from less digestible materials such as scales, fur, or feathers, this makes them a suitable food source for a wide range of predators (Wells, 2010). For example, snake species that specialise in eating frogs such as the Western terrestrial garter snake (*Thamnophis elegans*) have declined in abundance in concordance with the decline of their amphibian prey (Jennings, Bradford and Johnson, 1992). Amphibians are important invertebrate predators in their adult form (Wells, 2010). Amphibians are also widely reported in the literature as being good ecosystem indicators: something that can be used as a surrogate measure of factors such as environmental contamination or habitat quality, or as a prediction of population trends in other species (Beebee and Griffiths, 2005; Waddle, 2006). However, there is some doubt in the literature about the reliability of this measure, as amphibians have been found to be less useful as ecosystem indicators than other taxa such as fishes (Pinheiro *et al.*, 2021).

Amphibians are important for overall ecosystem wellbeing; however, they are in decline from several threats, often occurring simultaneously. In order to be able to assess the health of a population of amphibians, it is important to be able to monitor the health of individuals, both at an individual level as well as on a scale of populations within ecosystems. This literature review aims to outline the main threats to amphibians globally with a particular focus on endocrine disruptors (EDCs), describe anuran reproduction in the context of endocrine disruption, and overview the use of biomonitoring techniques that can be used to assess the effects of pollutants on anuran health, with a particular focus on reproductive health and growth and development.

Threats to amphibians

There are several causes of decline thought to be impacting amphibian populations, and often these causes co-occur and interact to drive declines (reviewed in Beebee and Griffiths, 2005; Collins, 2010; Díaz *et al.*, 2019). This highlights the need to carry out multiple stressor studies to investigate the interacting effects of multiple causes of decline (Linder, Krest and Sparkling, 2003; Boone *et al.*, 2007; Chen *et al.*, 2008). Multiple stressors often occur in the most at-risk areas such as in the tropics where there is less research priority and amphibian extinction rates are higher (see **Figure 1.1**) (Hayes *et al.*, 2010; Becker and Zamudio, 2011). This is especially concerning given the high levels of diversity in the tropics (Alexander Pyron and Wiens, 2013). So called, “unexplained declines”, have also been reported, usually occurring in undisturbed habitats (Hayes *et al.*, 2010). The unique ecology and natural history of the amphibian clade makes them particularly vulnerable to these changes, and their biphasic lifestyle must also be taken into account regarding amphibian conservation (Wells, 2010; Nolan *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1.1: Image highlighting the probability that a randomly selected amphibian occurring in a $50 \text{ km} \times 50 \text{ km}$ cell is impacted by habitat loss (a), agriculture (b), hunting (c), pollution (d), invasive species (e) and climate change (f). Darker colours indicate higher probabilities. A value of 0 indicates that no species is affected, and 1.0 indicates that all species occurring are affected. Grey indicates areas with fewer than 10 species for which the impact probability has not been estimated. (g) The threat with the highest probability of impact in each cell. The colours correspond to the maximum colour scales in a–f. (h) The variability of the estimates calculated by resampling the threat classes of each species on the basis of the proportion of Data Deficient species in a given cell. Taken from Harfoot *et al.* (2021), used under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Figure 1.2: Image highlighting the expected number of amphibian species in each 50×50 km cell impacted by (a) habitat loss, (b) agriculture, (c) hunting, (d) pollution, (e) invasive species, and (f) climate change. Darker colours indicate higher numbers. Grey indicates areas with fewer than 10 species for which the threat probability models were not calculated. Taken from Harfoot *et al.* (2021), used under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Habitat loss and degradation

As demonstrated by **Figure 1.2**, land use change and habitat loss are the biggest causes of decline and extinction of amphibian species (Collins, Crump, and Lovejoy, 2009; Harfoot *et al.*, 2021). In the second global amphibian assessment, agriculture is shown to be the most common cause of habitat loss and degradation threatening amphibians, followed by timber and plant harvesting, and infrastructure development (Luedtke *et al.*, 2023). A comprehensive meta-analysis of the responses of amphibians and reptiles to land use changes, indicated that almost all types of land use change have negative effects on herpetofauna, and that time elapsed does not reduce the effect of impacts, demonstrating a poor ability for species to recover (Cordier *et al.*, 2021). Historic patterns of amphibian decreases reflect the major impact of habitat destruction in Europe during the mid-twentieth century, contrasting more recent declines seen elsewhere (Houlahan *et al.*, 2000). The presence of road traffic impacts amphibians significantly, especially during breeding migration (Hels and Buchwald, 2001). For example, amphibian species richness in Ontario ponds in Canada was affected by forest cover and road density, the effects of which were seen up to thousands of metres from ponds (Houlahan and Findlay, 2003). Fragmentation of important amphibian habitats such as wetlands will also impact populations, as amphibians need to securely move between areas to find resources such as mates or food sources (Joly, Morand, and Cohas, 2003; Zamberletti *et al.*, 2018).

Climate change

As climate change continues to cause an increase in the average global temperature, as well as other effects such as an increase in extreme weather events, ectothermic organisms such as amphibians that regulate their metabolism using their external environment will undoubtedly be affected (Gibbons and Scott, 2000; Carey and Alexander, 2003; Rohr and Palmer, 2013; Kirkpatrick Baird *et al.*, 2023). The increasing frequency of wildfires associated with a warming climate, are also of growing concern to herpetofauna, through habitat destruction and direct mortality (Beranek *et al.*, 2023). The need to conserve water for amphibians is also greater than other organisms as their semi-permeable skin provides little resistance to evaporative water loss, which may increase as temperatures rise, increasing their susceptibility to climate change (Heatwole *et al.*, 1969; Spotila, 1972; Lertzman-Lepofsky *et*

al., 2020). Foden *et al.* (2013) predict that with mid-range climate-warming scenarios for 2050, 15–37% of amphibian species will be ‘committed to extinction’ globally. Evidence of these climate driven declines can already be found. For example, at La Selva biological research station in Costa Rica, amphibian populations have declined over a 35-year period. Whitfield *et al.* (2007) attributed these declines to reductions in amphibian microhabitats resulting from climate change. Recent climatic warming and the subsequent desiccation of wetland habitats have caused declines in numbers of four amphibian species native to Yellowstone National Park in the United States of America (USA) (McMenamin, Hadly and Wright, 2008). There is also evidence that increased global temperatures could be responsible for the spread of amphibian diseases into new climates. In 2006, Pounds *et al.*, proposed the ‘chytrid thermal optimum hypothesis’ based on a complex relationship between increased temperature and increased growth of chytridiomycosis in tropical habitats. Temperature is also related to development rate in amphibians, and so increased global temperatures could affect amphibian metamorphosis (Arietta and Skelly, 2021). It is also important that phenological shifts in the breeding season of amphibian populations are considered in the context of pesticide exposures and agricultural activities. For example, Lötters *et al.*, (2014) show that as the breeding season of amphibian species in Germany has shifted earlier in the year due to climate change, they experience reduced glyphosate exposure, and that a shift of one month could reduce glyphosate exposure of *R. temporaria* by 50 %. Climate change and its effects on productivity and crop yields may also cause changes in agricultural practices, and so this is a factor that must also be considered within the field of amphibian ecotoxicology and conservation (Palikhe, 2007; Kattwinkel *et al.*, 2011; Delcour, Spanoghe and Uyttendaele, 2015; Tudi *et al.*, 2021).

Disease

The role of disease in amphibian declines is well studied. In particular, the chytrid fungus chytridiomycosis (both *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* or Bd, and *Batrachochytrium salamandivorans* or Bsal), ranaviruses, and parasites (*Saprolegnia* and *Ribeiroia*) are most commonly studied (Carey, 1993; Daszak *et al.*, 1999; Berger, Speare and Hyatt, 1999; Kiesecker, Blaustein and Belden, 2001; Johnson and Speare, 2003; Blaustein *et al.*, 2012). *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (Bd) and *Ranavirus* are of particular concern, with Bsal becoming more of an emerging concern in the past few years (Van Rooij *et al.*, 2015).

Endemic pathogens have been spread through the global amphibian trade to areas where native amphibians have little to no natural immunity, which can cause widespread disease and mortality (Fisher and Garner, 2007; Schloegel *et al.*, 2009). Bd is associated with anuran declines and extinctions in Australia, Africa, Central, South, and North America (Collins, 2010). The presence of other anthropogenic stressors affecting amphibian populations can reduce immune function, and so increase disease susceptibility (Haislip *et al.*, 2012). There is no general consensus amongst herpetologists regarding factors that drive epidemiological patterns in amphibian populations, and the complexity and specificity of the ecological interactions between the environment, the host, and the pathogen makes conservation management challenging (Bienentreu and Lesbarrères, 2020).

Invasive species

The aquatic life-history stages of amphibians are particularly sensitive to the introduction of invasive species, as many amphibians breed in isolated freshwater ecosystems such as ponds where large predators normally are scarce (Cox and Lima, 2006). Studies show that when non-native species (such as fish or crayfish) are introduced, impacts on native amphibians include direct predation, reduced activity levels, use of different habitats, increased use of refuges, smaller body sizes at metamorphosis, higher mortality, present with more injuries, and higher competition for resources (Collins, Crump, and Lovejoy, 2009). For example, introduced rainbow and brook trout contributed to the decline of mountain yellow-legged frogs (*Rana muscosa*) in California, USA (Vredenburg, 2004). Invasive amphibians, such as tadpoles of the Indian bullfrog (*Hoplobatrachus tigerinus*) which prey upon native tadpoles, impair the survival of endemic frog larvae (Mohanty and Measey, 2019) and introduction of invasive species (such as fish) can disrupt host-pathogen equilibria and lead to disease events (Rosa *et al.*, 2022). Mendelson *et al.* (2006) and Schloegel *et al.* (2009) both cite trade of amphibians as a source of ‘pathogen pollution’, and Fisher & Garner (2007) report that 28 species of introduced frogs and salamanders were found to be carrying Bd.

Overexploitation

Amphibians make popular pets, and while trade in live amphibians has increased drastically over the last few decades, trade for pets in particular is responsible for the majority of amphibian introductions beyond their native range (Kraus, 2009; Carpenter *et al.*, 2014; Mohanty and Measey, 2019). Amphibians, and in particular frogs, are also an important food source in many cultures. For example, the mountain chicken frog (*Leptodactylus fallax*) was previously found on several different Caribbean islands, and is now limited to just the islands of Dominica and Montserrat (Daltry, 2002). While several factors have likely contributed to the decline of the mountain chicken frog, it was also the national dish of Dominica and historically overcollected for food (Nicholson *et al.*, 2020). A Food and Agriculture report from the UN reached the conclusion that almost 95% of the world demand for frog legs and frog products came from wild stocks, with 11 species being the main harvesting focus (Teixeira, Mello and dos Santos, 2001). The international frog leg trade spanned over 30 countries and was worth over \$49 million (US) (Teixeira, Mello and dos Santos, 2001). This lucrative market for amphibians to be traded internationally results in amphibians not only being over collected from the wild for various purposes but increases the risk of releasing species into non-native habitats where they may become invasive. It also makes the passage of amphibian disease between different countries more likely.

Other potential causes of decline

Increased levels of UVb radiation have been cited as a cause of amphibian mortality, however there is little evidence linking it to widespread declines, and captive studies that irradiate amphibians usually do so at levels well above that found in the wild, often without providing refugia (Beebee and Griffiths, 2005; Whatley *et al.*, 2020). Acid rain and acidification of aquatic habitats is another hypothetical cause of amphibian declines, although there is not enough evidence to link increased pH levels to widespread declines (Vertucci and Corn, 1996).

Pollution

Pollution that affects an ecosystem can take many forms, such as light pollution (Wise, 2007; Hölker *et al.*, 2010, 2023), sound pollution (Lengagne, 2008; Grace and Noss, 2018), or electromagnetic radiation (Arihilar and Arihilar, 2019). However, the biggest area of concern is chemical pollution, such as that from agricultural run-off and from the pharmaceutical industry. It has been suggested that global amphibian declines first began in the 1990s, however synthetic pesticide use has increased dramatically since the 1950s, so it is possible that amphibians may have been in decline since then (National Research Council, 1993). A meta-analysis of the effects of chemical pollution by Egea-Serrano *et al.* (2012) revealed that pollutant exposure in amphibians has negative effects at environmentally relevant levels. However, research investigating the effects of chemicals on amphibians is comparatively recent (Collins and Storfer, 2003). Amphibians are particularly vulnerable to chemical pollution due to the semi-permeable nature of their skin, and the extensive amount of their life cycle spent in or around bodies of water (Quaranta *et al.*, 2009; Hayes *et al.*, 2010). Both aquatic and terrestrial stages of amphibian life cycles have the potential to be exposed to contaminants, although the most vulnerable stage varies according to the natural history of a species. For example, larvae are unable to leave a contaminated water body until post-metamorphosis (Costa *et al.*, 2023).

Pollution has been demonstrated to cause reductions in amphibian populations. For example, historical pesticide use has directly linked the application of organophosphates and carbamates with the declines of the Yosemite toad (*Bufo canorus*), California red-legged frog (*Rana aurora draytonii*), foothill yellow-legged frog (*R. boylei*), Cascades frog (*R. cascadae*), and the mountain yellow-legged frog (*R. muscosa*) in California (Davidson, 2004). Direct mortality, such as cases where large numbers of organisms are found dead, are more obvious indications of problems within an ecosystem, however sublethal effects can remain undetected. At sublethal levels, chemical pollution in the environment can have effects on the health and reproduction of amphibians (Polo-Cavia, Burraco and Gomez-Mestre, 2016). The diversity of pollutants and their modes of exposure and action is vast, and so it is unsurprising that the effects seen in amphibians vary greatly (Egea-Serrano *et al.*, 2012). Pollutants, such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) can bioaccumulate and biomagnify from exposed prey items which are consumed by amphibians,

and then accumulate within different amphibian tissues depending on the properties of the pollutants (Ding *et al.*, 2022). The sublethal effects of chemical exposure can include decreased growth and development (Baker, Bancroft and Garcia, 2013), increased frequency of developmental abnormalities (Haas *et al.*, 2018), susceptibility to diseases (North *et al.*, 2015), and behavioural alterations (Reviewed in Sievers *et al.*, 2019). These effects are often less immediately obvious, and so may go undetected for some time, leading to long term amphibian health crises and a loss of recruitment over time which is crucial for population stability (reviewed in Hayes *et al.*, 2010). Decreased recruitment can result directly from a failure to reproduce or from developmental issues that lead to an inability to reproduce, such as reproductive organs or structures not developing normally. Developmental failures that do not lead to death can also directly decrease recruitment, for example, limb deformities or decreased growth could limit reproductive potential of an individual without killing individuals directly. Studies comparing which characteristics affect reproductive success in a species are useful to identify how changes to these characteristics from pollution exposure could affect reproduction and subsequent population recruitment (Hayes *et al.*, 2010).

Chemical pollution can enter the water bodies which amphibians inhabit via multiple sources. Ground and surface waters receive different forms of chemical pollution arising from anthropogenic activities. Toxicants associated with these activities include pesticides and fertilisers in run-off from agricultural areas, and pollutants from domestic and industrial wastewater discharges (Holt, Phillips and Bates, 2000). A study by White *et al.* (2023) reported higher concentrations of copper, lead, zinc, and total petroleum hydrocarbons within underpasses designed to mitigate fragmentation of habitat for *Triturus cristatus* (great crested newts), demonstrating the need for conservation measures to be more considerate of pollution exposure. In the amphibian literature, particular attention has been paid to the effects of plant protection products (PPPs) and other agrochemicals. Amphibians are at high risk of exposure to these chemicals since breeding ponds are often situated in or near to agricultural land-use areas (Bishop *et al.*, 1999; Taylor *et al.*, 2005; Hayes *et al.*, 2010). Roughly 360 million kg of pesticide formulations are used every year within the EU, with only a small proportion of what is applied reaching the target organism due to spray drift and run off (Pimentel, 1995; Reichenberger *et al.*, 2007; Zhang, Luo and Goh, 2018; Leeb *et al.*, 2022). The remaining pesticides can end up in agricultural ponds, which are important amphibian habitats (Knutson *et al.*, 2004). The toxicity of pesticides to amphibians can depend on many different factors,

such as the active ingredients, additives to the pesticide formulation, previous pesticide exposures, species, and developmental stage (Mann, Bidwell and Tyler, 2003; Johansson, Piha, Kylin and Merila, 2006; Biga and Blaustein, 2013; Hua, Morehouse and Relyea, 2013; Wagner *et al.*, 2017). A growing body of literature shows that contaminants are widespread in freshwater lakes and streams, often in trace concentrations. For example, concentrations of aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA), a metabolite of the controversial herbicide glyphosate, has been shown to alter embryonic development in the spined toad (*Bufo spinosus*) at concentrations as low as 0.07 µl/L, well within the range found in the environment (Cheron and Brischoux, 2020). Co-stressors may also increase the adverse effects of pollutant exposure on amphibians (Wagner and Lötters, 2013b).

Microplastics

Microplastics (either formed from the breakdown of plastic products or manufactured as microplastics) are of global environmental concern, and have been found in environments ranging from the icecaps to the deep ocean (Allen *et al.*, 2019; Barboza *et al.*, 2020). For recent reviews of the current body of literature regarding microplastics in amphibians, see da Costa Araújo *et al.*, (2021); Balestrieri *et al.*, (2022); Burgos-Aceves *et al.*, (2022); and Szkudlarek *et al.*, (2023). Plastics and microplastics can act as vectors for chemical contaminants in the aquatic environment through the sorption of contaminants into the plastic (Burgos-Aceves *et al.*, 2022). This is of particular concern with microplastics, as their small size means they are easily ingested by organisms such as tadpoles, and chemical contaminants then released internally (Fred-Ahmadu *et al.*, 2020). Microplastics have been shown to accumulate within amphibian larvae through consumption during the scraping of algae, thereby demonstrating how chemical pollutants could be ingested by amphibian larvae (Boyero *et al.*, 2020). There is a lack of data on the effects of microplastics on anuran adults. Microplastic exposure can also cause direct effects – exposure to 60 mg/L of sterile polyethylene (PE) microplastic particles for 7 days caused reduced growth and development, and erythrocyte and cytoplasmic abnormalities, in Cuvier’s weeping frog (*Physalaemus cuvieri*) tadpoles (da Costa Araújo *et al.*, 2020). Microplastic exposure can also cause mortality at high enough concentrations (1800 particles/ml polystyrene microplastics in the common midwife toad (*Alytes obstetricans*; Boyero *et al.*, 2020).

Metals

Although naturally present within aquatic ecosystems, essential and non-essential trace metals vary in their concentrations and origins, mostly due to anthropogenic changes, and can act as chemical pollutants (Tchounwou *et al.*, 2012). The most common sources of metal contamination in the environment come from industry, mining, and agriculture (Trudeau *et al.*, 2020). In addition to toxic effects, when amphibians are exposed to metal contamination, some metals can act as endocrine disruptors (Alves da Silva *et al.*, 2018). For reviews of metal exposure in amphibians as well as associated reproductive and developmental endpoints, see Slaby *et al.*, (2019), and Hill *et al.*, (2022). For example, it has been suggested that the decline of the northern dusky salamander (*Desmognathus fuscus fuscus*) population in the Acadia National Park (Maine, USA) is related to mercury and aluminium leaching, although the specific mechanisms of metal action were not discussed (Bank *et al.*, 2006). As with other threats to amphibians, metals occur in natural environments alongside other stressors. Peluso *et al.* (2023) report the presence of metals, pesticides, and veterinary medications found within a stream running through crop fields and cattle breeding activities in Buenos Aires, Argentina. Exposure to the stream water caused lethal and sublethal effects in the Argentine toad (*Rhinella arenarum*).

Tadpoles are particularly at risk from metal pollution due to the leaching of agrochemicals and industrial runoff into natal breeding ponds (Arslan and GÜngördü, 2024). Exposure to endocrine disrupting metal pollution in tadpoles has been shown to disrupt metamorphosis, alter the length of development, and affect the mass and morphometrics of tadpoles (Tyler-Jones, Beattie, and Aston, 1989; Sharma and Patino, 2008; Barry, 2011; Dovick *et al.*, 2020; Arslan and GÜngördü, 2024; de Albuquerque *et al.*, 2024). The toxic effects of metals on tadpoles can include mortality, bioaccumulation, changes to the gut microbiome, hepatocyte degeneration, increased stress biomarkers, behavioural changes, and reduced respiratory function (Rice *et al.*, 1999; Rissoli *et al.*, 2016; Ya *et al.*, 2019; Buncharoen *et al.*, 2022; Murthy *et al.*, 2023; Arslan and GÜngördü, 2024; de Albuquerque *et al.*, 2024).

It can be difficult to distinguish between specific endocrine disrupting effects and toxic effects as these effects often co-occur, and the concentration and composition of different

metal compounds can also have different effects in other species. In addition, some metals such as lead, copper, and cadmium are well studied with a large body of associated literature. In contrast, some metals such as bismuth and magnesium have little to no relevant associated literature, so their effects are largely unknown. This can make the interpretation of the specific effects of metals challenging. The effects of particular metals on tadpoles is discussed in greater detail in a later Chapter of this thesis.

Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs)

A group of pollutants of particular concern are the endocrine disrupting chemicals (or EDCs), as they interfere with hormone function within the endocrine system. Although exposure to EDCs can affect all endocrine processes, this review will only focus on the reproductive and metamorphic endocrinology of EDC exposure in anurans. EDCs act on the hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal (HPG), -thyroid (HPT) and/or -adrenal/interrenal (HPA/I) axes, which have crucial roles in reproduction, growth, and development (Duarte-Guterman *et al.*, 2009; Duarte-Guterman, Navarro-Martín and Trudeau, 2014; Flood and Langlois, 2014; Dang, 2022; Norris, 2024). The HPT axis regulates amphibian metamorphosis, and the HPA/I axis is involved in physiological stress responses. The HPG axis regulates gonadal development and gametogenesis through production of sex steroid hormones. Disruption to the HPG axis in vertebrates can lead to adverse reproductive outcomes, including decreased fecundity, fertility, or fitness, and can have multigenerational effects (Ankley *et al.*, 2010; Kadhim *et al.*, 2024). For more detail on the anuran reproductive system, please refer to **Anuran Reproduction**.

In anurans, adverse reproductive outcomes following exposure to EDCs are well documented in the laboratory, particularly with model *Xenopus* species, although a wider breadth of research using different amphibian species is needed (Hayes *et al.*, 2010; Ziková *et al.*, 2017; Orton *et al.*, 2018; Regnault *et al.*, 2018; Rozenblut-Koscisty and Ogielska, 2018). There are few data pertaining to the types and quantities of EDCs in the water bodies used by amphibians for spawning and larval development. One reason for this is that many amphibians avoid flowing waters and large lakes with little shoreline vegetation, preferring smaller, shallower pools instead (Wells, 2010). The functional nature of different pollutants

may be different in these water bodies than in large lakes, lochs, and rivers, yet the former have been much less frequently surveyed for EDCs than the latter, and much less is known about the associated water chemistry of ponds compared to other freshwater systems (Lorenz *et al.*, 2018; Biggs and Williams, 2024). This may be partially due to the temporary nature of some of these bodies of water and is an area that should be prioritised in future research. Amphibians living in anthropogenically influenced landscapes often breed in privately owned ponds, in particular residential garden ponds (Hassall, 2014). These kinds of water bodies are also rarely included in EDC surveys, despite the fact that they may be particularly exposed to certain contaminants, such as those leaking from untreated wastewater (Smits, Skelly and Bolden, 2014).

Even less is known about EDCs in the sediment of these ponds, even though many chemicals persist much longer in sediment than in water, and sediment analyses can be used to identify past pollution events. Although the chemicals absorbed to sediment are considered to have little bioavailability, they can get re-suspended by disturbances to the pond bottom and re-enter the food chain via bottom-grazing and filter-feeding animals such as the larvae of many amphibian species (Chapman and Anderson, 2005; Knott *et al.*, 2009; Wells, 2010). Sediments represent important elements of aquatic ecosystems, playing several roles in maintaining their structure and function. Sediments interact with biota and provide habitats and substrate for a wide variety of aquatic organisms (Palmer *et al.*, 2000). These organisms also contribute to the degradation of the sediment which contains many important organic and inorganic substances that will later become bioavailable to the water column and the subsequent trophic chains of aquatic ecosystems (Fenchel *et al.*, 2012; Cardoso *et al.*, 2019). Despite the importance of sediment, data pertaining to its quality indicates that globally, sediments are contaminated by ‘diverse toxic and bioaccumulative substances’ according to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2001). Bókony *et al.*, (2018) found a wide range of contaminants (including pesticides and pharmaceuticals) in sediment samples from common toad (*Bufo bufo*) habitats in Hungary. In this sense, a sediment toxicity test could be considered as a first line of evidence within ecological risk assessments (ERA) and can be used to assess the presence of chemical contaminants, and the risk they pose to aquatic organisms.

Prolonged exposure to EDCs may also result in a change in resource allocation within anurans such as adopting a ‘fast living strategy’. Fast living strategies are utilised when environmental conditions are suboptimal, so individuals will put more investment into reproduction to increase fitness at the cost of the individuals’ own health and survival (Schultner *et al.*, 2013). This trade-off reduces longevity, growth, future fertility, and immune function (Reniers, 2015). This has been hypothesised in wild individuals of the Mongolian toad (*Bufo raddei*) exposed to endocrine disrupting heavy metals (mainly copper, zinc, lead, and cadmium), resulting in these organisms exhibiting changes in sex characteristics that suggested a competitive breeding advantage (Guo *et al.*, 2018). Male individuals from the polluted site displayed calling behaviour, larger breeding glands, larger forearm size, and individuals started breeding earlier than at the control site. However, these individuals also presented with a much lower body condition. Brady *et al.* (2019) found that wild wood frog (*Rana sylvatica*) individuals collected from roadside populations exhibited better locomotion and a higher measure of fitness (such as increased offspring survival). In order to understand the role that EDCs may have in the disruption of amphibian development, then an understanding of how metamorphosis and reproduction occurs in anurans is needed. Agrochemicals can affect multiple hormone axes at once, and so the effects of EDC exposure on cross talk between these axes as well as compounding effects need to be considered (Trudeau *et al.*, 2020). Kloas *et al.*, (2024) suggest that the accepted definition of endocrine disruptors as ‘exogenous substances’ by the WHO should be adapted to include other sources of endocrine disruption, such as artificial light at night (ALAN), decomposition of plants, and parasitic infections. It is important to consider the effects of endocrine disruption within the context of the wider environment, especially concerning wild data.

Anuran metamorphosis

Overview of metamorphosis

In order to interpret the effects of EDCs on metamorphosis and identify suitable tools for biomonitoring, it is crucial to understand the mechanisms of anuran metamorphosis, and other potential factors that may influence anuran development. Amphibian metamorphosis is the transformation of an aquatic larval amphibian, to a terrestrial or semi-terrestrial adult form via biochemical, morphological, and behavioural changes. Metamorphosis is a natural

part of the ecology of most anuran species, but some species have alternate life histories, such as giving birth to live precocial young, for example the Surinam toad (*Pipa pipa*) (Rabb and Rabb, 1960). In order to better allow the study and comparison of different stages of metamorphosis, several methodologies for the staging of anuran metamorphosis have been developed for different species, such as Nieuwkoop-Faber staging for *Xenopus* spp. (Faber and Nieuwkoop, 1994), and Gosner staging (Gosner, 1960) (see **Appendix 1.1** for an illustration of the later stages of Gosner staging utilised throughout this thesis). It is of note however, that these staging tables are based on growth and development under stable conditions with unlimited resources, and so may differ from growth and development seen in wild specimens (Wells, 2010). For a recent review of anuran metamorphosis and the factors affecting it, see Nizam *et al.*, (2023).

Positive correlations have been seen between adult body size and size at metamorphosis, particularly in the family Ranidae which transform at a large size compared to their adult body size when compared to Bufonidae and Hylidae (Werner, 1986). A small metamorphic size can also be disadvantageous in more arid environments due to rapid rates of evaporative water loss due to a greater surface area to volume ratio (Newman and Dunham, 1994). Aquatic larvae are unable to predict terrestrial conditions based on the conditions of the aquatic natal environment, and so can only respond and adapt to immediate aquatic conditions. For example, in a rapidly desiccating pond, emerging metamorphs are more likely to be surrounded by a hot, dry environment. Nevertheless, the tadpole has no choice but to metamorphose and leave the water quickly into unfavourable environments, or succumb to desiccation (Wells, 2010). The timing of metamorphosis and size of metamorphs shows considerable plasticity, as tadpoles have the ability to speed up or slow down hatching and metamorphosis to enhance their chances of survival through plastic developmental responses. This however comes at a cost, and trade-offs often have to be made in their developed morphometrics, for example shorter legs, longer arms, shorter body length, reduced mass, and narrower heads, resulting in poorer locomotion and reduced fitness (Ficetola and De Bernardi, 2006, Capellán and Nicieza, 2007, Warkentin, 2011, Kinsey *et al.*, 2023). There is natural variation in metamorphosis within individuals even from the same clutch and under favourable conditions, which likely reduces competition at different stages of metamorphosis amongst conspecifics (Wells, 2010). There is also variation in the egg size and energy content between eggs laid by females, but it is unknown how important this is in determining

metamorphic success, as results vary between species (Crump, 1984, Walls and Altig, 1986, Kaplan, 1992, Tejedo and Reques, 1992). Depending on the species, some individuals who start the metamorphic process with slow growth will never catch up to faster growth individuals, and some are able to catch up (Semlitsch and Caldwell, 1982, Travis and Trexler, 1986). Chronic exposure to unfavourable conditions such as chemical pollutants across populations and generations of a species could have negative impacts on the overall health and fitness of populations through the continued recruitment of disadvantaged metamorphs.

Morphological changes from tadpole to adult

The lifecycle of most temperate anurans involves eggs laid in water bodies hatching into tadpoles, which (at the earlier stages) are characterised by long tails with fins, no limbs, no skeletal structures, and specialised mouthparts and internal anatomy that suits their aquatic ecology. Tadpoles undergo a process of transformation into an adult anuran, characterised by no tail, forelimbs and hindlimbs, ossified skeletal structures, a mouth, and internal anatomy that suits a transitional ecology between aquatic and terrestrial habitats. Therefore, metamorphosis involves major changes to almost every part of their anatomy (Nizam *et al.*, 2023). Such changes include the degradation and reabsorption of the tail, the emergence of the legs and arms, the ossification of the skeleton, and transition from the primary use of gills to respiration occurring using the lungs and skin via cutaneous respiration (Gilbert, 2000, Yaoita, 2019). The keratinised teeth on oral discs used by tadpoles to scrape food particles are replaced by a mouth and tongue, as well as a shortening of the intestinal tract to help transition from a more herbivorous diet to a more carnivorous one (Alford, Richards, and McDonald, 2001, Noel and Hu, 2018). During the later stages of metamorphosis while these dramatic changes to the digestive system take place, the tadpole will stop eating (Bender *et al.*, 2018). Throughout this process (under favourable conditions), tadpole mass will steadily increase during growth before reaching a peak and then decreasing as the tail is reabsorbed (Wells, 2010). Metamorphosis and the associated morphometrics of tadpoles undergoing this process can be affected by many different biotic and abiotic factors, such as temperature, water level, food, and stocking density, which can affect tadpole morphometrics as well as the timing of the larval period and subsequent metamorphic climax (Albecker, Strobel and Womack, 2023, Nizam *et al.*, 2023). Tadpoles also have the ability to overwinter, whereby instead of leaving the water into potentially unfavourable conditions, they can remain in

ponds as tadpoles (even if at appropriate size to commence metamorphosis) and grow larger, ready to emerge from the pond early in spring (Walsh, Downie, and Monaghan, 2016). The exact mechanism of this phenomenon is unknown, but there are many cases of tadpoles with genetic abnormalities (for example, cannot produce thyroxine, a hormone involved in metamorphosis) that prevents them from undergoing metamorphosis at all, suggesting a genetic cause (Dodd and Dodd, 1976). In Scotland in particular, populations at high altitudes such as in the Cairngorms, and at high latitudes such as on Shetland, overwinter habitually (Venables and Venables, 1955, Archibald and Downie, 1996).

The endocrine system and its role in metamorphosis

The process of metamorphosis is under endocrine control via the hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis and the hypothalamus-pituitary-interrenal (HPI) axis (Norris and Lopez, 2011). The HPT involves the release of corticotropin releasing factor (CRF) in the hypothalamus, which stimulates the release of thyrotropin, also known as thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), in the pituitary. TSH then stimulates the production of two thyroid hormones triiodothyronine (T₃) and thyroxine (T₄). These thyroid hormones are responsible for directing metamorphosis. Circulating levels of thyroid hormones are low in the early stages of metamorphosis, increasing and reaching its peak at metamorphic climax (the latest stages during the transition to a terrestrial lifestyle), but the sensitivity of target tissues to these thyroid hormones varies (Wells, 2010). The actions of these hormones is mediated by interactions with other hormones, including prolactin (PRL), produced in the pituitary gland, and corticosterone, produced in the adrenal glands (Hayes, 1997, Wells, 2010). PRL has been shown to inhibit metamorphosis in younger larvae, and to be involved in metamorphosis in older tadpoles (Norris and Lopez, 2011). Growth is stimulated by PRL, which increases the intestinal absorption of amino acids and glucose from food (Wells, 2010). CRF also stimulates the release of corticosterone production in the adrenal glands through the stress axis, which increases escape reaction times and other behavioural and physiological responses to stressful conditions (Rose, 2005). When close to metamorphic climax, CRF release can result in an increase in foraging behaviours and mobilisation of energy reserves in order to accelerate growth and development and escape unfavourable conditions (Crespi and Denver, 2004, 2005). CRF also increases corticosterone levels in tadpoles exposed to a range

of stressors such as desiccation, increased competition, and reduced food availability (Hayes, 1997, Glennemeier and Denver, 2002, Boorse and Denver, 2004, Crespi and Denver, 2005). For reviews on the role of the thyroid axis in amphibian development and reproduction, see Fort *et al.*, (2007) and Carr and Patiño (2011).

Endocrine disruption and metamorphosis

As metamorphosis is heavily influenced by the endocrine system, these processes are subject to the effects of endocrine disrupting pollution. Endocrine disrupting chemicals may alter the synthesis or release of these hormones, such as the transport of hormones to their target tissues, the actions of hormones on their target tissues, or the rates at which hormones are metabolised or excreted, and this may disrupt metamorphosis. For example, exposure to 14 mg/L sodium perchlorate, a thyroid inhibitor, over two weeks causes developmental delays in tadpoles of *Lithobates sylvatica* (wood frog) tadpoles at Gosner stage 25-30. Exposed tadpoles also reached metamorphic climax (Gosner stage 42) 11(±)3 days later than control groups (Bulaeva *et al.*, 2015). Exposure to 10-100 nM of the herbicide Acetochlor accelerates T₃ induced forelimb emergence in *X. laevis* (Crump *et al.*, 2002). Octylphenol (OP) is a degradation product of alkylphenol polyethoxylates (APEs) that are used in a variety of industrial processes such as plastic production. Exposure to OP at concentrations ranging from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻⁸ mol/L decreases body length and mass, and also slows tadpole development in the Chinese brown frog (*Rana chensinensis*) (Xie *et al.*, 2019). Exposure of bullfrogs (*Rana catesbeiana*) to three concentrations (234 µg/L, 468 µg/L, or 936 µg/L) of nonylphenol (an endocrine disruptor used in detergents and emulsifiers) combined with exogenous T₃ resulted in decreased cranial transformation rate, and a reduced rate of tail reabsorption at the highest exposures compared to controls, thereby having an inhibitory effect on metamorphic progression (Christensen *et al.*, 2005). The frog embryo teratogenesis assay-Xenopus (FETAX) assay has been developed to study the early growth and development of *Xenopus laevis*, a model species. This assay has been used to study the disrupting effects of EDCs, but the endpoints of this assay mostly focus on general toxicity rather than sublethal effects (Hoke and Ankley, 2005, Gutleb *et al.*, 2007, Bosisio *et al.*, 2009, Cardoso-Vera *et al.*, 2017).

Environmental influences on metamorphosis

The timing, duration, and resulting morphology of metamorphosis can be affected by several different environmental factors (Albecker, Strobel and Womack, 2023). When assessing potential biomarkers for endocrine disruption of growth and development, it is important to understand how different environmental factors affect metamorphosis in order to allow proper interpretation and evaluation of results, especially in a changing anthropogenic environment. This process is highly variable between different species, so a thorough understanding of the ecology of a particular species is key. This section does not represent all environmental factors that can affect metamorphosis, but the most commonly studied and therefore best understood factors. It is also important to note that in a wild environment, there is likely to be multiple stressors co-occurring at any one time.

Temperature

A long term study of common toads (*Bufo bufo*) in England looked at the SVL of emerging toadlets from 2003 to 2009. During this timeframe, the days of spawn deposition varied due to different environmental conditions in different years by up to 90 days. The duration of the tadpole stage was negatively correlated with the date of spawn deposition, and mean pond water temperature. Although duration of the tadpole stage was longer when deposition occurred earlier, and tadpoles emerged with a lower body condition than when spawning time was late. Body condition was also highly correlated to the temperature of the pond water, with warmer water increasing body condition compared to cooler rearing conditions; this was hypothesised to be due to an increase in ‘body reserves’ (Reading, 2010). Cold temperatures also affect tadpole morphometrics: Álvarez and Nicieza, (2002a) found that larval body mass varied inversely with temperature between 12-22 °C in Iberian painted frogs (*Discoglossus galganoi*). Low temperatures have been shown to inhibit the production of thyroxin and reduces the sensitivity of target tissues to thyroxin (Smith-Gill and Berven, 1979, Suzuki *et al.*, 2016). These results suggest variable effects of temperature on different species, and that both increases and decreases in temperature away from an optimal rearing temperature range should be considered.

Diet

Tadpoles that are fed high protein diets grow and develop more quickly, and in other vertebrate groups thyroid function is linked to dietary protein intake (Kupferberg, 1997). Tadpoles fed on filamentous green algae with epiphytic diatoms developed faster and metamorphosed at larger sizes than tadpoles raised on other diets, and during choice experiments, tadpoles foraged selectively on algal foods that resulted in the most rapid growth and development. Álvarez and Nicieza, (2002a) also found that a carnivorous diet resulted in bigger metamorphs compared to plant based diets. A dietary study of the Yucatan casque-headed treefrog (*Tripurion petasatus*) showed that individuals raised on a high-quality diet of fish experienced increased growth, a short larval period, low mortality, and a larger size at metamorphosis and as metamorphs; however, the duration of metamorphosis was shorter in individuals fed a more natural omnivorous diet (Jacobson *et al.*, 2019). The effect of diet on metamorphosis likely depends on the ecology of individual species, and whether the species is known to engage in cannibalistic behaviour, but generally a higher protein diet leads to improved body condition at metamorphosis (Jacobson *et al.*, 2019).

Overcrowding

Tadpoles raised under crowded conditions exhibit slower growth rates, longer larval periods, and smaller body size at metamorphosis, and when food supply and quality is increased to reduce competition for resources, the same results are observed (Morey and Reznick, 2001, Saidapur and Girish, 2001, Laugen, Laurila, and Merilä, 2002, Álvarez and Nicieza, 2002b, Girish and Saidapur, 2003). Lab studies in this area have been criticised for utilising stocking densities of tadpoles that are too high, and so not environmentally relevant, as well as showing biases towards discovering competitive effects by housing tadpoles in enclosures that are highly simplified (Smith, 1999, Skelly and Kiesecker, 2001). However, studies looking at the effects of overcrowding in more environmentally-relevant field enclosures found similar results, including in *R. temporaria*, so this is likely still an important factor in metamorphic growth and development for wild tadpoles (Goater, 1994, Tejedo and Reques, 1994, Loman, 2002). Studies have demonstrated that water conditioned by tadpoles can have inhibitory effects on growth even when no other tadpoles are present, suggesting that it is a

tadpole secretion that is responsible for growth limitation, but the exact mechanisms of this are debated (Richards, 1958, Akin, 1966, Gromko, Mason and Smith-Gill, 1973, Semlitsch and Caldwell, 1982, Waldman, 1986).

Predation

Predation studies in tadpoles can be divided into two categories: caged studies where either the tadpoles or predators are caged so that the only contact between tadpole and predator involves visual and/or chemical cues, or lethal predator studies where active predation is allowed. In a review of how predators affect metamorphosis, Relyea (2007) states that lethal predator studies produce a wide variety of outcomes. In contrast, in caged predator studies chemical cues rarely induce the expected stress outcomes of smaller sizes at metamorphosis, or reductions in time taken to reach metamorphosis, although there are exceptions (Newman, 1987, Hagman *et al.*, 2009, Stamper *et al.*, 2009). For example, water frog (*Rana ridibunda*), tadpoles exposed to caged *Aeshna* dragonfly larvae lost mass through metamorphosis faster than a control group, and froglets developed shorter, more muscular legs capable of achieving 5 % greater hopping distance, thereby utilising developmental plasticity to induce defence mechanisms (Buskirk and Saxer, 2001). Predation threat can also alter the shape of tadpole tails (shallower tail fins) in order to escape predation more easily, partially through plasticity and partially through predator induced selection (Van Buskirk, McCollum and Werner, 1997, Van Buskirk and Mccollum, 2000). This highlights how not all morphological changes observed through metamorphic plasticity have negative consequences for fitness, but it is vital to understand these changes to allow accurate interpretation of results. In studies where time to metamorphosis is slowed, it is hypothesised that greater allocation of resources towards antipredator responses may account for increased time spent in the larval stages, rather than the expected strategy of early metamorphosis (Relyea, 2007). It is of note that it is possible that in cases where tadpoles are caged rather than predators, this may also lead to compounding effects on tadpole metamorphosis, and so this should be factored into experimental designs (Rose, 2014).

Desiccation

There is a variable amount of plasticity in tadpole development in response to the desiccation of ponds. In the Pacific horned frog (*Ceratophrys stolzmanni*), tadpoles were raised in three water level treatments: high, constant low, and decreasing. Tadpoles from the high water treatment had a higher growth rate than the other groups (up to 0.3 g per day), in contrast to the low and decreasing water treatment groups where metamorphosis was sped up, leading to a smaller body size and mass at metamorphosis (Székely *et al.*, 2017). Difference in length of larval period at low density in ephemeral compared to permanent ponds varies between species, but is approximately 1-2.5 days (3-6 % of total average larval period) in *R. temporaria*. This demonstrates a small amount of plasticity in metamorphic timing compared to a 50 % reduction in larval period observed in Eastern spadefoot toads (*Scaphiophus*) spp., a common model species for desiccation studies that inhabits dry areas (Newman, 1989, Denver, Mirhadi, and Phillips, 1998). This will vary the amount of tolerance a species has for desiccation risk, which is likely linked to the specific ecology of individual species. Another study looking at the compounding effects of food availability and desiccation in the painted frog (*Discoglossus pictus*) demonstrated that in the absence of adequate resources (food deprivation), the ability to respond and adapt to desiccation risk is lost. It is important when assessing a site to consider all environmental factors that could affect metamorphosis of tadpoles.

Anuran reproduction

In order to interpret the effects of reproductive EDCs and identify suitable tools for biomonitoring, it is crucial to understand the mechanisms of anuran reproduction and other potential factors that may influence their reproductive success. For a recent review of the anuran reproductive system, see Méndez-Tepepa *et al.*, (2023).

Environmental influences on reproduction

Reproduction in both explosive and prolonged breeders can be tied to abiotic factors such as rainfall, wind, and temperature, however biotic factors such as predation, competition, and

foraging prospects may be important as well (Wells, 2010). Amphibians rely on water bodies for oviposition because most larval species require a water body to survive until metamorphosis (Corben, Ingram and Tyler, 1974). Patterns of rainfall and temperature influence frequency of breeding in temperate species, which mostly reproduce after a period of prolonged rainfall and increasing temperatures (discontinuous), whereas tropical species typically reproduce all year (continuous). Temperate species begin oviposition between late winter and early spring, utilising both permanent and ephemeral water bodies (Delgado, Gutiérrez and Alonso-Bedate, 1989; Eikenaar *et al.*, 2012). Generally tropical species are not limited by the availability of water bodies, so an energetic trade-off is made between foraging, searching for a mate, and offspring provision. Males therefore compete for higher quality territories which either contain more food (less foraging time), or better breeding pools. In these cases, the quality of site or number of mates acquired could be used to indicate reproductive success (Pröhl, 2002). For a review of environmental influences on hormones and reproduction in amphibians, see Norris (2024).

Breeding dynamics

A diverse range of breeding strategies are employed by anurans (reviewed in Crump, 2015). Anurans also inhabit a wide range of habitats that drive the availability of breeding resources and display a range of parental care strategies (also reviewed in Crump, 2015). The social dynamics of anuran reproduction have previously been reviewed (Wells, 1977; Bateson, 1983), as have reproductive dynamics of temperate anurans (Hartel and Sas, 2007). Anurans are often categorised as either explosive or prolonged breeders, however this is more of a spectrum of reproductive strategies (Wells, 1977). On one end of the spectrum, explosively breeding species, such as *Rana temporaria*, have short breeding periods (scale of days-weeks) and may involve large gatherings of males engaging in scramble competitions. In these scenarios, take over events can occur and can also lead to females being drowned (Davies and Halliday, 1979). There is a certain amount of plasticity in the behaviour of explosively breeding species. For example, male cane toads (*Rhinella marina*) are more likely to amplex (a mating posture known as “amplexus”, where typically male frogs clasp females dorsally and position themselves so as to bring their cloacae in close proximity before coordinated gamete release) when exposed to the sound of other males calling as opposed to silence (Chuang, Bee and Kam, 2013; Clarke, Shine and Phillips, 2019). An

increase in population size increases levels of polygyny in the agile frog (*Rana latastei*), shifting from a more equal 1:1 mate distribution to a few individuals monopolising and outcompeting all others (Ficetola *et al.*, 2010). In enclosed breeding areas with a female biased sex ratio, male common toads were found in amplexus with larger females, which was positively correlated to fecundity indicating a degree of mate choice probably also occurs in explosive breeders (Arntzen, 1999).

On the other end of the spectrum, prolonged breeders have a longer breeding period (scale of weeks to months), whereby males compete in territories. Female choice drives mate selection as opposed to male aggression, resulting in lekking behaviour (Sherman, Sagvik and Olsson, 2010). Female choice has led to speciation in the Peters' dwarf frog (*Physalaemus petersi*), whereas divergence in male call types and a strong female preference for local call patterns has driven behavioural isolation, and therefore speciation (Boul and Ryan, 2004). Female choice may be based on energetically costly male calling behaviours (see **Calling and larynx physiology** for more details). Size assortative mating (mating of similar sizes) is considered to be an advantageous strategy, as cloaca positioning can be optimised for gamete release to increase fertilisation success. Several species employing explosive breeding strategies develop a large male size, which is advantageous for displacing other males in combat. In size assertive mating, such as in the Asiatic grass frog (*Rana chensinensis*), males that are larger than females are unable to maintain amplexus, so females kick them off leading to a female choice of mating partner (Lu *et al.*, 2010).

Sexual dimorphism and sexual selection

Sexual dimorphism is commonly documented in anurans, with 90% of females presenting larger in mass and length than their male counterparts, with the exception of certain secondary sex characteristics (SSCs) that may be larger in males, such as nuptial pads or forelimb structures (Wells, 2010; Goldberg *et al.*, 2024, see sections on **Nuptial pads**, **Forelimb morphometrics**, and **SSCs**). Sexual selection in a species will vary according to the ecology and natural history of the species. In general, males are more subject to sexual selection than females because of the differences in the way each sex invests energy and resource into gamete production, as the cost of producing sperm is lower than that of egg

production. There is also a difference in parental investment in gametes, and so the reproductive success of males is usually limited by the number of mates acquired, whereas reproductive success of females is limited by energy availability. This means that the reproductive potential of a male exceeds that of a female, and as females are a limited resource, they are the object of competition amongst males. Traits that enhance the ability of males to locate, attract, capture, and retain females will be favoured by sexual selection (Arnold, 1994). In lek species, traits associated with defence of mates or territories are more likely to use persuasion tactics such as body size, enlarged forelimbs, nuptial pads, and spines. In arboreal species such as dendrobatids this is less important, and the male's ability to persuade the females depends more on advertisement strategies such as calling (Wells, 2010).

The endocrine system and its role in reproduction

The mechanisms of reproduction are highly conserved across the vertebrate classes, but this Chapter will explore the specifics of anuran reproduction (Orton and Tyler, 2015). Reproduction is controlled via the Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Gonadal axis (the interaction between the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, and the gonads) producing steroid sex hormones derived from cholesterol (Trudeau *et al.*, 2022; Carr, 2024; Woodley and Leary, 2024). These can be divided into the androgens (male sex hormones) responsible for producing male sex characteristics, such as development of the testes and spermatogenesis, and the estrogens (female sex hormones) that produce female sex characteristics, such as development of the ovaries and oogenesis. The androgens testosterone (T), dihydrotestosterone (DHT), and 17 β -oestradiol (E2) are the main steroids involved in gonadal growth. In a cascade event, gonadotropin releasing hormone (GnRH) stimulates the production of the gonadotropins luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) from the pituitary gland in the brain, which themselves stimulate and regulate the production of steroid hormones such as T, DHT, and E2 (Norris and Lopez, 2011; Orton and Tyler, 2015). Disruption of the HPG axis has adverse reproductive outcomes in vertebrates, such as reduced fecundity, fertility, and fitness both in adults and in their offspring through intergenerational effects (Ankley *et al.*, 2010; Miccoli *et al.*, 2017). Reproduction and its associated breeding behaviours are largely controlled by hormone cycles. In male anurans, levels of androgens rise prior to breeding in order to promote maturation of the gonads and spermatogenesis (Narayan *et al.*, 2010a). In females, estrogens and progesterone interact to control reproductive processes

such as oogenesis (egg production) (Boyd, 1992). As the endocrine system is so interlinked with the reproductive system, EDCs can have profound effects on the reproductive health of anurans. It is important to be able to develop biomonitoring tools for identifying the potential causes and scale of exposure to EDCs.

Interactions between reproduction and the stress axis

The reproductive axis and the stress axis in amphibians are linked through the endocrine system. Comprehensive reviews on the amphibian reproductive endocrine system and its interaction with the stress endocrine system are available (Moore, Boyd and Kelley, 2005; Carr and Patiño, 2011; Carr, 2024). Stress can be defined as “a set of generalized physiological responses that are experienced by all organisms exposed to a variety of environmental challenges, such as temperature change or exposure to noise” (Selye, 1991). While stress is a normal, necessary physiological response needed to allow an organism to adapt to its environment, prolonged periods of stress may become chronic and exert negative effects on the physiological wellbeing of an individual. Stress responses include a wide range of physiological systems and behaviours, but the most common element is the activation of the hypothalamo–pituitary–interrenal (HPI) axis in amphibians, which is homologous to the hypothalamo–pituitary–adrenal axis in higher vertebrates (Rollins-Smith, 2001). The HPI axis consists of a combination of neural transmitters and hormone responses, and allows an individual to react to a stress event in a way that maximizes survival (Hill *et al.*, 2004). The first phase of HPI axis activation involves the central nervous system receiving signals that a stressor has occurred, and a stress response is needed. Signals are sent to the hypothalamus, where corticotrophin-releasing hormone is released. Corticotrophin-releasing-hormone travels through the hypothalamo–hypophyseal portal system to the anterior pituitary gland, where adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) is released. ACTH is released into blood circulation, where it travels to the interrenal cortex and stimulates the release of glucocorticoids (corticosterone in amphibians) (Narayan, 2013). Early studies have shown that fully aquatic amphibians produce cortisol as their primary glucocorticoid, while terrestrial or semi-terrestrial amphibians produce corticosterone as their primary glucocorticoid (Bern and Nandi, 1964; Nandi, 1967). In addition, recent reviews on the roles of the reproductive and stress endocrine systems in the ecological context of animal reproduction, behaviour, and survival are available (Wilczynski and Lynch, 2011; Creel *et*

al., 2013). For a comprehensive review of studies using non-invasive amphibian endocrinology biomarkers, see Narayan, (2013). For a review of the effects of EDC exposure on adrenal gland function, see Di Lorenzo *et al.* (2020).

Hormone concentrations are closely tied to the calling behaviour of anurans. In wild populations of the Bombay night frog (*Nyctibatrachus humayuni*), American green tree frog (*Hyla cinera*) and túngara frog (*Physalaemus pustulosus*), calling males had higher androgen levels and blacksmith tree frog (*Hypsiboas faber*) males with higher testosterone had increased responsiveness to social cues from other males in a chorus (Marler and Ryan, 1996; de Assis *et al.*, 2012; Leary and Harris, 2013; Joshi, Narayan, and Gramapurohit, 2017). Corticosterone concentrations did not vary with behaviour as uniformly as androgens across these species; no difference in corticosterone concentration was found between calling and non-calling Bombay tree frogs and túngara frog males, whereas blacksmith tree frog males with higher corticosterone levels displayed with higher calling rates. Contrastingly, male American green tree frogs that did not call (also known as satellites), had increased corticosterone concentrations. Both plasma androgen and corticosterone concentrations were higher in cane toads (*Bufo marinus*) found in amplexus, than from individuals found on their own, indicating higher reproductive success in male competition (Orchinik, Licht, and Crews, 1988). Restraint and/or confinement can result in a spike in stress hormone levels, which can interfere with data collection. For example, in the whistling frog (*Litoria ewingii*) plasma corticosterone levels increased at 30 min after handling, and was high for 3 h after capture (Coddington and Cree, 1995).

Hormone levels can be measured both destructively and non-destructively using bodily fluids. A variation in hormone metabolism can be determined by injecting an organism with a radiolabelled hormone and determining the metabolites they are broken down into using liquid chromatography (reviewed in Germano *et al.*, 2012). Taking blood can be destructive depending on the size and life stage of the anuran. Blood sampling from tadpoles can be destructive due to their small body size, usually using cardiac puncture and collection using a heparinised capillary tube (Whatley *et al.*, 2020). A methodology for collecting blood from the facial vein of Ranid species is outlined in Forzán *et al.* (2012). Direct enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays, also known as single-antibody EIAs are also gaining popularity for

the measurement of reproductive and stress hormone metabolites in amphibians (Germano *et al.*, 2009; Narayan *et al.*, 2010; Janin *et al.*, 2012; Kindermann, Narayan and Hero, 2012). Polyclonal antibodies used in urinary EIAs detect the amount of steroid hormone metabolites in a sample. This allows detection of the amount of hormone present after metabolism by the kidney and excretion (Narayan, 2013). Further studies investigating both urinary and plasma hormone levels across areas of varying environmental contamination could help to elucidate whether urine sampling can replace blood sampling. Narayan (2013) recommended that biological validation of metabolite hormone concentrations should be carried out for both sexes, and that the use of urine needs more development as a method across species. The non-invasive assessment of reproductive hormone metabolites in anuran faeces has also been achieved (Szymanski, Gist and Roth, 2006; Hogan *et al.*, 2013) but this is very time consuming in non-captive species (Narayan, 2013).

Biomarkers as biomonitoring tools

What is a biomarker?

In order to carry out effective environmental monitoring, researchers must be able to identify contaminants within the environment and be able to study and fully understand their effects. There has been a shift away from contaminant-based monitoring (using data such as sediment analysis or taking aquatic measurements), moving towards more effect-based monitoring, looking at the effects within the organisms being conserved (Lam, 2009). This can be done by looking at the temporal or spatial changes within a selected species or ecological system, in order to detect and measure parameters that can be used to reflect any changes in the quality of the environment. These responses have been used in both wild and captive held organisms in order to assess their health and wellbeing, as well as that of their ecosystems (Moore *et al.*, 2004). In using a biomonitoring approach such as this, many different parameters could be assessed, ranging from the chemical residues present in tissue and bodily fluid samples, to looking at specific biological endpoints such as fertility or fecundity (Lam, 2009). Such parameters can be considered as biomarkers, which are defined as “a xenobiotically induced variation in cellular or biochemical components or processes, structures, or functions that is measurable in a biological system or sample” (Henderson *et al.*, 1989).

Use of biomarkers

A biomarker could be used to assess biochemical, physiological, morphological, or behavioural changes in an organism, as well as overall ecological community changes (Lam, 2009). Wu *et al.* (2005) argue that a useful biomarker should be ecologically relevant (for example, being able to reveal effects at the population level or higher) enabling predictions to be made, as well as being able to be definitively linked (particularly in the case of an exposure biomarker) to a significant biological effect. Biomarkers can be either destructive (requiring the organism to be euthanased or harmed in order for parameters to be measured) or non-destructive (where the collection of data has minimal impact on the organism). Non-destructive biomarkers should be prioritized where possible, especially in endangered species where sacrifice of individuals would conflict with conservation priorities. Factors such as the natural history and ecology of a specific species, life stage, age, and sex should also be considered when choosing which biomarkers to investigate, as well as how this biomarker may be affected by different abiotic and biotic factors that a species may be exposed to in the wild or in a laboratory setting.

Most of the biomarkers used in studies carried out in wild organisms involve analysing tissues or organs, which means that they must be euthanased. The sacrifice of wild organisms is undesirable for ethical considerations, if there is a limited number of individuals at the study site, if the species has legal protection, or because medium or long-term monitoring is required (Fossi and Leonzio, 1993). Consequently, when utilising non-lethal biomarkers such as whole blood, plasma, urine, stool, or excretions of wild organisms, the biological responses can be measured with little or no harm to any individuals or to the population as a whole (Cruz-Santiago *et al.*, 2021).

The use of non-lethal biological techniques such as the analyses of enzyme and blood biomarkers has gained attention due to their effectiveness as early signals of the adverse effects of exposure to chemical contamination in fishes (Barata *et al.*, 2010; Sloman and McNeil, 2012), reptiles (Basso *et al.*, 2012) and birds (Martinez-Haro, Green and Mateo, 2011). Hence, the use of different biological endpoints in combination with other enzymatic and blood biomarkers can be used as a consistent warning sign of the level of environmental

change, and has been considered a priority in characterising environmental risk for amphibian larvae (Lajmanovich *et al.*, 2010; Rocha, 2011). A multi-biomarker approach has proven useful in human disease diagnostics, as well as in amphibian ecotoxicological studies, as it allows for more powerful multivariate statistical analysis to be performed and allows the researcher to observe trends in the data (Handy *et al.*, 2003; Lopes *et al.*, 2023). Such a multivariate approach utilizing several different biomarkers to answer a particular research question may also be useful in environmental work for biomonitoring of populations.

Limitations of biomarkers

When using biomarkers derived from bodily fluids, particularly stress hormones, there may be a delay in sampling. Alternatively, stress hormone levels may confound other biomarkers being investigated as a result of capture/handling stress on the organism (Narayan, 2013). Although biomarkers are certainly useful tools for investigating the effects of contamination on the environment, it is important to understand their limitations. Different biomarkers have differing degrees of specificity, so should be utilised in regard to their specific strengths. For example, lead exposure inhibits the enzyme aminolevulinic acid dehydratase (ALAD) in the production of heme and is used as an incredibly specific biomarker of lead contamination (Selander and Cramér, 1970; Lam, 2009). Other biomarkers can be used as indicators of general environmental stress, such as the mixed function oxidase (MFO) system, a detoxification enzyme complex that is induced in response to general environmental stress. Induction of this system can make interpretation of other results more difficult and can make it hard to attribute results to a particular environmental stressor (Lam, 2009). There may also be factors unrelated to exposure that cause induction of a biomarker response, such as food availability, water temperature, and reproductive activity (Viarengo and Canesi, 1991; Sheehan and Power, 1999; Niyogi *et al.*, 2001). Knowledge of how these factors impact a biomarker response in the species being studied is key to the utility of a particular biomarker. Wu *et al.* (2003) demonstrated that hypoxia significantly decreased serum levels of testosterone, estradiol, and triiodothyronine in carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). As a result, both male and female carp displayed stunted gonadal development, and spawning success, sperm motility, fertilization success, hatching success, and larval survival were all reduced. These effects could all be attributed to disruption of the endocrine system as a result of EDC exposure. Scenarios such as this can increase the chances of false positive results.

Organisms also have a limited capacity to be able to evade and repair environmental stress. This not only makes it harder to detect when an organism has been exposed to a stressor, but it makes the results less ecologically relevant. For example, there has been a large body of work carried out looking at DNA repair in mussels, where a biomarker response recorded in mussels from polluted sites showed increased levels of DNA strand breakage with increased pollution levels (Xu *et al.*, 1999; Ching *et al.*, 2001). However, approximately 12 days later, the pattern of dose-related response increase had disappeared, suggesting a DNA repair mechanism is taking place. It is also crucial to understand the interactions between exposure level and duration of biomarker response in order to maximize the effectiveness of biomarker usage.

Use in biomonitoring

Studies looking at effects occurring at the molecular level are on average more repeatable, and therefore predictable (Lam, 2009). Effects that occur at the physiological, organismal, or population level are more ecologically relevant and useful, however these are much more difficult to detect and attribute to particular causes (Lam, 2009). In addition, the most useful biomarkers are ones where it is a clear indicator of an organism's exposure to pollutants (exposure biomarkers) and/or the magnitude of the organism's response to the pollutant (effect biomarkers) (Hamza-Chaffai, 2014). The most effective biomonitoring programmes have been shown to employ multiple biomarkers and biomonitoring tools in combination, in order to achieve the most ecologically relevant results, with the best understanding of how the environment can affect results achieved (Lopes *et al.*, 2023). The remainder of this review will discuss potential biomarkers or tools for biomonitoring of reproductive success, growth and development, and EDC exposure in anurans.

Biomarkers of reproductive success and EDC exposure in adult anurans

Nuptial pads

Nuptial pads are areas of modified epidermal and dermal tissue found on the digits (and in some species forelimb) of many anurans, including *Rana temporaria* (Noble, 1931; Luna, McDiarmid and Faivovich, 2018; Orton *et al.*, 2023). For a thorough review of nuptial pad morphology and function spanning 507 species, see Luna *et al.* (2018). Luna *et al.* separates nuptial pads into three specific morphologies: Nuptial pads with papillary epidermal projections, nuptial pads with non-papillary epidermal projections, and smooth nuptial pads with no projections, but a light thickening of the dermis. Nuptial pads are used by male anurans to grip the female during amplexus, while egg deposition and sperm release occurs (Duellman and Trueb, 1994). The exact function of nuptial pads is still widely debated, and they present a wide variety of morphologies (see **Figure 1.3**), although this likely depends on the ecology of a particular species, in particular their breeding dynamics. Such functions may include enabling males to obtain females during scramble competitions in explosive breeding species, preventing takeover attempts from other males, or as a sexually selected trait in direct male combat or through female choice (Savage, 1961; Duellman and Trueb, 1994). Nuptial pads are typically only found on adult male anurans, although in a few cases they may be found on female or juvenile anurans. These nuptial pads however lack the specialised mucous glands (SMGs) that are found in the pads of males (Thomas, Tsang and Licht, 1993; Luna, McDiarmid and Faivovich, 2018; Jeckel *et al.*, 2019). These SMGs secrete amplexins onto the surface of the pads, although the function of these gland secretions is currently unknown (Kyriakopoulou-Sklavounou, Papaevangelou and Kladisios, 2012). It is hypothesised that these secretions could act as a glue to prevent displacement by rival males during amplexus (Brizzi, Delfino and Jantra, 1994), or have chemical functions related to courtship and mating (Thomas, Tsang and Licht, 1993; Zheng *et al.*, 2024). In some species, abrasions of the skin on the dermis of the female can be found following mating, which may allow for transfer of chemical signals (Luna *et al.*, 2018). These chemical communications may serve to encourage females to speed up egg deposition and reduce amplexus time, as being in amplexus leaves frogs vulnerable to predation. More research is needed to establish the exact function of nuptial pads and their associated secretions in reproduction.

Nuptial pad colouration depends on three factors (Luna, McDiarmid and Faivovich, 2018). Firstly, the colouration of the outer layer of the epidermis, the stratum corneum, which creates a light brown to black colouration. Secondly, the colour of the glandular cells which are visible through the stratum when it is not coloured. Thirdly, in some rare cases, melanophores are found between the dermis and epidermis. Different colour intensities could be attributed to factors such as different phases of hormone cycles, the age of individuals, or the method of preservation used for deceased specimens (Luna, McDiarmid and Faivovich, 2018). For example, Izzo *et al.* (1982) demonstrated that nuptial pad colour varied in *Agalychnis dacnicolor* seasonally, with darker black or brown colours displayed in the breeding season and a white colour outside of the breeding season. Both formation of the nuptial pad as well as control of their associated glands appear to be largely under the control of androgens, as demonstrated by androgen replacement studies (Emerson *et al.*, 1999). For example, androgen supplementation has been found to induce growth of nuptial pad tissues in castrated males, males outside of the breeding season, and ovariectomised females (Iwasawa and Kobayashi, 1974; Kelley and Pfaff, 1976; Blackburn and Lynch, 1995). As a result, exposure to chemicals known to have endocrine disrupting properties such as flutamide, octylphenol, nonylphenol, 17 α -ethynylestradiol (EE2), and vinclozolin could reduce the area of breeding glands in *X. laevis* (Wyk, Pool and Leslie, 2003). Very little is also known about the potential influence of the environment, however external factors such as temperature and photoperiod, are thought to play a role in nuptial pad development (Izzo *et al.*, 1982; Luna, McDiarmid and Faivovich, 2018).

Figure 1.3: Image highlighting the diversity of nuptial pad (circled in red) morphology amongst anurans. **A:** *Espadarana audex* **B:** *Rana japonica* - white arrow denotes the thickness of the nuptial pad skin compared to other digits **C:** *Lechriodus melanopygia* . Scale bars: 1 mm. Taken from Luna *et al.* (2018). From erotic excrescences to pheromone shots: structure and diversity of nuptial pads in anurans. Volume 124, issue number 3, pp 403-446. Reproduced by permission of the author and Oxford University Press.

Several studies have looked at investigating nuptial pad changes in wild anurans relating to EDC exposure (McCoy *et al.*, 2008; Orton, Baynes, *et al.*, 2014; Guo *et al.*, 2018; Brady *et al.*, 2019; Zlotnik, Gridi-Papp and Bernal, 2019; Tang *et al.*, 2021). For example, wild individuals of *Bufo raddei* exposed to endocrine disrupting heavy metals (mainly copper, zinc, lead, and cadmium) exhibited larger nuptial pads along with other changes in sex characteristics (Guo *et al.*, 2018). Studies in the lab have also been carried out (Wyk, Pool, and Leslie, 2003; Hayes *et al.*, 2010; Orton *et al.*, 2018, 2020), however many studies focus mainly on *Xenopus* species. It is difficult to extrapolate these data to other species as it is unclear how the responses to endocrine disruptors vary between *Xenopus* and other taxa, and so other amphibian species should be considered as alternative models, for example *Rana temporaria* (Pettersson and Berg, 2007). Measurements of nuptial pad morphology (such as length, width, or colour) can easily be taken non-destructively both from lab-reared anurans, and from wild anurans in the field. If more detailed structural analysis of the nuptial pad is needed, this can also be carried out using techniques such as histology, as demonstrated in Luna *et al.* (2018). As a result, most studies employ destructive techniques to analyse nuptial pad data (usually in combination with other biomarkers such as larynx morphology and muscle morphometrics). Orton *et al.* (2023), a study for which the current thesis author is a co-author and contributed significant data collection and analysis to, showed that adult male *R. temporaria* that achieved amplexus were more likely to have a longer and/or darker nuptial pad than non-amplexing males. This would suggest that these morphological features are important secondary sex characteristics involved in breeding success.

Forelimb morphometrics

The forelimbs of male anurans are often larger than those of their female counterparts, making this a sexually dimorphic characteristic (Wells, 2010). In explosive breeding Ranids, such as *Rana temporaria*, the forelimb of the male encircles the female during amplexus, with front toes under the body (Banta, 1914; Noble and Aronson, 1942; Savage, 1961). This allows them to hold on firmly, and prevents females from being stolen by competing males (Wells, 2010). In breeding scenarios where it is assumed that achieving and maintaining amplexus is more important than other elements of male competition (such as calling), larger forelimbs may be selected for through sexual selection, as hypothesised by Howard and Kluge (1985). For example, in *Rana sylvatica* the males have longer arms relative to body

length than females, presumably to allow the forelimbs to encircle the female during amplexus. In contrast, in *Rana clamitans*, there is no evidence that males have longer arms compared to females, as the males do not encircle the female. However, Howard (1988) found no evidence that forelimb length influenced mating success. Recent studies have come to opposing conclusions regarding sexual dimorphism of forelimb muscles, suggesting that sexual dimorphism is species-specific (Yang *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2023). Larger forelimbs in males may also be indicative of breeding success in species where fighting occurs between males, as fighting males will push each other using their forelimbs (Wells, 1977). There are correlations in the literature between forelimb size and body size, which makes differentiating between using these traits as a measure of reproductive success difficult. For example, both forelimb length and width were correlated to body size in wild populations of *Bufo bufo* (Orton *et al.*, 2014). In wild *R. clamitans* populations, males with larger forelimbs were also larger in body size, and larger males are able to occupy higher quality territories and thus acquire a higher number of females (Wells, 1977; Schulte-Hostedde and Schank, 2009). Svanholm *et al.*, (2020) showed that forelimb width was positively associated with fertility in *X. tropicalis*.

Differences in clasping behaviour affects the functional morphology of the forelimb according to different amplexus methods (for more details see **Amphibian reproduction** above). The ability to retain a mate likely depends on strength rather than length of the forelimbs. Forelimb length solely depends on the skeletal structure of the forelimb, whereas it is the muscular tissue that is sexually dimorphic and therefore affects the force of amplexus from males (Emerson, 1991). Lee (2001) found that in *Bufo marinus*, the male forelimbs are more robust than in females, and males with large forelimbs are more likely to be found in amplexus. The role of forelimb muscles in clamping behaviour has hardly been investigated, and needs more comparative studies combining observations of clasping with limb morphology. Muscle size may also vary seasonally as androgen levels fluctuate (Melichna *et al.*, 1972; Dorlöchter, Astrow and Herreta, 1994; Wells, 2010). Size development of the forelimb muscles is under androgenic control. This is demonstrated experimentally by castrated males developing smaller forelimbs, and supplementation with androgens increasing forelimb size (Blackburn and Lynch, 1995; Blackburn *et al.*, 1995; Sidor and Blackburn, 1998). For example, Kampe and Peters (2013) demonstrated that testosterone replacement in castrated *Rana catesbeiana* produced higher force production and lower

fatigability of the forelimb muscles compared to castrated males not supplemented with testosterone. This study also indicated that exposure of young males to testosterone produces a masculinising force on the forelimbs during their first breeding season that is not reversed through seasonal hypertrophy between breeding seasons when testosterone levels drop. This allows contractile properties of the muscles to maximise quickly in order to enhance breeding success when testosterone levels rise again. As such, forelimb morphology may be affected by exposure to EDCs.

In order to measure the muscular force generated by an anuran, destructive methods must be used to dissect the musculature of the forearm, meaning that use of this biomarker is limited. However, using a novel method (Patent number: 201710022860.9), forelimb force was reportedly measured *in situ* in two populations of *Bufo raddei* in varying heavy metal contamination, finding increased forelimb width and force in males from the polluted site (Guo *et al.*, 2018). It is of note that no other reference to this patent could be found. This, combined with a handful of other wild studies demonstrate contrasting results. For example, forelimb width increased in natterjack toad (*Epidalea calamita*) populations from an agricultural area compared to a natural site, indicating a higher investment in reproductive potential (Zamora-Camacho and Comas, 2017). In contrast to these findings, forelimb width and nuptial pads were reduced in male cane toads along a gradient of increased agricultural land use (McCoy *et al.*, 2008). Laboratory studies have also been carried out in this area, for example forelimb width was reduced after exposure to anti-androgenic chemicals in *Xenopus tropicalis* (Orton *et al.*, 2018).

Calling behaviour and larynx morphology

Anurans use calling as a form of communication, but it is also a key component of reproductive behaviour (reviewed in Barkan *et al.*, 2020). Females choose mates based on call characteristics, and females are hypothesised to prefer longer, more complex calls with more ‘croaks’ in accordance with the ‘good genes’ hypothesis (Guerra, Ryan and Cannatella, 2014; Huang, Duan and Ji, 2015). Pekny *et al.*, (2024) demonstrated that in anurans, male advertisement calls are dynamic and relate to the suitability of a breeding site for reproduction, thereby acting as a potential biomonitoring tool. Calling makes a male anuran

vulnerable to predation, and so being able to call for a long time indicates a high level of fitness that suggests to a female anuran that his genes would improve survival of potential offspring (Welch, Semlitsch and Gerhardt, 1998). Calling behaviour can also be influenced by external environmental changes, both natural such as temperature and precipitation (Oseen and Wassersug, 2002; Schalk and Saenz, 2016), or unnatural such as anthropogenic noise pollution (Lengagne, 2008; Pomezanski, 2021). Social factors can also affect calling behaviours (Wells, 1977; Lengagne, 2008).

A structure in the larynx called the fibrous mass is responsible for calling, and it has been suggested that a larger larynx is capable of producing more complex calls (Boul and Ryan, 2004). Males have larger laryngeal muscles and higher levels of androgen receptors in tissues than females (Kelley *et al.*, 1989). Laryngeal muscle of male *Xenopus* was found to have three times the androgen binding level than female tissue and 1.7 times the amount of muscle fibres (Segil, Silverman and Kelley, 1987). Exposure to EE2 increases the proportion of repelling calls, and decreases the advertisement calls of *X. laevis* (Hoffmann and Kloas, 2012b). Formation of a larynx capable of calling in males is androgen-dependent, and endocrine disrupting chemicals influence calling behaviour (Guo *et al.*, 2018). For a review of auditory processing in amphibians, the role of acoustic communication in reproduction for *X. laevis*, and the effects of EDC exposure on anuran vocalisation with a focus on *X. laevis*, see Hall and Kelley (2020).

It is hypothesised that subacute exposure to heavy metals such as cadmium that are capable of disrupting the endocrine system could decrease larynx size; for example, cadmium toxicity affected call characteristics (call latency, call duration, and call rate) in *Pelophylax nigromaculata* (Huang, Duan and Ji, 2015; Huang *et al.*, 2016). Vocalisation composition was affected by vinclozolin (a fungicide used in agriculture) in *X. laevis* (Hoffmann and Kloas, 2012b). Exposure to atrazine in male *X. laevis* altered the structure of the larynx to resemble a morphology more similar to that of a female, however the size of the larynx was unaffected (Hayes *et al.*, 2010). Only two studies could be found looking at the effects of EDC exposure on larynx physiology in wild anurans, however they have conflicting results. Zlotnik *et al.* (2019) demonstrated that cane toads (*Rhinella marina*) collected from near sugar cane fields in Florida, USA differed in larynx morphology compared to urban sites.

Results showed that male toads from sugarcane areas have smaller laryngeal masses, shorter vocal cords, and thinner dilator muscles than males from urbanised sites, despite no differences in overall body size. The larynxes of female toads did not differ between study sites. Smith *et al.* (2005) investigated differences in larynx morphology in *X. laevis* inhabiting maize growing and non-growing areas, but found no differences between sites. This highlights the importance of using non-*Xenopus* models in future research in this area.

Other secondary sex characteristics (SSCs)

There are several other secondary sex characteristics that are important in anuran reproduction that may have limited potential as biomarkers in certain species, including muscle groups other than those mentioned above, body size, colour and fighting characteristics.

Other muscle groups

The external and internal oblique muscles of the torso are used for sound production in calling, in combination with the abdominal hypaxial muscles (Blackburn and Bernardo, 1998). These muscle groups are also a sexually dimorphic characteristic, as in some males, these muscles are much larger than in females (Emerson *et al.*, 1999). Recent research also suggests that the hind limb muscles may be sexually dimorphic (Lee and Corrales, 2002). Muscle analysis generally involves destructive methods that conflict with conservation priorities of endangered species, and so non-destructive methods should be prioritised. These muscle groups are less studied and so the effects of EDCs on their function and development have not yet been assessed.

Body size

Despite the fact that large males are more likely to win fights over territories, the largest males in a population do not necessarily achieve the highest mating success. In *Rana clamitans* and *Rana catesbeiana*, large males were generally more successful than small

males in defending high quality territories and obtaining mates, but the correlation between male size and mating success in different years varied greatly. Mating success was more a function of territory quality rather than male size. However, if females choose good territories and the largest males occupy the best territories, then this will result in indirect selection for large body males (Wells, 1977). Another theory regarding the importance of size in anuran reproduction is that larger females prefer larger males because the call frequency to which they are attuned decreases as they grow, and so large males with low frequency calls are likely to be heard better by large females (De Orense and Tejedo-Madueno, 1990).

In many lek breeding anurans, large males do not consistently have a mating advantage over small males. In some cases, this is simply due to a very narrow range of body sizes in the male population, but in others body size has little effect on mating success despite significant size variation among males. There is only limited evidence for size assortative mating in anurans with prolonged breeding seasons (Wells, 2010). Body size in females can be associated with reproductive outputs like clutch size, and body size can also be affected by factors such as food availability, pollution, and environmental factors (Gibbons and McCarthy, 1986; Oromi *et al.*, 2016; Horato *et al.*, 2024). Overall, body size plays an important role in anuran reproduction in some species, although there are differing reports in the literature regarding its importance for reproductive success, combined with many external factors that may influence body size leading to complications in using it as a biomarker. Body size or mass measurements can also be very easily obtained non-destructively. There are limited studies looking at the effects of EDCs on body size (Tamschick *et al.*, 2016; Hoskins, 2019), and so this is an area of research that needs prioritisation.

Colour

Colour is a crucial part of reproductive courtship for many anuran species. For example, in many species of frog, brightly coloured patches are displayed on the throat during territory disputes (Ryan, 1980). In at least two species of dendrobatid frogs (*Colostethus palmatus* and *Mannophryne trinitatis*), calling males turn completely black and become aggressive towards other black males. Males then signal submission by turning brown (Wells, 1980). In *Litoria wilcoxii*, males turn from brown to yellow during amplexus. Gardner *et al.* (2021) report that

male *Incilius luetkenii* (yellow toad) become bright yellow during the brief breeding season before reverting back to their usual brown colouration when the breeding season is finished, with considerable variation in the yellow breeding season coloration. However, there was no female preference between different colours, so this is likely not driven by female choice. A study carried out by Kindermann *et al.* (2014) determined a neuro-hormonal cause of this colour change, although they hypothesised that this may be a by-product of other hormonal processes that are occurring during amplexus and fertilisation. Stückler *et al.* (2022) demonstrated that in *Duttaphrynus melanostictus* (Asiatic common toad), epinephrine and norepinephrine are responsible for rapid colour change from brown to yellow during reproduction, even in the absence of social and environmental reproductive cues. As such, EDCs may affect colour changes of amphibians, but studies would be needed to determine the roles of colour in reproductive success, as well as interactions with other stressors. For example, Auld (2023) reports a non-significant trend of chytrid infected male juvenile brown toad (*Pseudophryne bibronii*) possessing darker throats than uninfected males. This was hypothesised to be associated with increased levels of testosterone.

Colour could potentially be used as an indication of intersex individuals within a population, as identified in *Bufo bufo* treated with a glyphosate-based herbicide and EE2 (Ujhegyi and Bókony, 2020). The colour of specific body parts may also serve as a more indicative biomarker in some species (see **Nuptial pads** section above). Colour has potential as a non-destructive biomarker, but is very species specific and so detailed knowledge of the natural history of a species is needed, as well as an understanding of the natural colour variation found within a population. An understanding of the influence of external factors such as temperature and precipitation on anuran colour also needs to be considered when investigating the effects of EDCs.

Fighting characteristics

Some anurans possess other sexually dimorphic morphologies that are used in reproduction. For example, some anurans have spines on their chest or forelimbs that are used to stab or slash opponents during fights, such as the nest building gladiator frogs (Martins, Pombal and Haddad, 1998). These animals possess a curved spine on the front foot with which to slash

opponents, and males are frequently injured during fights, sometimes fatally. Families such as Leptodactylidae and Hylidae possess spines, such as the males of centrolenid frogs with humeral spines on their forelimbs (Shine, 1979; Lynch and Ruiz-Carranza, 1996; Malagoli *et al.*, 2021). In fanged frogs such as *Limnonectes leporinus*, the males are larger than females and possess hypertrophied jaw muscles accompanied by fangs on the lower jaw. These features are used as weapons; males have been observed fighting over territories and can injure rival males with their fangs (Emerson and Voris, 1992). The formation and maintenance of these characteristics is likely to be under androgenic control, however exact mechanisms and potential effects of EDCs on development, and the subsequent effect on reproductive success are currently unknown (Sever and Staub, 2011). These features may also be measured non-destructively which is beneficial to anuran conservation.

Sex determination and sex differentiation

In vertebrates, sex is determined via either genetic or environmental factors, or a combination of the two (Nakamura, 2009). Sexual determination is the process whereby it is determined if an individual will become male or female, and sexual differentiation is the process whereby sexual characteristics develop (Norris and Lopez, 2011). Sexual differentiation and determination in amphibians occur differently depending on the species in question, and the process is very complex, even within the same species. As of 2001, only 4% of amphibian species had cytologically different sex chromosomes, with 96% of species having morphologically undifferentiated chromosomes (Schmid and Steinlein, 2001). Some species present with XY/XX genetic sex determination as found in mammals, where a sex determining gene found on the heterogametic male Y chromosome determines the development of testes or ovaries (Norris and Lopez, 2011). Some species on the other hand, present with ZW/ZZ genetic sex determination, where a gene on the heterogametic female W chromosome determines sex. In rare cases, there is intraspecific variation where a species will vary in its method of sex determination in different localities, such as *Rana rugosa*, with XY/XX and ZW/ZZ present in different populations (Nishioka and Hanada, 1994; Nishioka *et al.*, 1994; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2016). Several genes that act as sexual markers of genotypes have been identified, but are inconsistent across amphibian species, and also within species (Eggert, 2004). A sex determining gene (*DM-W*) in *Xenopus laevis* has been found. This gene

is believed to be female determined, and is involved in ovary development (Yoshimoto *et al.*, 2008). More research is needed into the exact role this gene plays in sex differentiation before it can be implemented as a potential biomarker (Norris and Lopez, 2011). Environmental sex determination (ESD) or temperature dependent sex determination (TDSD) can be found in some anurans, but can be induced artificially in the laboratory usually at temperatures outside of normal environmental range, with higher temperatures skewing sex ratios more towards males (Hayes, 1998; Wallace, Badawy and Wallace, 1999; Eggert, 2004; Ruiz-García, Roco and Bullejos, 2021).

Intersex and sex ratio

Intersex is the occurrence of a mixture of male and female reproductive tissue within a particular individual, and has been used as a biomarker of EDC exposure in wild anurans, as well as in lab studies (Reeder *et al.*, 2005; Orton and Routledge, 2011; Orton *et al.*, 2014; reviewed in Orton and Tyler, 2015). Many different types of gonadal malformations can result from EDC exposure, and have mainly been identified from lab studies. Examples include malformation of the testes, development of ovaries and testes within the same individual, non-pigmented ovaries, growth of oviducts in males, and the presence of diplotenic oocytes (see **Figure 1.4**) (Hayes, Stuart, *et al.*, 2006; Hayes *et al.*, 2010; Orton *et al.*, 2018). Intersex can be induced by exposure to EDCs in anurans. For example, exposure to finasteride (a chemical that inhibits 5 α -reductase: the enzyme that converts T to DHT) has been shown to cause feminisation and to increase intersex in *X. tropicalis* at a concentration of 25 μ M (Duarte-Guterman *et al.*, 2009). Aromatase (the enzyme that converts T to E2) is inhibited by fadrazole and flavone. Exposure to these chemicals has been shown to induce masculinisation and intersex in *X. tropicalis* (Duarte-Guterman *et al.*, 2009) and in *R. pipiens* (Mackenzie *et al.*, 2003), respectively. Larval exposures to EE2 result in female-biased sex ratios, including intersex, in *R. pipiens* at 5 nM (Hogan *et al.*, 2008) and at 1 nM (in the absence of intersex) in *X. tropicalis* (Pettersson and Berg, 2007). Exposure to EDCs has the potential to disrupt sex development in anurans, and so cause increased levels of intersex found in a population.

Although intersex could be used as a marker of EDC exposure both in field studies and in the laboratory, levels at which intersex is found in the wild naturally are unknown, as it is almost impossible to detect unless destructive methods are used. Intersex and gonadal abnormalities exist in the wild depending on different factors, such as age (Orton and Tyler, 2015). There is also no evidence in amphibians that these levels of intersex affect reproductive success, and therefore is not a useful biomarker for reproductive disruption.

Figure 1.4: Histopathology of an adult intersex *Xenopus laevis* A shows the entire dissected kidney–adrenal–gonadal complex showing the presence of testes (T) and ovaries (O) within the same specimen. B–E show an 8 μm transverse cross-section (stained with Mallory’s trichrome stain) through the areas indicated by the lines in A. [Bar 0.1 mm (A) and 25 μm (B–E)]. Of note is the absence of pigment in the ovaries, which is typical of hermaphrodites. This individual had been exposed to 1 ppb atrazine, a herbicide known to have feminising effects. Taken from Hayes *et al.* (2002) with the author’s permission.

Sex ratio is the relative number of males to females at fertilization (primary sex ratio), birth (secondary sex ratio), and sexual maturity (tertiary sex ratio) (Székely, Weissing and Komdeur, 2014). When measuring sex ratio of a population, a male:female ratio of 1:1 is

assumed normal, with any variations from this within a population being abnormal. It is rarely possible to accurately measure the actual sex ratio of a population, so the operational sex ratio (ORS) is used instead, the ratio of sexually active males to females in a given location. Males usually leave first in explosive breeding species such as *Rana temporaria*, so this can lead to inaccurate estimates, and so sex ratio estimates should be taken outside of the breeding season (Hartel and Sas, 2007; Wells, 2010). For example, Reyne *et al.* (2020) used a combination of egg spawn counts, photo IDs of individuals, and genetic barcoding in order to determine population size and sex ratio of a population of natterjack toads (*Epidalea calamita*) in Caherdaniel, County Kerry. They estimated the sex ratio to be approximately 1:5, deviating strongly from the expected 1:1 ratio and suggesting that previous population estimates had been largely underestimating. Measuring sex ratio in species without obvious sexual dimorphism requires using destructive methods such as gonadal histopathology, and so this impacts any conservation efforts of a particular species. In order to accurately measure sex ratio, it is crucial to also consider factors such as temperature, breeding behaviours, migration, disease, and predation. Sex reversal in green frogs (*Rana clamitans*) was found to occur naturally along a gradient of suburbanization (Lambert *et al.*, 2019). Reported sex ratios for *R. temporaria* also vary within the literature; Alho *et al.* (2010) report a ratio of mostly 1:1, with some all-female or mostly female populations, Schmeller and Merilä, (2007) report a ratio of 3:1 females to males, and Gibbons and McCarthy, (1986) report a ratio of 1:1.3 females to males. This suggests that the sex ratio of a population naturally fluctuates, and differs between populations based on complex factors, so unless a population becomes close to 100 % male or female and affects reproductive output, it is not a particularly useful measure of intersex or fecundity.

Hormones

Hormones are largely responsible for the coordination of reproduction and development of reproductive structures, as well as metamorphosis (Trudeau *et al.*, 2022; Méndez-Tepepa *et al.*, 2023). Exposure to EDCs has been shown to alter plasma hormone concentrations (reviewed in Orton and Tyler, 2015). Unlike other biomarkers reviewed here, more studies have been carried out in the wild measuring different concentrations of hormones. The primary hormones studied in the literature are thyroid hormones, testosterone, and

corticosterone, and the Genera *Xenopus*, *Rana*, and *Bufo* have been the most studied. Trends in the literature suggest that testosterone levels are subject to fluctuations as a result of EDC exposure – however whether plasma androgen levels rise or fall may be species specific and may also be affected by the timing of sampling (such as during the breeding season) (Feder and Burggren, 1992). Rapid changes in plasma hormone concentrations may also contribute to a disparity in these findings. Further studies on baseline levels of these hormones for comparison as well as data regarding differences in testosterone levels of amplexing and non-amplexing males would be a welcome addition to the literature. Also, most hormonal work focuses on males, with a focus on female hormones being far more recent; this area should be investigated more thoroughly. As individuals become chronically stressed, GC levels may become permanently elevated (homeostatic overload) or permanently suppressed (homeostatic failure) (Romero, Dickens and Cyr, 2009). Corticosterone is a common biomarker of stress, and can be used as a biomarker of EDC exposure which acts as a stressor on amphibians.

Several studies on wild amphibians have been carried out using hormones as biomarkers. Lower levels of plasma androgens and higher peaks of plasma estradiol concentration were found in edible frog (*Rana esculenta*) and pool frog (*Rana lessonae*) populations in agricultural areas compared to reference sites, whereas no effect of land use was found on steroid concentrations in green frogs (*Rana clamitans*), bull frogs (*Rana catesbeiana*) or leopard frogs (*Rana pipiens*) (Mosconi *et al.*, 2005; Murphy *et al.*, 2006). Increased agricultural land use resulted in decreased cane toad (*Rhinella marina*) plasma testosterone concentrations (McCoy *et al.*, 2008). Corticosterone and testosterone levels in both calling and non-calling southern toad (*Bufo terrestris*) males were higher in a polluted site compared with a ‘natural’ site (Hopkins, Mendonça and Congdon, 1997). Furthermore, testosterone levels were decreased in male *Xenopus laevis* from an urban field site compared to reference sites (Rojas-Hucks *et al.*, 2019). Orton *et al.* (2014) utilised plasma testosterone and corticosterone concentrations as a potential destructive biomarker of reproductive health in *Bufo bufo*, alongside other measures (destructive: bidders organ, fat bodies spermatogenesis ; non-destructive: mass, SVL, forelimb length, forelimb width, and nuptial pads). This study reports that size was the most important variable for measuring inter-individual differences, in addition to hormone levels and nuptial pad (independent of size).

Molecular markers

Many EDCs are highly lipophilic and interact with components of cell membranes. As such, these compounds are able to disrupt normal enzymatic and signal transduction activities that are linked to cell membranes, affecting the downstream processes that are regulated by them. These same endocrine disrupting compounds can also interact with specific receptors, triggering signalling events that elicit detoxification or stress responses within an organism, that can have negative consequences. Transcription factors can be altered, thereby modifying the genetic expression of proteins and enzymes, and so altering their function (Ashida and Matsumura, 1998). As such, there is a wide range of biomarkers that could be measured and utilised along this process, from looking at which genes are being expressed in a particular part of the body following EDC exposure, to measuring the amount of a protein or enzyme that is produced as a result of changes in gene expression (up or down regulation of genes). Several molecular biomarkers are utilised for determining the overall health of an anuran exposed to EDCs, however only those related to reproduction will be considered in this review (for a review of biomarkers of amphibian ecotoxicology, see Venturino and Pechen de D'Angelo, 2005).

All stages of the life of an anuran, from metamorphosis to reproduction, are controlled by the expression of genes. EDCs can also alter the expression of genes through epigenetics, or long term changes to genetic structures even after the initial cause has dissipated (Alavian-Ghavanini and Rüegg, 2018). For example, hormonal treatments applied early in life alter the response of hormonally regulated genes to the same or different hormones later in life (Edinger, Mambo and Evans, 1997). The term epigenetic imprinting has also been used to describe a process in which estrogens in development cause persistent alterations in gene expression and reprogram cell fate (Alworth *et al.*, 2002; Crews and McLachlan, 2006; Fei, Nyikó and Molnar, 2021). Possible epigenetic changes should be taken into consideration when utilising genetic biomarkers. Another potential molecular marker are lysosomes that are known to play a major role in the sequestration of organic contaminants, such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) (Nott *et al.*, 1985; Lam, 2009). Although the ability to remove contaminants from within cells could act as a protective mechanism, it also leaves the lysosomal membrane susceptible to elevated toxicant concentrations, leading to an efflux of

hydrolytic enzymes and apoptosis (cell death). Many chemical physical and environmental stressors, including pollutants, are known to destabilize the membranes of lysosomes, and membrane damage is often proportional to the magnitude of stress (Moore *et al.*, 2004). A neutral red retention (NRR) assay has been used to assess lysosomal membrane permeability or integrity. Recent studies have revealed that the NRR assay in *P. viridis* appears to be a robust biomarker under laboratory conditions although responses are not always entirely concentration-dependent (Nicholson, 2003). This has been used as a biomarker for pollutants in amphibians before, and if cell death occurred in primary or secondary sex characteristics of an anuran, reproductive viability may be compromised (Valbona *et al.*, 2009; Falfushynska *et al.*, 2017). Vitellogenin (VTG) proteins are precursors to egg proteins only involved in oocyte production. These proteins are usually only found in males, so can be used as a biomarker of endocrine disrupting effects in males (Kidd *et al.*, 2007; Rojas-Hucks *et al.*, 2019).

In order to determine molecular biomarkers for reproduction and EDC exposure, it is most useful to utilise sexually dimorphic genetic elements. Several have been identified in wild anurans, such as genes (*dmrt1*, *amh*, *cyp17*, *foxL2*, *cyp19*, *rsp01*, ADP/ATP translocase, *DM-W*), microsatellite markers (bfg201, bfg266, W_{HA} 5-22A, rtS03), single nucleotide polymorphisms (raclCT001, -003, -005, -007, -009) entire linkage groups (LG2), and amplified fragment length polymorphisms (Berset-Brändli *et al.*, 2006; Hayes, Stuart, *et al.*, 2006; Uhlenhaut and Treier, 2006; Yoshimoto *et al.*, 2008; Alho, Matsuba and Merilä, 2010; Navarro-Martín *et al.*, 2012; Piprek *et al.*, 2013; Ma *et al.*, 2018; Lambert *et al.*, 2019). The vast majority of molecular work concerning amphibian reproduction regarding EDC exposure has been laboratory based; only two wild studies could be found (Rojas-Hucks *et al.*, 2019; Nemesházi *et al.*, 2020). Agile frogs (*Rana dalmatina*) collected from sites of varying anthropogenic land use in North-Central Hungary showed 20% of phenotypic males being genotypically male according to sex markers developed from toe clippings (Nemesházi *et al.*, 2020). VTG proteins were found in liver samples of 34 out of 36 wild caught male *Xenopus laevis* in Chile, however there were no differences found with changes in land use (Rojas-Hucks *et al.*, 2019).

Tadpole biomonitoring

Tadpoles are often used in ecotoxicological studies due to their presence in water bodies that are likely to be contaminated with chemical pollutants (Cooke, 1981; Babini *et al.*, 2015). As such, the development of anuran larvae may be the most sensitive endpoints to study, and so provide good opportunities for biomonitoring. (Wagner *et al.*, 2013). As anurans tend to produce high numbers of offspring to ensure some will survive to adulthood, it is presumed that small numbers of larvae can be sampled for destructive methods without effect on the overall population (Duellman and Trueb, 1994).

There are many endpoints that are shown to be effective in monitoring the effects of endocrine disruptors on tadpoles, including destructive methods such as, tail clipping, molecular analysis, and histology (Lajmanovich *et al.*, 2010; Carlsson, 2019; Orton, *et al.*, 2023), and non-destructive methods such as clutch size, hatching success, offspring fitness, rate of abnormalities, morphometrics such as mass and length, and rate of metamorphosis (Bishop *et al.*, 1999; McDaniel *et al.*, 2004; Babini *et al.*, 2015; Adams, Gerstle and Brühl, 2021; Orton, *et al.*, 2023). Cage studies, where wild tadpoles are kept within water bodies *in situ* in an enclosure, are also used to allow exposure to environmentally relevant contaminants while allowing for repeated measurements of individuals (Skelly, 1997; Ralph and Petras, 1998; Harris, Bishop and McDaniel, 2001; Brown *et al.*, 2006; Pickford *et al.*, 2015; Pahor-Filho *et al.*, 2019; Castellano and Friard, 2021). However, Rose, (2014) reports that caging of *X. laevis* tadpoles slows growth and development, both of which are commonly used endpoints for exposure of tadpoles to chemical pollutants. Therefore, caging may be having unintended effects on tadpoles being studied and so may skew results. The effects of chemical pollutants on anuran larvae noted throughout the literature are very diverse, and vary depending on many different factors. A good understanding of the ecology of a particular species, such as factors that affect metamorphic rate, is needed to be able to distinguish the effects of ecotoxicology from the effects of environmental changes.

The common frog (*Rana temporaria*)

The common frog (*Rana temporaria*) is a large, temperate species of frog, and is also the only frog species native to Britain. There are three known subspecies: *R. t. temporaria*, *R. t. homnorati*, and *R. t. parvipalmata*. The species inhabits almost all of western Europe (except for Portugal), and is also found as far east as Japan (see **Figure 1.5**). *Rana temporaria* inhabits a wide range of habitats ranging from lowland and mountain forests, through to areas of tundra and forest steppes. It can also inhabit swamps and different kinds of anthropogenic landscape, such as fields, gardens, parks, residential areas, and cities. This species requires waterbodies for breeding and adjacent wetlands and grasslands for foraging and hibernation. *Rana temporaria* adults enter their breeding ponds in spring and spend the remaining seasons foraging for food before hibernating, or brumating during the winter. Hibernation occurs from August - November to February - early June, depending on the latitude and altitude of the population. The breeding season can occur anywhere from January - late June, but peak breeding can be observed in April over the main part of its distribution (AmphibiaWeb, 2020).

Figure 1.5: Global distribution map of countries where *Rana temporaria* is found. Some countries only have *R. temporaria* in certain areas rather than distribution throughout. Created using mapcreate.net.

The diet of the common frog adult consists of a wide variety of isopods, insects, and molluscs, such as slugs and snails, whereas tadpoles consume mainly detritus, algae, and higher plants, with limited amounts of proteinaceous material. Adult male frogs can grow up to 9 cm in length, and females up to 13 cm. Common frogs can be identified by a black patch next to their eye and dark stripes on the hind legs, as well as their classic frog-like morphology (see **Figure 1.6A**). They may also have dark spots on the dorsal surface, which can be used to identify individuals from each other (Petrovan *et al.*, 2024). The colour of adult common frogs varies greatly ranging from grey, green, yellow, brown, orange, and particularly in the Scottish regions, red (Smith, 1954). The tadpoles begin as a dark black colour but develop gold specks as they mature, and late tadpoles and metamorphs resemble the adult form (see **Figure 1.6B**) (pers. obs. C. Whatley). During the breeding season, adult males possess a bluish throat and black nuptial pads for holding onto the female during amplexus. Breeding does not occur below 5°C (Muir, Biek and Mable, 2014), and their life span reaches anywhere from 6 to 17 years at high latitudes (AmphibiaWeb, 2020). The common frog is an explosive breeding species (see Dittrich (2020) for a review of *R. temporaria* reproduction). Amplexus is pectoral (axillary), and sometimes occurs on land on the way to the breeding pond. Reproduction and early development occurs in shallow (5-50 cm) bodies of fresh water such as lakes, ponds, swamps, ditches, river- and stream pools and puddles with stagnant or semi-flowing water. Each small black egg is surrounded by a clear jelly capsule around 1 cm across (Froglife, 2021). The spawn is deposited usually in a large clump containing 670-4500 eggs, which form large deposits with other clumps from mating pairs, although single clumps can also be found (AmphibiaWeb, 2020). Tadpoles have the ability to metamorphose early if they are at risk of desiccation (Loman, 1999).

Figure 1.6: *Rana temporaria* (A) adult with the characteristic black patch behind the eye, as well as the dark stripes on the back legs, and (B) tadpole showing their characteristic gold speckling. Image credit (A) Howard Inns and (B) Fred Holmes. ©ARC Trust. Images reproduced with permission from ARC trust.

Common frog tadpoles are also palatable to a wide range of aquatic predators, and larger pools are inhabited by a rich variety of predators including insects, newts, and fishes. Whilst *R. temporaria* is generally widespread, some local declines have been observed. Habitat fragmentation or loss (Cooke and Arnold, 1982), infilling of breeding ponds, the introduction of competing/predatory biota (Orizaola and Braña, 2006), and pollution events (Mikkelsen and Jenssen, 2006) are likely responsible, as well as over collection for medical research, food, and commercial purposes as a threat in more localised areas of its range. The status is least concern (LC) according to the IUCN Redlist, however this assessment was carried out in 2008, and so needs updating. Increases in temperature for Britain due to climate change (by 2050-2070) may stretch outside the physiological range for *Rana temporaria* (Phillimore *et al.*, 2010). Models predict that the first spawning date for populations in southern Britain need to advance by about 21-39 days, however genetic plasticity in spawning date may only allow an advance of 5-9 days. Genetic flow from more southern populations that are adapted to higher temperatures may help, but as the UK is a highly urbanised island, this is unlikely. Cases of ranaviriosis have also been observed in *R. temporaria* causing mortality (Cunningham *et al.*, 2007). No evidence could be found in the literature of any chytrid cases found in this species to date.

Rana temporaria is widespread across Scotland, stretching in distribution from the English border up to Shetland, including some of the Western isles and the Outer Hebrides (see **Figure 1.7**). Scotland's landscape is known for being especially diverse, with a wide range of habitats such as ancient Atlantic rainforests, grasslands, peatlands, freshwater lochs, mountains, and coastal habitats (Maitland, Boon and McLusky, 1994; Johnson and Thompson, 2002; Maitland, 2012; Ellis and Eaton, 2016; Mitchell *et al.*, 2017; Payne *et al.*, 2018; Burden *et al.*, 2020). Of the total 80,231 km² of Scotland's total land area, the greatest single land use is agriculture, covering 69 % of the total land area (Davis *et al.*, 2022; Office of National Statistics, 2023). Of that 69 %, arable land makes up 8 %, grassland makes up 18 %, and mixed agriculture makes up 20 % (Davis *et al.*, 2022). In 2022, over 4.5 million hectares of land were treated with over 1000 tonnes of pesticides, on 97% of the total crop area (Davis *et al.*, 2022). Percentage land use of these 4.5 million hectares treated with pesticides was broken down as follows: 94% fungicides, 93% herbicides, 56% growth regulators, 19% insecticides, 8% molluscicides (Davis *et al.*, 2022). Further details of the pesticides used in Scotland, which crops they are used for, and the endocrine disrupting and

toxic effects that have been observed in anurans can be found in **Table 1.1**. Overall pesticide use in 2022 was 2 % lower than in 2020, but 1 % higher than in 2018, demonstrating consistent useage across the time frame of this Ph.D. In addition, 91 % of Scotland’s total population reside in only 2.3 % of Scotland’s land area (National Records of Scotland, 2022). Scotland is also home to many different industries, such as tourism, mining, oil and gas, landfill, and engineering works, all of which will have varying degrees of anthropogenic impacts on amphibian populations, and have potential for endocrine disrupting pollution (Gordon and Barron, 2011; Ballantyne *et al.*, 2021). Known pesticide use (see **Table 1.1**), combined with highly concentrated urban areas, and the widespread nature of *R. temporaria* across Scotland indicates that it is likely that *R. temporaria* in Scotland will be exposed to pesticides and other pollutants in the habitats where they are found, thereby exposing them to potential endocrine disruptors.

Figure 1.7: Map of all known *Rana temporaria* records to date (September 2024) across Scotland. Each point, shown in red, represents one record. Map made and adapted from the NBN Atlas (NBN Trust, 2024).

Table 1.1: Summary table of pesticides used across Scotland, which crops they are used for, and the endocrine disrupting and toxic effects that have been observed in anurans. Please note that some pesticides had no appropriate exposure literature that could be found, but this does not indicate a lack of effect. Some of these effects are observed as co-exposures, and with differing water chemistry, but individual effects have been reported where identified. Pesticide data extracted from Davis *et al.* (2022).

Pesticide Group	Formulation	Crop useage	Endocrine disrupting effects on anurans	Other effects on anurans	References
Fungicide/ growth regulators	Azoxystrobin	Legumes	Reduced growth, teratogenicity, increased developmental rate, no effect on mass or SVL at metamorphosis	Mortality, increased Bd susceptibility, reduced quality of leaf litter as tadpole food	Johansson <i>et al.</i> , 2006, Hooser <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Hartman <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Rohr <i>et al.</i> , 2017, Wu <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Bundschuh <i>et al.</i> , 2021
	Chlormequat	Winter barley, Spring oats, Winter rye		None	
	Folpet	Winter and spring barley, Winter wheat	Altered breeding gland morphology	Mortality, reduced locomotor activity, reduced feeding behaviour	Van Wyk <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Adams, Gerstle and Brühl, 2021, Leeb <i>et al.</i> , 2022
	Mancozeb	Seed and ware potatoes	Altered breeding gland morphology, reduced size, delayed development, no effect on total length, delays in breeding and reaching sexual maturity	Mortality, reduced DHT levels, microcephaly, abnormal swimming behaviour, oedema, altered epidermal pigmentation, disrupted respiratory metabolism, reduced thermal tolerance	Van Wyk <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Sana <i>et al.</i> , 2015, Asparch, Svartz and Pérez Coll, 2020, Azambuja <i>et al.</i> , 2021
	Mepiquat chloride	Oilseeds		None	
	Metconazole	Oilseeds		Mortality	Cusaac <i>et al.</i> , 2015, 2016
	Prohexadione-calcium	Oilseeds		None	
	Prothioconazole	Winter and spring oats, oilseeds		None	
Spiroxamine	Spring oats		None		

	Tebuconazole	Spring wheat, oilseeds	Reduced metamorphic success, delayed time to metamorphosis, increased mass, no effect on SVL and body length, accelerated development	Mortality, changes to tail fin morphology, abnormal mouth, limb deformities, oedema, skeletal abnormalities, intersex occurrence, liver and kidney inflammation and necrosis, histological abnormalities, oxidative stress, hepatic lesions	Bernabò <i>et al.</i> , 2016, 2020, Warsneski <i>et al.</i> , 2024
	Trinexapac-ethyl	Spring barley, Winter and spring wheat		None	
Herbicides/ Desiccants	Carfentrazone-ethyl	Seed potatoes		None	
	Diflufenican	Winter wheat, Winter oats		None	
	Florasulam	Spring wheat		None	
	Flufenacet	Winter wheat, Winter oats		None	
	Fluroxypyr	Spring oats		None	
	Glyphosate	Winter barley, Oilseeds, Legumes	No effect on growth, decreased SVL, increased time to metamorphosis, decreased mass, decreased total length	Mortality, elevated thyroid hormone receptor P mRNA transcript levels, tail damage, gonadal abnormalities, impaired mobility	Howe <i>et al.</i> , 2004, Dinehart <i>et al.</i> , 2009, Edge <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Edge <i>et al.</i> , 2014 (a,b), Agostini <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Herek <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	Halauxifen-methyl	Spring wheat		None	
	Metsulfuron-methyl	Spring barley		Mortality, glutathione S- transferase (GST) and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibition, increase in erythrocyte nuclear abnormalities	Lajmanovich <i>et al.</i> , 2013

	Pendimethalin	Winter rye	Delayed hatching, reduced hatching success, decreased total length	Mortality, bioaccumulation, reduced oxygen consumption	Van Meter <i>et al.</i> , 2014, 2015, Ponopal, Brînzea and Păunescu, 2017
	Picolinafen	Winter rye		None	
	Pyraflufen-ethyl	Ware potatoes		None	
	Thifensulfuron-methyl	Spring barley		None	
Insecticides	Esfenvalerate	Winter barley, Ware potatoes	Growth inhibition	Mortality, convulsive twitching, deformities, heart and gut malformations, underdeveloped gills, oedema	Materna, Rabeni and Lapoint, 1995, Danish EPA, 2004, Kittusamy <i>et al.</i> , 2014
	Lambda-cyhalothrin	Spring barley, Winter wheat, Winter and spring oats, Winter rye, Oilseeds, Seed potatoes, Legumes		Mortality, inhibition of GST, carboxylesterase, and lactate dehydrogenase, behaviour changes, larvae malformations, oxidative stress, cytotoxicity	Aydin-Sinan, Gungordu and Ozmen, 2012, Nkontcheu <i>et al.</i> , 2017, Jiang <i>et al.</i> , 2019, Barreto <i>et al.</i> , 2024
Molluscicides	Ferric phosphate	Winter barley, Winter wheat, Winter oats, Oilseeds, Seed potatoes, Ware potatoes		None	
	Metaldehyde	Winter rye		None	
Seed treatments	Fludioxonil	Winter and spring wheat, winter and spring oats, Winter rye, Ware potatoes		Mortality, severe embryo malformations, microcephaly, abnormal pigmentation, underdeveloped gills, oedema, spasmodic contractions, weakness	Svartz <i>et al.</i> , 2016, 2018
	Fluopyram	Winter barley		None	
	Flutolanil	Seed potatoes		None	

	Fluxapyroxad	Winter rye	Delayed growth and development	Mortality, liver injury, glycogen accumulation, lipid depletion, alterations to gut microbiome	Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2023, 2024
	Imazalil	Spring Barley		None	
	Ipconazole	Spring Barley		None	
	Prothioconazole	Winter barley		None	
	Tebuconazole	Winter barley	Reduced metamorphic success, delayed time to metamorphosis, increased mass, no effect on SVL and body length, accelerated development	Mortality, changes to tail fin morphology, abnormal mouth, limb deformities, oedema, skeletal abnormalities, intersex occurrence, liver and kidney inflammation and necrosis, histological abnormalities, oxidative stress, hepatic lesions	Bernabò <i>et al.</i> , 2016, 2020; Warsneski <i>et al.</i> , 2024
	Triticonazole	Winter rye		None	
Sulphur	Sulphur	Winter barley, Spring barley, Winter wheat, Spring wheat, Spring oats, Legumes		None	

In *R. temporaria*, the processes of sex determination and differentiation are complicated, as it has been shown that both genetic and environmental factors vary between populations. Firstly, the genetic contribution to sex determination and the number of sex chromosomes varies between different populations (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2016). Secondly, there exist some populations of *R. temporaria* that demonstrate what are known as ‘undifferentiated races’, whereby some populations present at metamorphic climax with all individuals having ovaries (Amanuma, 1963; Norris and Lopez, 2011). Roughly 6-9 months after metamorphosis, some individuals go through an intersexual stage, and develop into males (Amanuma, 1963; Norris and Lopez, 2011). Finally, *R. temporaria* exhibits temperature-dependent sex determination (TDSD), whereby the rearing temperature of the tadpoles affects changes to gonadal development. High rearing temperatures ($\geq 25^{\circ}\text{C}$) produce a masculinising effect, and low rearing temperatures ($\leq 12^{\circ}\text{C}$) produce a feminising effect (Witschi, 1914). Altogether, this process is very complex in this species, and presents a challenge in forming baselines with which to compare changes arising from pollutant exposure, thereby making sexual determination and differentiation of this species difficult to use in biomonitoring.

Rana temporaria has potential as a test species for use in the assessment of risk for endocrine disruption in European frogs. It is widespread across Europe and parts of Asia, and is sensitive to estrogenic compounds. For example, Pettersson and Berg (2007) report the effects of environmentally relevant concentrations of EE2 in the environment (0.06 nM) on *Rana temporaria*, causing a skewed female dominated sex ratio. In this study, survival rates from hatching until metamorphosis were high, and time to metamorphosis was short compared to studies of other Ranid species. The variation in timing and type of sex differentiation pattern as well as high post-metamorphic mortality rate in *R. temporaria* is a disadvantage, however it was suggested that this was due to poor husbandry rather than EE2 exposure. Provided that methodology for post-metamorph husbandry is improved, *R. temporaria* could be used as a model species in parallel with other more commonly used model species, such as *X. laevis* and *X. tropicalis*.

Conclusion

There are a wide variety of causes of amphibian declines globally, which often co-occur. One cause of particular concern is anthropogenic pollution, especially chemical pollution. The natural ecology of amphibians makes them particularly vulnerable to chemical pollutants (Boone *et al.*, 2024). In order to effectively conserve amphibians in the wild, it is crucial to be able to both detect the presence of chemical pollution, as well as be able to observe and fully understand their effects. If reproduction and recruitment are significantly affected in a population, long term effects could lead to further endangerment and extinction of a species. Data collection is needed over time to be able to establish baselines, identify trends, and carry out long term monitoring of the environment (Biek *et al.*, 2002; Storfer, 2003; Magurran *et al.*, 2010; Lindenmayer *et al.*, 2012).

It is of critical importance that effective methods of detecting EDC exposure and the subsequent impacts on amphibian reproductive health and growth and development are developed. The extent to which EDCs affect reproduction in amphibians is unknown, particularly in the wild, and more studies are needed in order for more concrete conclusions to be drawn (reviewed in Orton and Tyler, 2015). Lots of experimental work has been carried out in laboratory settings, however it is tricky to extrapolate these data to population level data (Beebee and Griffiths, 2005). Biomarkers for amphibian ecotoxicology have previously been reviewed (Venturino *et al.*, 2003; Venturino and Pechen de D'Angelo, 2005), however more emphasis on field-based biomarkers is needed. A recent review on non-destructive biomonitoring techniques for pollution in frogs and toads was published, to which the author contributed significantly and is listed as a co-author (Orton *et al.*, 2023). In particular, the development of non-destructive measures should be a research priority, as the collection of samples via destructive methods does not align with conservation goals, especially in endangered species. It is also crucial that a wider spectrum of amphibians is studied with more emphasis on neglected groups such as tropical anurans, as well as caudates and caecilians. When selecting the most appropriate biomonitoring methodologies, knowledge of the natural history and ecology of a species is key, especially when utilising non-destructive methods.

A wide variety of potential biomarkers have been discussed in this review. Whilst some biomarker categories are more generally applicable to all anurans, such as sex ratio or molecular work, some are much more specific, such as looking at SSCs related to fighting, such as spines, which are more typically found in tropical anuran species. Some potential biomarkers identified in this review are not suitable for use in this Ph.D. project, for example examining calling behaviours, as they require specialist equipment that is unavailable. Other biomarkers such as larynx size is a destructive biomarker, and would require the destructive sampling of adult frogs which in conflict with the aims of this project regarding the prioritisation of non-destructive sampling. Biomarkers can be a useful tool in environmental monitoring, by utilizing many different biological parameters ranging from the chemical residues present in tissue and bodily fluid samples, to looking at specific biological endpoints such as fertility or fecundity. However, there are many limitations that must be considered when determining which biomarkers are suitable, such as the effects of different biotic and abiotic factors, levels of contaminant exposure, and the ability of an organism to remedy the effects of exposure that must be considered when carrying out biomarker research. A multivariate approach utilizing several different biomonitoring tools may prove most effective, and a good understanding of the ecology and natural history of a species is key to interpreting results and drawing conclusions.

Thesis aims

The aim of this thesis was therefore to investigate and assess non-destructive biomonitoring tools for *Rana temporaria* (common frog) reproductive health, growth, and development with regards to endocrine disrupting pollution in Scotland. This thesis also aimed to compare novel biomonitoring tools developed and refined during the course of this project to more established destructive methods, such as gene expression and histological analysis. This was achieved through the following objectives:

In **Chapter 2**, *R. temporaria* breeding sites were sampled in Scotland and a range of morphometrics measured in adult frogs and tadpoles. This allowed investigation into relationships between *R. temporaria* morphometrics and characteristics of the sites such as land use and water quality. Another aim of this chapter was to measure androgenic/anti-androgenic activity in the pond water at these sites, via the optimisation of two cell-based luminescence transactivation assays. Unfortunately, this could not be optimised as part of this thesis. The protocols developed are presented in **Appendices 2.5-2.7**.

Tadpole gonads that were sampled at the sites investigated in Chapter 2, were then investigated in **Chapter 3** for gonad morphology and expression of masculinising and feminising genes with the objective of linking to site characteristics (from Chapter 2).

Finally in **Chapter 4**, water samples and water quality from six different *R. temporaria* neonatal ponds were taken to determine how trace element concentrations and water quality parameters affect tadpole growth and development.

Chapter Two: Determination of land-use type and water quality of *Rana temporaria* breeding sites and their relationship with adult and tadpole morphometrics

Information in this Chapter contributed to:

Orton, F., Roberts-Rhodes, B., Moore, E., Whatley, C. and Tyler, C.R., 2023. Nuptial pad (“breeding gland”) morphology is related to non-random mating in wild male common frogs (*Rana temporaria*). *Ethology*. Vol. 129(4-5), pp.232-239.

Introduction

Land use change and habitat loss are the biggest causes of amphibian declines, with chemical pollution also a factor of concern (Gallant *et al.*, 2007; Díaz *et al.*, 2019; Luedtke *et al.*, 2023). Their moist semi-permeable skin makes amphibians particularly susceptible to chemical pollution and environmental factors such as desiccation. Habitat loss disrupts already limited distribution ranges of amphibians by increasing distance between sites that are important to particular amphibian species (Smith and Green, 2005). For example, Boissinot *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that the occurrence of small mosaics of woodland (~1 ha) positively affected lowland populations of *R. temporaria*, as it allows easier travel between areas with a reduced risk of predation or desiccation. Two environmental factors that affect amphibian populations are land use surrounding amphibian habitats (Houlahan and Findlay, 2003; Gray and Smith, 2005; Taylor *et al.*, 2005; Babini *et al.*, 2015) and water quality (Odum and Zippel, 2008; Calderon *et al.*, 2019). Chemical pollution, especially from agricultural sources, has also been shown to affect amphibian health and development (Rouse, Bishop, and Struger, 1999; Taylor *et al.*, 2005; Orton and Tyler, 2015).

Rana temporaria are ideal model organisms for investigating anthropogenic effects on amphibians. They are found in a wide range of aquatic and terrestrial habitats (e.g. bogs, pastures, woods and even high altitudes in the highlands of Scotland), with their larval development mostly occurring in small ponds, often near agricultural land where exposure to chemical pollution is high. Their ecology is well understood, including their reproduction, and populations have been shown to be affected by pesticide pollution (Johansson *et al.*, 2005; Vos *et al.*, 2007; Brühl *et al.*, 2013). *Rana temporaria* is an explosively breeding species, categorised as having short breeding periods (on a scale of days-weeks) which involve male-male competition for mating opportunities with females (Wells, 1977). As such, adult male frogs possess secondary sex characteristics (SSCs), with an ‘ideal’ male possessing a big body size/mass (to assist in fighting off rival males), big forearms, and large, darkly coloured nuptial pads (to hold onto the female during amplexus). These SSCs are under androgenic control and so are vulnerable to endocrine disrupting pollution (Orton and Tyler, 2015). This is reflected in the literature regarding other anurans. Nuptial pads have been shown to reduce in size in different *Xenopus* spp.: Exposure to the anti-androgens flutamide and vinclozolin at 100 µg/g/week (Wyk, Pool, and Leslie, 2003), and 2.5 ng/L

atrazine (Hayes *et al.*, 2010) in *X. laevis*, and exposure to 10 ng/L of the estrogen EE2 in *X. tropicalis* (Iguchi, 2011). Inversely, exposure to 10.5 nM of the androgen levonorgestrol increased developmental speed of the nuptial pad. Exposure to endocrine disrupting trace metals increased the size of nuptial pads, and forelimb width in wild *Bufo raddei*, as well as inducing calling behaviours, an earlier breeding season and a lower body size condition (Guo *et al.*, 2018).

Water quality parameters such as elevated pH, low dissolved oxygen (DO) levels, and higher water temperatures have been linked to western agricultural ecosystems, with these different stressors acting singularly or in combination (Boyer and Grue, 1995). Water quality parameters have also been shown to affect amphibian health and development, with most studies focusing on amphibian larvae as the majority are confined to the water during this stage of their life cycle. For example, Godfrey and Sanders (2004) showed that water hardness (conductivity of 2,000 to 2,100 μ S) affected the embryo development of *X. laevis*, with only 20-25 % of embryos reaching the tailbud stages at low hardness levels, increasing up to 70 % with the addition of salts to increase water hardness. Low pH of water has been linked to the mobilisation of aluminium from pond sediments, reducing amphibian embryo survival (Boyer and Grue, 1995). *Rana temporaria* tadpoles can also have reduced survival when temperature shocked (10 to 2 °C) in their natal pondwater (Beattie, Tyler-Tones and Baxter, 1992).

Changes in *R. temporaria* morphometrics at sites more chemically polluted than others (such as agricultural areas where pesticides are likely to be applied, compared to nature reserves which are assumed to be ‘cleaner’) could be an indicator of poor health or stress that affects growth and development, or reproductive fitness. Effective biomonitoring relies on baseline data of environmental parameters within an organism’s habitat, such as water quality. This allows subsequent measurements over time to be compared to ‘baseline’ levels in order for effective management and conservation of species and environments. Tools such as GIS (Geographic Information Systems) and environmental modelling are excellent, not only for creating baselines for biomonitoring, but also for drawing conclusions about an organism and its environment in a minimally invasive and non-destructive way (Collier, Haigh and Kelly,

2007). The majority of literature concerning the effects of water quality and chemical pollution on amphibians are lab studies, which while useful, are less ecologically relevant and are often destructive in nature in order to investigate physiological endpoints. The ability to use modelling to assess how certain environmental factors affect the growth and development of organisms provides a powerful non-destructive biomonitoring tool. Therefore, the aim of this Chapter was to determine whether land use characteristics (within a 0.5 mile radius) and water quality affected morphometrics of both tadpoles and adult male *R. temporaria* in the wild.

Methodology

Site selection

Study sites were selected based on recommendations from an established network of amphibian-interest volunteers. In addition, sites that could potentially be polluted through surrounding land use types were searched for using Google Maps, based on visual inspection of the land use type surrounding the area (such as golf courses, agricultural areas, and areas of industry). Potential sites were visited during the day to determine the practical suitability for fieldwork, as well as to confirm the presence of *R. temporaria* (depending on season through the sighting of adults, larvae, or spawn, or other indicators such as calling). Sites were deemed unsuitable either if there was no sign of *R. temporaria* at the site, or if the site was impractical for fieldwork purposes (i.e. inaccessible or unsafe to access the pond). In total, 14 sites from across the central belt of Scotland were selected. Full details of the sites selected are given in **Table 2.1**.

Table 2.1: Fieldwork sites selected, and the number of adults and tadpoles sampled for morphometric data. Water samples were also collected from these sites for later analysis using a cell-based luminescence assay for androgenic/anti-androgenic activity (see Chapter 3).

Site Name	Site Type	GPS co-ordinates	No. of Tadpoles (morphometrics)	Water sample extracted	No. of male frogs (morphometrics)
Ravenswood Bog	Suburban nature reserve	NS 74559 73765	20	Yes	0
Erik's Pond	Agricultural/Rural	NS 62971 51066	30	Yes	3
Victoria Park	Urban park	NS 53782 67339	20	Yes	0
Arcadia	Rural	NS 47954 88310	23	Yes	0
Langlands Gate	Suburban nature reserve	NS 63902 51108	15	Yes	0
Glasgow University	Urban park	NS 56758 66936	20	Yes	16
Froggy Pond	Suburban park	NT 05106 65871	20	Yes	15
Endfield Avenue	Urban garden	NS 55828 68695	10	Yes	0
Craigmore	Suburban garden	NS 41741 66565	20	Yes	0
Irvine	Rural garden	NS 36950 42364	9	No	16
Robroyston	Urban park	NS 62810 68097	-	No	20
Campbridge Ponds	Suburban park	NT 05130 64035	-	Yes	19
Hunterstone	Pond at nuclear power plant	NS 18496 51962	10	Yes	-
Laurieston	Rural	NX 67600 65600	7	Yes	-
Total			204	12	89

Adult frog sampling and morphometrics (2021)

Once sites were selected, fieldwork to collect adult frog morphometrics was carried out at night from February to April in 2021 (see **Table 2.3**). The exact site to visit each night was determined using a combination of ideal weather parameters for *R. temporaria* breeding (above 5°C for several nights, and no extremes of wind or rain), as well as information about breeding sightings in different areas given by the established amphibian volunteer network. Previous work has found that *R. temporaria* prefers to breed at about 4-5°C night air temperature, and in almost any weather with the exception of excessive wind or rain (Muir, Biek and Mable, 2014).

A photograph (Canon digital SLR 2000), an air temperature reading (mercury thermometer) and a water quality reading (Hanna waterproof multiparameter meter HI-98194) was taken at each site as well as detailed notes about any defining site characteristics, such as the presence of any predators, other amphibian species, any plastic or detritus pollution, or any dead amphibians or individuals showing signs of disease. Adult frogs were collected from ponds by hand, and separated if a pair was found to be in amplexus. Adult males were weighed using a mesh bag and a hanging scale, their snout-vent length measurement (SVL) was taken by laying the male ventral side down on a ruler. Measurements of the forelimb width were taken using callipers, as well as nuptial pad length. Nuptial pad colouration score was determined using the methodology outlined in Orton *et al.* (2023), to which data and methods from this Ph.D. Chapter contributed significantly (see **Appendix 2.1**).

Tadpole sampling and morphometrics (2021 and 2022)

Collection of tadpole morphometrics was carried out from May to July in both 2021 and 2022. Sites were visited for sampling during the day based on the adult breeding observed earlier in the year, or by using the established amphibian volunteer network. Up to 20 tadpoles per site (see **Table 2.1**) were removed from the pond using a net and stored in a clean 37 × 22 × 25 cm faunarium (Exo Terra) with approximately 1 L of pond water until processing (either in the lab following transportation (2021), or in the field (2022)).

Ten litres of pond water (or less if water levels were low) were collected in glass jars from selected sites (**Table 2.1**; both reference sites and those suspected to be polluted with EDCs). Water samples were fixed by adding ultrapure methanol to a final concentration of 1%, and stored at in the dark at 4°C until extraction, for the purposes of measuring androgenic/androgenic activity of the pond water (see **Appendix 2.6**). A water quality measurement was also taken of water temperature (°C), salinity (psu), pH, conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), TDS (ppm), and dissolved oxygen (DO) (ppm) of the pond water. Salinity, TDS, and conductivity are all measures of water quality that are closely related; TDS and salinity are often converted from conductivity readings measured by a water quality probe (Corwin and Yemoto, 2020). This is usually considered an accurate representation of the relationship between these parameters within a water body, although other factors can affect these parameters, and therefore the efficacy of the probe conversion. These factors are hard to identify, and are not always linear (Rusydi, 2018). The ability to measure each of these parameters individually requires equipment unavailable as part of this Ph.D., and so these water quality parameters were all measured using water quality probes, as is standard practice.

For the 2021 tadpoles collected, once transported back to the lab, tadpoles were euthanised by submersion in a 1% buffered methocaine trisulphate solution (MS222) for 2 minutes or until all movement had ceased, and brain death ensured by pithing (inserting a needle into the brain). Snout-vent length (mm) and total tadpole length (mm) were measured using callipers, and mass (g) was recorded on scales after patting dry to remove excess liquid. Tail length (mm) was calculated by subtracting SVL from total tadpole length. Tadpoles were then dissected to remove the liver and gonads for gene expression and histological analysis (see **Chapter 3**). For the 2022 tadpoles collected, euthanasia, measurements, and dissections were carried out in the field and mass was not collected due to lack of access to a scale. All other methodologies remained the same.

GIS analysis of land use type

Sites were analysed using QGIS (version 3.24.3). The sites were characterised in order to calculate the percentage land use type within a 0.5 mile radius of the sample collection point of each site. The land use layer selected was the Corine UK land use dataset from 2018 (Cole *et al.*, 2021). Corine Land Cover (CLC) datasets are produced by the EU Copernicus programme on land monitoring, providing consistent information on land cover and land cover changes across Europe. These datasets are created through photointerpretation of satellite images, and land use categorising into 44 land use classes (see **Figure 2.1**). The minimum mapping unit (MMU) of status layers is 25 ha, so any land cover smaller than 25 ha will not be included within the resolution of this map (Cole *et al.*, 2021).

The study site data were collated into Excel along with Northing and Easting OS values for each sample collection point. These data were then uploaded into QGIS as a vector in EPSG 27700 (National Grid). The Corine UK Land Use dataset for 2018 (the latest dataset available) was uploaded as a layer, and the associated style was loaded that gives colour values to all distinct categories (see **Figure 2.1**). A buffer of 804.672 m (0.5 miles) was uploaded around each data point, and the area of each buffer zone was calculated using the \$CatchArea function in the attribute table.

Figure 2.1: Original 44 land use classifications and their associated map colours from the Corine 2018 UK land cover dataset.

The buffers around each point were intersected with the Corine land use map, and then the original Corine dataset layer was removed to leave the buffer zones with the land use types within. The class area of each land use type was calculated using the \$ClassArea function within the attribute table, and then the percentage land use type for each buffer zone was calculated in the attribute table using the formula (“ClassArea”/”CatchArea”)*100. Results were exported to Excel for data clean up. More detail on GIS methods is provided in **Appendix 2.2**.

The number of land cover classifications was then refined in order to reduce the number of overall classes, as well as allow better identification of land use types likely to be responsible for pollution that may affect morphology of *R. temporaria* (such as golf courses, industry, and agricultural areas). This was done by combining certain land use codes into new categories once the percentage GIS land use of each site was calculated. Final defined land-use types that were used in statistical analysis, along with the CLC codes which were combined are given in **Table 2.2**.

Figure 2.2: Location of fieldwork sites generated using QGIS. Image was created by overlaying site coordinates onto the Corine 2018 land use dataset for the UK. A buffer zone of 0.5 miles was then created around each point. Sites are marked with a white circle. Colours shown here correspond to the key shown in **Figure 2.1**.

Table 2.2: Final land use categories used in this study, adapted from the CLC 2018 nomenclature guide (https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/technical-library/corine-land-cover-nomenclature-guidelines/docs/pdf/CLC2018_Nomenclature_illustrated_guide_20190510.pdf). CLC codes combined for each land use type are shown. Land use types used for analysis were condensed from 44 to 14 categories that were most relevant to amphibian ecology and pollutant potential.

Land use type	Definition	CLC codes covered
Urban fabric	Areas mainly occupied by dwellings and buildings used by administrative/public utilities (including connected areas such as associated lands, approach road network, and car parks). Continuous and discontinuous areas of urban fabric covering >30% of land surface area.	111-112
Green urban	Areas voluntarily created for recreational use. Includes green or recreational and leisure urban parks, sport and leisure facilities including golf courses.	141-142
Industrial urban	Areas mainly occupied by industrial activities of manufacturing, trade, financial activities and services, transport infrastructures for road traffic and rail networks, airport installations, river and sea port installations, industrial livestock rearing facilities, and mining and construction.	121-133
Arable land	Lands under a rotation system used for annually harvested plants and fallow lands, which are rain-fed or irrigated. Includes flooded crops such as rice fields and other inundated croplands.	211-213
Pastures	Lands that are permanently used (at least 5 years) for fodder production. Includes natural or sown herbaceous species, unimproved or lightly improved meadows and grazed or mechanically harvested meadows. Regular agriculture impact influences the natural development of natural herbaceous species composition.	231
Agricultural land with natural vegetation	Areas where a mosaic of parcels <25 ha of agricultural land (arable crops, pasture, permanent crops) are intermixed with natural vegetation and natural areas (<25 ha) that occupy >25% and <75% of the area.	243
Other agriculture	All other agricultural areas including areas of annual crops associated with permanent crops on the same parcel, annual crops cultivated under forest trees, areas of annual crops, meadows and/or permanent crops which are juxtaposed, landscapes in which crops and pastures are intimately mixed with natural vegetation or natural areas.	241-244
Permanent crops	All surfaces occupied by permanent crops, not under a rotation system. Includes ligneous crops of standard cultures for fruit production such as extensive fruit orchards,	221-223

	olive groves, chestnut groves, walnut groves, shrub orchards such as vineyards and some specific low-system orchard plantation, espaliers and climbers.	
Forests	Areas occupied by forests and woodlands with a vegetation pattern composed of native or exotic coniferous and/or broad leaved trees and which can be used for the production of timber or other forest products. The forest trees are under normal climatic conditions higher than 5 m with a canopy closure of 30% at least.	311-313
Scrubland	Transitional bushy and herbaceous vegetation with occasional scattered trees.	321-324
Open space with little/no vegetation	Natural areas covered with little or no vegetation, such as steppic grasslands, perennial steppe-like grasslands, meso- and thermos-Mediterranean xerophile, mostly open, short-grass perennial grasslands, alpha steppes, vegetated or sparsely vegetated area of stones on steep slopes, screes, cliffs, rock faces, limestone pavements with plant communities colonising their tracks, perpetual snow and ice, inland sand-dune, coastal sand-dunes and burnt natural woody vegetation areas.	331-335
Freshwater wetland	Low-lying land usually flooded in winter, and with ground more or less saturated by fresh water all year round.	411-412
Marine wetlands	Vegetated low-lying areas in the coastal zone, above the high-tide line, susceptible to flooding by sea water. Often in the process of being filled in by coastal mud and sand sediments, gradually being colonized by halophilic plants.	421-423
Freshwater water bodies	Lakes, ponds and pools of natural origin containing fresh (i.e. non-saline) water and running waters made of all rivers and streams. Man-made freshwater bodies including reservoirs and canals.	511-512
Saline water bodies	Oceanic and continental shelf waters, bays and narrow channels including sea lochs or loughs, fiords, or fjords, rya straits and estuaries. Saline or brackish coastal waters often formed from sea inlets by being cut-off from the sea by sand or mud banks.	521-523
No data	No data available.	990-999

Statistical analysis

Generalised linear mixed effects models (GLMERs) were run using the package ‘lme4’ in R Studio (version 3.6.1) to investigate the fixed effects of land use characteristics or water quality (temperature, salinity, pH, conductivity, TDS, and DO) on morphometric measurements in both tadpoles and adult male *R. temporaria*. Land use and water quality were analysed in separate models, and site and year (for tadpoles only) were considered as random effects. The response variables for tadpoles were mass (g) (only collected in 2021), total length (mm), and snout to vent length (SVL) (mm). As tadpole morphometrics change as metamorphosis occurs, all tadpole morphometrics were used within models as a function of tadpole developmental (Gosner) stage (see **Appendix 1.1**). For the adult male frogs these were mass (g), nuptial pad length (mm), nuptial pad colour (average RGB value), forelimb width (mm), and snout to vent length (SVL) (mm).

There are discrepancies in the number of sites between different adult and tadpole morphometrics. This is due to the fact that adult morphometric data were only collected in 2021, and so there are data collected from fewer sites compared to most tadpole morphometric parameters. Tadpole mass was also only collected in 2021, and so there are data from fewer sites presented.

GLMER was selected as the best model to analyse these data because the response variables are numeric in nature, and the data are hierarchical in structure (i.e. tadpoles or adult frogs within different sites), therefore a linear mixed effects model suited the data the best. As the data were continuous but not proportional, Gamma models with an identity link function were used for the water quality models, and Gaussian models with an identity link function were used for the land use models, as these were the most effective. Model selection was made by fitting a model using all terms, and removing non-significant effects in a stepwise fashion in order to create the most parsimonious models according to the AIC values generated. GLMER models were validated using the DHARMA package in R.

The issue of collinearity was identified as a potential cause for concern in this Chapter, whereby different explanatory variables within a statistical model are correlated with each other (Vanhove, 2021). However, as has been previously identified within the body of literature, the concept of collinearity is a natural part of research and the relationships between different environmental variables that are intrinsically linked, and to remove them arbitrarily would not be representative of the ecological exposures of the tadpoles in this study (Morrissey and Ruxton, 2018; Vanhove, 2021). Instead, by removing non-significant effects from the model, the most significant variables contributing to model effects were identified, and only these were used within the statistical analyses. For visual representation, the figures in the results section show linear regressions of morphological variables against site parameters, but are provided with statistical values from the GLMER. For multiple regression where the relationship of the response variable to one or more explanatory variables is considered, the expected values of the response variable may be described by multiple explanatory variables (Morrissey and Ruxton, 2018), rather than a single explanatory variable acting in a linear manner. Therefore, significance may be identified by the GLMER, even if a linear relationship is not obvious.

Results

Site Overview

In order to better ascertain the likelihood of EDC exposure of *R. temporaria* at each site in the absence of measured data, descriptions of each site are presented in **Table 2.3** and the water quality at each site in **Table 2.4**. Data on the frequency of each Gosner stage of development at each site is shown in **Figure 2.3** with the raw data for each tadpole morphometric (mass, total length, SVL, and tail length) according Gosner stage for each site is presented in **Appendix 2.3**. The different percentages of land use surrounding each pond (0.5 miles) are presented in **Table 2.5**.

Table 2.3 demonstrates a range of pond types, sizes, and water sources, as well as a range of different amphibian species assemblages between sites. This wide range in pond characteristics demonstrates the diversity of sites used in this Chapter, and can allow for some basic comparisons and

interpretation of results between sites. **Table 2.4** also demonstrates the range of water quality found at all the different sites utilised in this Chapter. For example, Endfield Avenue and Laurieston are very similar in their water quality profiles, however they are very different in pond characteristics (**Table 2.3**) and land use (**Table 2.5**).

Table 2.3: Observations of pond characteristics at each site representing qualitative information only.

Pond Name	GPS co-ordinates	Pond Type	Size	Man made or Natural	Water Source	Other species
Glasgow University	NS 56758 66936	Wildlife research pond	Small	Man made	Rainwater	None
Erik's Pond	NS 62971 51066	Agricultural	Large	Natural	Rainwater and groundwater	Palmate newt and Smooth newt
Froggy Pond	NT 05106 65871	Suburban park	Large	Man made	Rainwater and tap water	Common toad
Ravenswood Bog	NS 74559 73765	Nature reserve	Large	Natural	Rainwater and groundwater	Common toad, Palmate newt
Victoria Park	NS 53782 67339	Urban park	Medium	Man made	Rainwater and tap water	Palmate newt
Arcadia	NS 47954 88310	Wider agricultural landscape	Medium	Natural	Natural spring and rainwater	Common toad, Palmate newt
Endfield Avenue	NS 55828 68695	Garden pond	Small	Man made	Rainwater	None
Craigmore	NS 41741 66565	Garden Pond	Small	Man made	Rainwater	None
Irvine	NS 36950 42364	Garden pond	Medium	Manmade	Rainwater	Palmate Newt
Langlands Gate	NS 63902 51108	Lake in private grounds	Medium	Natural	Rainwater and groundwater	None
Hunterstone	NS 18496 51962	Ditch near nuclear facility	Small	Man made	Unknown pipe and rainwater	Common toad
Laurieston	NX 67600 65600	Ditch near golf course	Large	Natural	Rainwater and groundwater	Common toad
Cambridge Ponds	NT 05130 64035	Suburban park	Large	Man made	Rainwater and groundwater	None
Robroyston	NS 62810 68097	Urban Park	Large	Natural	Rainwater and Groundwater	Common toad

Table 2.4: Water quality at each site where tadpoles were collected, and adult frogs were caught during the fieldwork for Chapter 2. Only one value is presented for each site, because each site was only visited once. Gaps in the data are due to equipment failures in the field.

Site	Salinity (psu)	Temp (°C)	pH	Conductivity (µs/cm)	TDS (ppm)	DO (ppm)
Ravenswood Bog	0.05	14.5	6.67	107	54	5.39
Erik's Pond	0.26	15.76	6.87	530	265	4.63
Victoria Park						
Arcadia	0.05	11.06	6.37	108	54	7.27
Langlands Gate	0.1	10.43	6.54	215	108	9.3
Glasgow University	0.06	5.11	6.25	135	42	6.34
Froggy Pond	0.56	8.75	7.14	1120	135	5.02
Endfield Avenue	0.04	12.34	5.71	67	56	4.86
Craigmore	0.03	10.92	6.45	146	120	6.37
Irvine	0.05	19.95	5.65	102	55	3.98
Robroyston	0.08	9.08	6.3	159	79	8.52
Campbridge Pond	0.31	9.48	7.59	647		
Hunterstone	0.09	12.51	6.65	193	96	
Laurieston	0.04	15.39	6.07	79	40	

Land use percentages

Land use percentages per site were calculated using QGIS and the results for each site are displayed in **Table 2.5**.

There is a wide variety of both the number and types of land use surrounding different study sites (**Table 2.5**). For example, Erik's pond and Langland's gate are both surrounded by six different land use types, whereas Endfield Avenue consists of only two with more than 95 % of land surrounding this pond being classed as Urban. There is a lot of diversity within the sites utilised within this chapter.

Table 2.5: Table summarising the percentage land use types within a 0.5 mile radius for all study sites. Note: all land use types that did not pertain to any sites (Other agriculture, Permanent crops, Open space with little/no vegetation, and No data) have been excluded from this table. Any spaces with no percentage data are equal to 0 % of that land use type for that site.

Year	Site	Continuous/ discontinuous urban fabric	Green urban	Industrial urban	Arable land	Pastures	Agricultural land with natural vegetation	Forests	Scrubland	Freshwater wetland	Saline wetland	Freshwater water bodies	Saline water bodies
2021	Glasgow University	87.02	12.98										
2021	Irvine					100							
2021	Robroyston	51.9	31.45			16.65							
2021	Erik's Pond	4.65	14.51	0.49	3.9	54.62		21.83					
2021	Cambridge Pond	35.18		1.84		62.98							
2021	Froggy Pond	58.25	16.47 92	25.27				0.000 8					
2021	Ravenswood Bog	62.44		35.99				1.57					
2021	Aberuthven	15.52			84.48								
2021	Victoria Park	76.93		19.5								3.57	

2021	Arcadia	16.73				69.33	9.92		4.02
2021	Endfield Avenue	95.69	4.31						
2021	Craigmore	46.02			33.47			20.51	
2021	Langlands Gate	1.99	18.67	23.05	15.21	25.09		15.99	
2021	Hundleshope				13.29	59.37		4.3	23.04
2022									
2022	Irvine	100							
2022	Langlands Gate	1.99	18.67	23.05	15.21	25.09		15.99	
2022	Hunterston			23.71		18.8	11.64		40.76
2022	Arcadia	16.73				69.33	9.92		4.02
2022	Laurieston					9.71	18	63.75	5.74
2022	Ravenswood Bog	62.44		35.99				1.57	

Frequency of different Gosner stages of development per site

Figure 2.3 Shows how the different frequency of Gosner stages of development varies across different sites. Sites such as Endfield Avenue and Arcadia have a scattered distribution of Gosner stages, whereas sites such as Glasgow University have a much more parametric distribution of Gosner stages across a much smaller range. This could be representative of different ecological or ecotoxicological conditions that affect the rate of development of tadpoles at different sites.

Figure 2.3: Frequency of tadpoles found at different Gosner stages of development sampled at each site.

Adult morphometrics and land use

There was no significant relationship between the nuptial pad colour and any land use type ($P > 0.05$; data not presented). However, significant relationships were found between land use type and adult male frog mass (**Table 2.6**). There was a positive relationship between percentage of urban fabric, green urban, arable land and frog mass and a negative relationship with industrial urban and pastures (**Figure 2.4**). Significant relationships were also found between land use type and nuptial pad length (**Table 2.7**) which followed the same pattern as for frog mass - positive with urban fabric, green urban and arable land and negative with industrial urban and pastures (**Figure 2.5**).

Table 2.6: GLMER results for relationships between adult male frog mass and different land use types surrounding breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.4**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Land use type	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Adult Frog Mass	Urban Fabric	-32443	6020	-5.389	7.08×10^{-8}	***
	Green Urban	-32443	6020	-5.389	7.08×10^{-8}	***
	Industrial Urban	-33858	6282	-5.389	7.08×10^{-8}	***
	Arable Land	-214436	39790	-5.389	7.08×10^{-8}	***
	Pastures	-32401	6012	-5.389	7.08×10^{-8}	***

Figure 2.4: Adult male frog mass against different percentages of land use types around each site: (A), Urban Fabric, (B) Green Urban, (C) Industrial Urban, (D) Arable Land, (E) Pastures. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Table 2.7: GLMER results for relationships between adult frog nuptial pad length and different land use types surrounding breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.5**). Significance codes are as follows: P < 0.001 ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Land use type	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Adult Frog Nuptial Pad Length	Urban Fabric	-1427	0.086	-16590	<2x10 ⁻¹⁶	***
	Green Urban	-1427	0.087	-16475	<2x10 ⁻¹⁶	***
	Industrial Urban	-1489	0.09	-16550	<2x10 ⁻¹⁶	***
	Arable Land	-9429	0.581	-16239	<2x10 ⁻¹⁶	***
	Pastures	-1425	0.086	-16578	<2x10 ⁻¹⁶	***

Figure 2.5: Adult male nuptial pad length against different percentages of land use types around each site: (A) Urban Fabric, (B) Industrial Urban, (C) Green Urban, (D) Arable Land, (E) Pastures. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Adult morphometrics and water quality

There was no significant relationship between pH and any of the adult morphometric parameters measured ($P > 0.05$). However, significant relationships were found between all other water quality parameters measured and adult frog mass (**Table 2.8**), nuptial pad length (**Table 2.9**) and nuptial pad colour (**Table 2.10**). For frog mass there was a positive relationship with salinity, temperature and conductivity and a negative relationship with TDS (**Figure 2.6**). For nuptial pad colour there was a positive relationship with salinity, conductivity and TDS and a negative relationship with temperature (**Figure 2.7**). For nuptial pad colour there was a positive relationship with temperature and TDS, and negative with conductivity and salinity (**Figure 2.8**).

Table 2.8: GLMER results for relationships between adult frog mass and different water quality parameters of breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.6**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Water Quality Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Adult Frog Mass	Salinity	3094.193	483.058	6.405	1.5×10^{-10}	***
	Temperature	-13.774	1.919	-7.177	7.14×10^{-13}	***
	Conductivity	-1.504	0.239	-6.293	3.11×10^{-10}	***
	TDS	0.567	0.089	6.359	2.03×10^{-10}	***

- Site**
- Cambridge Pond
 - Erik's Pond
 - Froggy Pond
 - Glasgow University
 - Irvine
 - Robroyston

Figure 2.6: Adult male frog mass against different water quality parameters of breeding ponds: (A) Salinity, (B) Temperature, (C) Conductivity, (D) TDS. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Table 2.9: GLMER results for relationships between adult frog nuptial pad length and different water quality parameters of breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.7**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Water Quality Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Adult Frog Nuptial Pad Length	Salinity	218.958	2.947	74.31	$<2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
	Temperature	-0.982	0.075	-13.19	$<2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
	Conductivity	-0.108	0.001	-74.45	$<2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
	TDS	0.045	0.003	13.78	$<2 \times 10^{-16}$	***

Site

- Cambridge Pond
- Erik's Pond
- Froggy Pond
- Glasgow University
- Irvine
- Robroyston

Figure 2.7: Adult male frog nuptial pad length against different water quality parameters of breeding ponds: (A) Salinity, (B) Temperature, (C) Conductivity, (D) TDS. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Table 2.10: GLMER results for relationships between adult frog nuptial pad colour and different water quality parameters of breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.8**). Significance codes are as follows: P < 0.001 ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Water Quality Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Adult Frog Nuptial Pad Colour	Salinity	-6248.83	232.031	-26.931	$<2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
	Temperature	37.32	7.869	4.743	2.11×10^{-6}	***
	Conductivity	3.044	0.119	25.607	$<2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
	TDS	-1.384	0.335	-4.136	3.53×10^{-5}	***

Figure 2.8: Adult male frog nuptial pad colour against different water quality parameters of breeding ponds: (A) Salinity, (B) Temperature, (C) Conductivity, (D) TDS. The higher the RGB value, the lighter the nuptial pad colour, and the lower the RGB value, the darker the nuptial pad colour. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Tadpole morphometrics and land use

There was no significant relationship between any land use type and tadpole total length or SVL ($P > 0.05$). However, significant relationships were found between all other water quality parameters measured and tadpole mass (**Table 2.11**) and tail length (**Table 2.12**). Tadpole mass was negatively related to percentage of urban fabric, and positively related to industrial urban and arable land (**Figure 2.9**). Tadpole tail length was positively related to green urban and arable land, and negatively related to saline wetland (**Figure 2.10**).

Table 2.11: GLMER results for relationships between tadpole mass and different land use types surrounding breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.9**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, $0.01 < P < 0.05$ **, $0.05 > P > 0.01$ *.

	Land use type	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Tadpole Mass	Urban Fabric	-0.003	0.001	-3.813	1.37×10^{-4}	***
	Industrial Urban	0.007	0.002	4.106	4.03×10^{-5}	***
	Arable Land	0.006	0.002	2.755	5.87×10^{-3}	**

Figure 2.9: Tadpole mass against different percentages of land use types around each site: (A) Urban Fabric, (B) Industrial Urban, (C) Arable Land. The black line is the line of best fit, and R2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Table 2.12: GLMER results for relationships between tadpole tail length and different land use types surrounding breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.10**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Land use type	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Tadpole Tail Length	Green Urban	0.233	0.116	2.014	4.4×10^{-2}	*
	Arable Land	0.261	0.087	2.99	2.79×10^{-3}	**
	Saline Wetlands	-0.152	0.058	-2.632	8.5×10^{-3}	**

Figure 2.10: Tadpole tail length against different percentages of land use types around each site: (A) Green Urban, (B) Arable Land, (C) Saline Wetland. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Tadpole morphometrics and water quality

There was no significant relationship between tadpole SVL or tail length and any other water quality parameter ($P > 0.05$). However, significant relationships were found between water quality and both tadpole mass (**Table 2.13**) and total length (**Table 2.14**). Tadpole mass was positively related to pH (**Figure 2.11**) and total length with salinity and conductivity (**Figure 2.12**).

Table 2.13: GLMER results for relationships between tadpole mass and different water quality parameters of breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.11**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

Tadpole Mass	Water Quality Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
	pH	0.268	0.028	9.719	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***

Figure 2.11: Tadpole mass against pH. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Table 2.14: GLMER results for relationships between tadpole total length and different water quality parameters of breeding ponds (see **Figure 2.12**). Significance codes are as follows: $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

	Water Quality Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	P value	Significance Level
Tadpole Total Length	Salinity	-260.554	67.85	-3.84	1.23×10^{-4}	***
	Conductivity	0.137	0.035	3.928	8.56×10^{-5}	***

Figure 2.12: Tadpole total length against different water quality parameters of breeding ponds: (A) Salinity, (B) Conductivity. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the GLMER output.

Discussion

The aim of this Chapter was to determine whether land use characteristics within a 0.5 mile radius, and/or water quality, of known amphibian habitats affected morphometrics of both tadpoles and adult male *R. temporaria* in the wild. Water quality was measured as part of this study because of close relationships with amphibian ecology, as well as its potential role as an indicator of polluted water bodies (Wells, 2010). The water quality parameters measured were salinity, conductivity, TDS, pH, temperature, and DO, which are all common parameters to measure when assessing water quality, and also in the context of amphibian habitats (Odum and Zippel, 2008; Omer, 2019). For example, conductivity changes have been shown within the literature to be indicative of pollution (Das *et al.*, 2006; Wu *et al.*, 2020). Changes over time to these parameters have also been shown to significantly affect tadpole growth, development, and health (Boyer and Grue, 1995; Odum and Zippel, 2008; Omer, 2019). As ponds are dynamic environments, water quality parameters will often vary through environmental processes such as pollution events, rainfall, and desiccation. There is also a lack of knowledge surrounding what constitutes a ‘healthy’ pond free from pollution, as there is no published guidance on expected water parameters found in ponds. However, based on the overall water quality found at each pond (**Table 2.4**), there does not appear to be any concerning levels of any particular water quality parameter that would indicate significant pollution outside of normal levels (Biggs and Williams, 2024). This is based off one time point, and so more consistent monitoring of each pond over time would be needed to confirm this. Published guidance on acceptable water quality parameters for ponds would be a useful addition to such analyses in future research. The land use surrounding ponds will also be a factor in determining the water quality of ponds, such as proximity to acidic peatlands or coastal areas (Hopkins *et al.*, 2016; Sønderup *et al.*, 2016). It would be expected that a higher percentage of areas surrounding a pond that are most likely to result in endocrine disruptors or other contaminants ending up in the environment would have significant effects on amphibian growth and development. For amphibians, this would likely be increased levels of urban areas (equating to ‘continuous/discontinuous urban fabric’, ‘green urban’, and ‘industrial urban’ in this study) and agricultural areas (‘arable land’, ‘pastures’, and ‘agricultural land with natural vegetation’) (see **Table 2.2**). This would be particularly expected in more transitional habitats where human activities meet more natural

areas, such as golf courses and urban parks (categorised as ‘green urban’), and agricultural areas where amphibian ponds occur.

From the adult frog morphometrics measured, adult frog mass and nuptial pad length were affected by some land use types, but there was no relationship with nuptial pad colour and percentage of any land use type. Mass (**Figure 2.4**) and nuptial pad length (**Figure 2.5**) were both positively correlated with ‘urban fabric’, ‘green urban’, and ‘arable land’, and negatively correlated with ‘industrial urban’ and ‘pastures’. Adult frog mass is under androgenic control, and is an important factor in male-male combat for mates in *Rana temporaria* (a lekking species), and so differences in mass in areas of high urban activity or agricultural land could be indicative that these areas could be contaminated with androgenic pollution (Burger and Nel, 2008; Jackson and Sutton, 2008; Orton, Baynes, *et al.*, 2014; Dabrowski, 2015; You *et al.*, 2015; Dittrich *et al.*, 2018; Dittrich, 2020). Nuptial pads and their characteristics are also formed and maintained under androgenic control; nuptial pad size and colour are a crucial factor in male breeding success, and so negative changes to their morphology are also expected with an increased level of agricultural and urban areas that could release endocrine disruptors into aquatic habitats (Wyk, Pool and Leslie, 2003; Luna, McDiarmid, and Faivovich, 2018; Orton *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, it is expected that a higher percentage of these land use types surrounding ponds would affect morphometrics of amphibians known to be impacted by EDC pollutants, although the exact manifestation of these changes (growth or shrinkage) is more unclear. Regardless, changes to amphibian size and nuptial pad morphology caused by EDC pollution could have consequences for the fecundity and fitness of breeding populations through natural selection. It is unclear what is driving differences in morphometric measurements between sites, suggesting this is due to ecological or physiological factors outside the scope of this study. There may also be issues with the data collection that are discussed below. Despite these discrepancies, it is still possible due to the differences seen across sites that androgenic or anti-androgenic endocrine disrupting activity could be responsible for the changes in adult frog mass and nuptial pad length and colour (Das *et al.*, 2006; Wu *et al.*, 2020). ‘Forests’ was the only land use type not significantly correlated with any adult morphometric parameter. This is not unexpected as thick areas of forest are not typical temperate amphibian habitat, providing too much shade through canopy cover preventing adequate homeostatic thermoregulation from the environment (Skelly, Freidenburg, and Kiesecker, 2002; Thompson and Donnelly, 2018). Amphibians need

diversity of habitats, and so can often be found at the fringes of habitats such as Forests, which would explain why this land use type is found around the study sites used in this chapter, despite being unlikely to be used by amphibians (Semlitch and Bodie, 2003).

Adult mass (**Figure 2.6**) increased with increasing salinity, water temperature, and conductivity, but decreased with increased levels of TDS. Adult nuptial pad length (**Figure 2.7**) increased with increased levels of salinity, conductivity, and TDS, but decreased with increasing water temperatures. A lighter nuptial pad colour (determined as higher RGB value) (**Figure 2.8**) was negatively correlated with salinity and conductivity, but positively with water temperatures and TDS. pH was not related to any adult morphometrics, likely because adults avoid water that is either too acidic or too alkaline (Freda and Dunson, 1986; Magee, 2019). Salinity, conductivity, and TDS are all closely related, and their frequent correlations within the GLMER outputs across both adults and tadpole morphometric data are noted. Despite adult frog mass, nuptial pad size, and nuptial pad colour all being morphometric variables that are controlled by the same processes, different water quality variables did not affect these morphometrics in the same way. For example, an increase in water temperature resulted in increased mass and a reduced nuptial pad length and colour. This is an interesting observation, as it would be expected that a larger frog would also have a larger, darker nuptial pad (Orton *et al.*, 2023). It is clear that the relationship between these morphometrics is more complex, and that there are many different influencing variables that are not fully understood. It is possible that either the adult frogs are gaining mass at the expense of developing other secondary sex characteristics, or perhaps that there is an effect of endocrine disrupting chemicals blocking the androgenic activity responsible for developing nuptial pad characteristics, as has been observed within the literature (Blackburn and Lynch, 1995; Wyk, Pool and Leslie, 2003; Orton *et al.*, 2018).

Tadpole mass (**Figure 2.9**) increased with decreased levels of ‘urban fabric’, and increased with increasing amounts of ‘industrial urban’ and ‘arable land’ surrounding ponds. Tadpole tail length (**Figure 2.10**) also increased with increased levels of ‘green urban’, and ‘arable land’, but decreased with increased areas of ‘saline wetland’. Tadpole total length and SVL were not related to any changes in land use percentages. As seen in the adult frogs, increased percentages of urban, industrial areas, and agricultural parameters are responsible for the

most changes in tadpole morphometrics, and there is an increased likelihood of EDC pollutants in these environments through road runoff or the application of pesticides. ‘Green urban’ areas as defined by the land use cover maps can include areas where *R. temporaria* breeding ponds are commonly found, such as urban parks and golf courses. These areas provide semi-suitable habitats for amphibians where they are commonly found in close proximity to anthropogenic activities that may result in endocrine disrupting pollution entering these ponds. This is also the case for habitats situated near arable land due to the increased levels of agriculture. Therefore, it is expected that higher percentages of these transitional habitat types (linking anthropogenic areas and natural areas) where pollution events in amphibian habitats are more likely to occur have resulted in changes to tadpole mass and tail length. Tadpoles have been shown to both increase and decrease in both mass and length when exposed to a wide variety of pollutants, demonstrating that although we would expect some morphological changes to occur, the exact manifestation of these changes is harder to predict in a wild setting (Bradford, Swanson and Gordon, 1992; Rice *et al.*, 1999; Johansson, Piha, Kylin and Merilä, 2006; Sharma and Patino, 2008; Huang, Duan and Ji, 2015; Bernabò *et al.*, 2016; Montalvao *et al.*, 2018; Sun *et al.*, 2018; Bernabò *et al.*, 2020; Dovick *et al.*, 2020; Herek *et al.*, 2020; de Albuquerque *et al.*, 2024).

Tadpole mass (**Figure 2.11**) increased with increased pH; total length (**Figure 2.10**) increased with increasing salinity and conductivity. SVL and tail length were not significantly related to any water quality parameters. Tadpole mass has been shown previously to increase with increasing pH in the Zhenhai brown frog (*Rana zhenhaiensis*), so this result is expected (Lu *et al.*, 2021). pH changes can be indicative of pollution, or sudden changes in land use such as peatland restoration, which could affect tadpole health or development. Reduced pH can also cause stress to the tadpole, causing early metamorphosis and rapid growth, which can have repercussions for survival and body condition post-metamorphosis (Beck and Congdon, 2000; Székely *et al.*, 2020). The heaviest tadpoles were seen at a relatively neutral pH of 7.2 (similar to that recorded in other amphibian surveys of Scottish ponds from the central belt (Bird *et al.*, 2019)), potentially as this pH was less stressful, whereas other sites measured during this study had a much lower pH. The range of pH measured in the current study was 5.65 to 7.59 across the different sites, with a median of 6.45 (**Table 2.4**). It is unclear whether these low pH values are due to natural acidification, or through anthropogenic stressors or pollution (Henriksen and Seip, 1980; Spyra, 2017). At the

same site (Froggy Pond), tadpoles were also longer, however, tadpole length appears to be driven more by salinity and conductivity rather than pH, which was not found to be significantly correlated (**Figure 2.12**). Tadpole tails have a lot of phenotypic plasticity, with tail morphology influenced by a range of environmental factors such as predator presence, pollution, and water currents (Van Buskirk and Mccollum, 2000; Kupferberg *et al.*, 2011; Kruger and Morin, 2020). Tail morphology parameters may therefore be less reliable for biomonitoring than tadpole mass which encompasses the entire tadpole and accounts for internal changes such as ossification of bone and restructuring of the internal anatomy during metamorphosis (Kemp and Hoyt, 1969; Rovira *et al.*, 1995; Brown and Cai, 2007).

High salinity can be a stressor for amphibians occurring due to road salt applications or salinisation of ponds from tidal inundation (Hopkins and Brodie Jr, 2015; Meindl *et al.*, 2020). High salinity can reduce tadpole growth rate, delay metamorphosis, and produce smaller metamorphs (Bernabò *et al.*, 2013; Hsu *et al.*, 2018; Welch *et al.*, 2019). Although a negative relationship was seen between percentage ‘saline wetland’ land use around ponds and tadpole tail length, a positive relationship was found with salinity. The salinity value measured at Froggy Pond was 0.56 psu (with the lowest site value being 0.04 psu found at both Laurieston and Endfield Avenue) (**Table 2.4**). It is of interest that the site with the highest percentage ‘saline wetland’ and ‘saline water bodies’ land use around the pond (Hunterstone with 40.67 % and 5.09 % respectively) was not the site with the highest salinity, with a relatively low salinity value of 0.09 psu. This is a site close to the coast, so a higher salinity would be expected, however there was an outflow pipe near to where tadpoles were found, including some tadpoles found inside the pipe itself. This may have provided a source of fresh water that reduced salinity at this site. It is also possible that other sources of anthropogenic salinisation such as from road salt may have inflated other sites above normal levels. Although there is substantial evidence that salt exposure is toxic to amphibians, there is very little information available regarding ‘normal’ water chemistry within ponds, making interpretation of the water quality parameters collected during this study difficult (Bernabò *et al.*, 2013; Hopkins *et al.*, 2016; Hsu *et al.*, 2018; Welch *et al.*, 2019; Biggs and Williams, 2024). More data are needed in order to compare pond chemistry between sites.

There are several issues with the data collection during this Chapter that makes interpretation of the results of this study difficult. Firstly, there were far fewer adult frog sites (6) found compared to tadpole sites (12), as adult frogs usually only congregate in breeding ponds for a few days or weeks a year, and are much harder to catch than tadpoles (Elmberg, 1990; Hartel, 2005). As such, far fewer adult frogs (89) were sampled compared to tadpoles (204). This decreases the applicability of using adult frogs as a biomonitoring tool, and suggests that monitoring of tadpoles that can be reliably found at sites over several weeks or months may be more useful. There were also significant gaps in the dataset for TDS and DO due to equipment malfunctions in the field, mostly digital callipers that failed during heavy rain, and the malfunctioning of water quality probes measuring certain parameters. For example, no water quality data could be collected from Victoria Park due to equipment failure (**Table 2.4**). These issues were rectified with backups and the use of traditional non-electronic callipers, but nevertheless the gaps in the data presented some problems with data modelling. There were also differences across the two years of data collection. Adult frog data could not be collected in 2022 due to timing issues clashing with other data collection, and unavoidable changes to the data collection meant that tadpole mass also could not be collected in 2022. These gaps in the data set likely affected the robustness of the GLMER models. In addition, the fact that salinity, conductivity, and TDS are all closely correlated could affect the model results and interpretation for these parameters (Das *et al.*, 2006). There are also differences in strength of significance seen within the GLMER outputs, and the visual representation of the data (linear models). For example, for the relationships between adult frog nuptial pad length and water quality parameters the GLMER outputs suggest a highly significant relationship, but the graphical representations show very weak positive and negative relationships (see **Table 2.9** and **Figure 2.7**). The GLMER outputs represent the statistical analysis performed on this data, whereas the linear model just provides a way to visually inspect this dataset, and so more weight should be given to the GLMER outputs.

For both tadpoles and the adult frogs, the study methodology utilised here only focuses on data from one time point for each *R. temporaria* individual, which may not be an accurate reflection of the complex interactions between the species and the environment throughout the breeding season. Tadpoles in particular will be exposed to the natal pond water from egg deposition until they leave the water. Data on different pond characteristics collected at each site are reported within this Chapter (**Tables 2.3, 2.4**), providing qualitative descriptive

information and a single measurement of water quality when the site was sampled. Therefore, no formal statistical comparison of water quality between sites could be carried out. However, these data illustrate that the pond sites selected were very variable in their hydrology and ecology. There is not enough historic data on pond characteristics and pond water quality to draw strong conclusions on the effect of these characteristics on EDC disruption, or their use as predictive tools (Biggs and Williams, 2024). Water quality changes frequently within these ponds through environmental factors such as rainfall or drought, and so a single data point per site as measured in this Chapter may not capture changes to water quality or contaminants. Therefore, studies such as Ficetola and De Bernardi, (2005) that look at wild tadpoles over time *in-situ* are likely to be more ecologically relevant. While the original intention of this Chapter was to determine androgenic and anti-androgenic activity within the natal pond water this was not possible (see **Appendix 2.4**). Therefore, while the question of whether amphibian morphology is affected by water quality could be addressed, information on other contaminants within the pond water can only be assumed based on land use type.

The Corine land use map used in this study dates back to land use at each site in 2018, and is based on one time-point. There has not been a more recent map released during the timeframe of this study for comparison, however it is unlikely that land use changed significantly in the span of six to seven years. The scale on the map (25 m) was not ideal for representing ponds suitable for amphibians, as these tend to be smaller and more ephemeral in nature. Bodies of freshwater reaching 25 m in size are likely to host fish and other large amphibian predators, as well as being too deep and cold (and potentially saline) to host most amphibian populations. This may be why freshwater wetlands and freshwater water bodies did not show up as being a significant factor for any morphometric variables, despite being typical amphibian habitat. A repeat of this GIS analysis using a map with smaller resolution would allow more amphibian-suitable water bodies to be identified and incorporated into future modelling efforts.

It is easier to interpret the effects of different water quality parameters on tadpole morphometrics, and land use surrounding ponds on adult frog morphometrics due to their different life history stages. Tadpoles are confined to aquatic environments and are unable to

escape even if the environment becomes unsuitable, whereas adult frogs are mostly terrestrial outside of the breeding season. Adults therefore have the option to leave aquatic environments when water quality is suboptimal, unlike tadpoles (Banks and Beebee, 1987; Wagner and Lötters, 2013a; Denoël *et al.*, 2018). Adults are more likely to be affected by land use, as they spend more time in the terrestrial environments and have the ability to disperse more freely. This reflects results from this Chapter, where adult parameters were affected by a wider range of land use types than tadpoles. Effects of land use type could be indicative of chemical pollutants but also other ecosystem factors, such as limited food sources, disease, or increased predation stress. Mass in both adult frogs and tadpoles was affected by percentage land use and water quality, and as such, was the most responsive parameter measured. Mass is an easy, non-destructive parameter to measure in amphibians, and so has the potential for use as a non-destructive biomonitoring tool in future research. Nuptial pad length was also influenced by both water quality and land use, but only applies to the males within a population. Both mass and nuptial pad length can be affected by other environmental factors such as food availability, seasonality, and disease, making interpretation of results in relation to contamination difficult. Length measurements in tadpoles (both total length and SVL) change frequently during the process of metamorphosis, whereby the tail is reabsorbed at a rapid rate. As such, this is likely not a good parameter for future studies if only measured at one time point, as in this study, and instead should be monitored over time (see **Chapter 4**).

In conclusion, the ecology and physiology of amphibians makes them especially vulnerable to the effects of endocrine disruptors, from sources such as pesticides, pharmaceuticals, road run off, and industrial waste. The sub-lethal effects of these contaminants on amphibians could have devastating effects for recruitment and overall fitness of populations. Amphibians are important predators and prey, and their decline has implications for the wider ecosystem. More long-term data on trends at sites is key to understanding the potential effects of land use and water quality/contamination on amphibian populations. Looking at the relationship between land use type/water quality and morphometrics provides preliminary data and could be refined in future research, for example using methodologies from the current Chapter in conjunction with analysis of pond contaminants. Future research could also investigate the relationships and interactions between endocrine disrupting activity in pond water, land use, water quality, and amphibian morphometrics in order to use these parameters as predictors of potential pollution of ponds with EDCs.

Chapter Three: Gonadal gene expression in wild *Rana temporaria* tadpoles

Introduction

Reproduction is fundamental to life, as it ensures the continued recruitment of subsequent generations of a species (Brannelly *et al.*, 2021). Reduced reproductive success of a species could result in localised extinctions, or in less severe cases, alterations in gene flow, and reduced genetic diversity through genetic drift (Bickham, 2011). Reproductive processes and their interrelations with the endocrine system are highly conserved amongst vertebrate taxa (Norris and Carr, 2020). As a result of this, many chemical pollutants designed to have an effect in one organism can have unintended effects on non-target organisms when pollution events occur (Hecker and Hollert, 2011). Wan *et al.*, (2025) analysed over 26,000 effect sizes from over 1,700 studies that look at the effects of insecticides, fungicides, and herbicides on non-target terrestrial and aquatic taxa, including amphibians. Their results indicate strong detrimental impacts of these pesticides on non-target organisms at environmentally-relevant exposures, and in both aquatic and terrestrial environments.

Pollution is the second most important threat impacting amphibians, and small freshwater bodies such as ponds, which are typical amphibian breeding habitat, have been shown to contain a range of chemical pollutants including EDCs, which may impact reproductive processes (Díaz *et al.*, 2019, Pinheiro *et al.*, 2021). For example, exposure to EE2, a synthetic estrogenic human contraceptive, causes a range of effects in amphibians such as altered sex ratios, altered reproductive behaviours, and complete and partial feminisation of males, in the same way that excess natural estrogen would as they utilise the same binding sites (Cevasco *et al.*, 2008, Gyllenhammar *et al.*, 2009, Hoffmann and Kloas, 2012, Tompsett *et al.*, 2013).

Exposure to endocrine disruptors can alter sexual determination and differentiation pathways in amphibians (Orton and Tyler, 2015). Sex determination is the process whereby it is determined if an individual will become male or female, however, our knowledge of the exact mechanisms of sex determination in amphibians is still quite limited (Hayes, 1998, Ruiz-García, Roco and Bullejos, 2021). In some anurans, a mixture of undifferentiated, semi-differentiated and differentiated modes of sexual development can occur within geographically distinct populations of the same species, as occurs in *R. temporaria* (Witschi, 1930). One sex-marker gene, involved in ovary development, has been identified in *X. laevis*,

and three effective sex-markers (c16, c2, and c12) have been identified in common toads (*Bufo bufo*) (Yoshimoto *et al.*, 2008; Nemesházi *et al.*, 2022). In *R. temporaria*, sex is determined through both genetic and environmental causes (see **Chapter 1**) (Norris and Lopez, 2011). Sex differentiation is the process of developing different sex characteristics that are typical of males or females, such as testes or ovaries respectively (Norris and Lopez, 2011). The resulting ratio of males to females within a population is known as the sex ratio, and the expected sex ratio varies between species (Nakamura, 2009). Deviation from the expected sex ratio for a species, if severe, could result in altered breeding dynamics and reduced recruitment for a population. Ultimately this could reduce the influence of genetic factors on sex determination, rendering populations more dependent upon the changeable environmental factors that induce sex changes (Stelkens and Wedekind, 2010, Lambert *et al.*, 2015).

It is not well understood at exactly which developmental stages sex determination and differentiation occurs in *R. temporaria*, although it is known that sex is determined by stage 43 (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2016). In *X. laevis*, the period of gonad undifferentiation is between Nieuwkoop-Faber (NF) stages 49-53, and sex determination is between NF 50-52 (Yoshimoto *et al.*, 2008, Piprek *et al.*, 2017). Both of these bands are equivalent to Gosner stages 26-30, when the hind limb bud is developing (see **Appendix 1.1**) (Simmons and Horowitz, 2006). Other studies have cited sex determination in *Xenopus* spp. between NF 51-53 (Gosner stage 26-30), and sex differentiation between NF 55-58 (Gosner stage 31-41) (Villalpando and Merchant-Larios, 1990, El Jamil *et al.*, 2008, Orton *et al.*, 2018). More data on the precise expression of genes involved in sex determination and differentiation at different developmental stages for *R. temporaria* is needed. *Amh*, or anti-müllerian hormone, is a gene involved in sexual differentiation of the male embryo (van Houten, Themmen and Visser, 2010). *Amh* is secreted by Sertoli cells of the testes, and induces regression of the Müllerian duct, which would otherwise develop into female reproductive structures (Josso *et al.*, 1993, Lee and Donahoe, 1993). The presence of higher levels of *amh* mRNA in ovaries of *X. tropicalis* than in testes at 2 weeks post-metamorphosis (before levels decline) suggests that *amh* also has a separate function in early ovarian development that is currently unknown (Jansson *et al.*, 2016). *Amh* protein products have been found at higher levels in developing testes compared to ovarian tissues in several anuran species, including *R. temporaria* (exact Gosner stage of peak expression is unclear, although stages 26-46 were used in this study)

(Piprek *et al.*, 2013). *Cyp17* is responsible for the conversion of progesterone into androstenedione, and is expressed at higher levels in testes than ovaries in the Japanese wrinkled frog (*Rana rugosa*) at Gosner stage 25 (Iwade *et al.*, 2008). Forkhead box L2 (*FoxL2*) is involved in ovarian differentiation of *R. rugosa* (possibly by regulating *cyp19* expression), and is expressed at its highest levels in the ovary at Gosner stage 25 (Oshima *et al.*, 2008). *Cyp19*, also known as cytochrome P450 aromatase, is responsible for the conversion of androgens into estrogens and is associated with feminisation of the gonads in *R. rugosa* (also at Gosner stage 25) (Nakamura, 2009, Navarro-Martín *et al.*, 2012). These genes have all been used previously in various combinations in literature on sex differentiation and determination in different amphibian species, and so were selected for use in this Chapter (Oshima *et al.*, 2008, Navarro-Martín *et al.*, 2012, Wada *et al.*, 2017, Orton *et al.*, 2018, Piprek *et al.*, 2018, Shen *et al.*, 2020).

Exposure to EDCs has the potential to disrupt sexual differentiation and/or development in anurans, and so can cause increased levels of intersex within a population. Intersex is defined as the abnormal presence of both testicular and ovarian cells found within the gonads of gonochoristic animals (species with separate sexes), and has previously been used as a biomarker of EDC exposure in wild and lab amphibian studies (Reeder *et al.*, 2005a, Orton and Routledge, 2011a, Orton *et al.*, 2014, Abdel-moneim *et al.*, 2015, Orton and Tyler, 2015). Examples of intersex characteristics include malformation of the testes, development of ovaries and testes within the same individual, non-pigmented ovaries, growth of oviducts in males, and presence of diplotenic oocytes (Hayes *et al.*, 2006, Hayes, Falso, *et al.*, 2010, Orton *et al.*, 2018). In a review of intersex occurrence in amphibians, Ranidae were found to have over 50 % of all reported cases of gonadal intersex (Abdel-moneim *et al.*, 2015).

Exposure to EDCs (such as from urban areas or pesticide exposure) can induce intersex characteristics in amphibians, both in lab studies and in the wild, and so intersex has been previously used as a biomarker of EDC exposure (Hayes *et al.*, 2002, 2006, 2010, Skelly, Bolden and Dion, 2010, Storrs-Méndez and Semlitsch, 2010, Hayes *et al.*, 2011, Abdel-moneim *et al.*, 2015, Orton and Tyler, 2015, Adolphi *et al.*, 2019, Lambert *et al.*, 2019). Smits, Skelly and Bolden (2014) report one in five male green frogs (*Rana clamitans*) from 28 suburban ponds were intersex, where 70% of ponds were thought to be contaminated with wastewater.

Biomarkers of EDC exposure in amphibians are needed in order to be able to determine the effects of EDCs in wild populations. As determining changes in sex differentiation is very difficult using external anatomy, the most frequently utilised biomarkers are destructive in nature and require euthanasia. The most common tools utilised are histological analysis, and gene expression within tissues, usually from the gonads or the thyroid. There are a few studies in anurans that have investigated the effects of EDCs on either gonad histology (Mackenzie *et al.*, 2003, Gyllenhammar, Holm, *et al.*, 2009), or gene expression (Urbatzka *et al.*, 2006, Behrends *et al.*, 2010). While several anuran studies have combined gene expression and histological endpoints to evaluate thyroid disruption in the context of growth and development (Opitz *et al.*, 2006, Zhao, Chai and Wang, 2013, Sun *et al.*, 2018), few studies have used this approach in the context of reproduction despite the role of thyroid hormones in reproductive processes (Norris, 2023). Orton *et al.* (2018) studied the effects of the anti-androgens flutamide (50 µg/L) and linuron (9 and 45 µg/L) in larval *Xenopus tropicalis* through metamorphosis. In that study, expression of different genes (*rpl8* as a housekeeping gene, *amh*, *cyp19*, *foxL2*, *cyp17*, *dmrt1*, and *ar*) as well as gonadal histology were analysed. Flutamide (50 µg/L) and the higher concentration of linuron (45 µg/L) resulted in the increased expression of *cyp17*, *foxL2*, and *amh* in metamorph (the earliest adult stages post metamorphic climax when juvenile frogs have left the water) brains, along with increased spermatogonia within the gonads, and a more feminised sex ratio. At the lower concentration of linuron, a reduction in male fertility, and demasculinisation of the sex ratios was observed. Gyllenhammar *et al.* (2009) demonstrated that larval *Xenopus tropicalis* exposed to 375 nM clotrimazole had increased gonadal *cyp19* expression, however this did not result in any histological changes. It is of note that both of these studies were lab based, and so there is a need for studies combining histology and gene expression in wild amphibians.

Biomonitoring is an important component for assessing the effects of chemicals in the field. Due to their small size, high density, and aquatic developmental stages, larval forms of amphibians are excellent models for assessing exposure effects of these chemicals. Processes related to sexual differentiation and development are highly dependent on hormonal activity and are sensitive to the effects of EDCs (Woodley, 2015). Apart from vitellogenin induction as a biomarker of estrogenic activity (see **Chapter 1**), validation of biomonitoring tools for detecting endocrine disrupting activity for reproductive modalities are lacking in amphibians

(Orton and Tyler, 2015). The aim of this Chapter was therefore to investigate the expression of gonadal genes central to sexual determination and differentiation (*amh*, *cyp19*, *foxL2*, *cyp17*) in wild common frog (*Rana temporaria*) tadpoles at varying sites across the central belt of Scotland to compare this with histological appearance of the gonads. It was originally planned to look for evidence of disruption to gene expression or gonad morphology in relation to the presence of EDCs in the pond environment. However, as it was not possible to determine EDC activity in the pond water (see **Appendix 2.4**), a secondary aim of this Chapter was to look for any relationships between gene expression, and the water quality and land use parameters found to affect tadpole morphometrics in **Chapter 2**. The gene expression work outlined in this Chapter was carried out at the University of Exeter during a research visit, and the histology work was carried out at the University of the West of Scotland.

Methodology

Sample collection

Tadpoles of *R. temporaria* were collected from a total of eight sites from across the central belt of Scotland. Full details of sample sites used can be found in **Figure 3.1** and **Table 3.1**, with qualitative site characteristics and water quality data presented in **Chapter 2**. Tadpoles were taken back to the lab, and humanely euthanised using buffered methocaine trisulphate (MS222) and pithed to ensure brain death. Sex is determined by Gosner stage 43 (**Appendix 1.1**), hence tadpoles were not collected after this stage (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2016). The Gosner stage of development (Gosner, 1960) for each tadpole was recorded, and the gonad-mesonephros complex (GMC) (hereafter referred to as the gonad) of the tadpole was removed. The frequency of Gosner stages of development sampled at sites is presented in **Chapter 2**. All equipment was cleaned with 100 % ethanol between samples to avoid cross-contamination. The tadpole gonad is present in two bipotent halves, one half on either side of the vertebral column. As the gonad of a tadpole is very small (the undifferentiated gonad is approximately 165 μM in the bicoloured frog (*Rana curtipes*) at Gosner stage 25, (Gramapurohit, Shanbhag and Saidapur, 2000)) the gonads were extracted through dividing the entire vertebral column in half. This involved the collection of other structures such as

skin and vertebrae, but also maximised chances that all gonadal tissues were collected and were not misplaced during the dissection process. One half of the gonad (*via* the vertebral column) was stored at -80 °C in RNAlater, and the other half in 50 % buffered formalin at room temperature to preserve the samples for later histological analysis of morphological structures. Due to changes in circumstance, histological specimens could not be collected from the 2022 dataset used in **Chapter 2**, and so only the 2021 tadpole samples utilised in **Chapter 2** with both gene expression and histology data have been used for this Chapter.

Figure 3.1: Locations of the eight sites from across the central belt of Scotland. Arcadia is shown in light blue, Victoria Park is shown in dark red, Glasgow University is shown in light red, Endfield Avenue is shown in dark blue, Craigmore is shown in green, Erik's Pond is shown in purple, Ravenswood Bog is shown in yellow, and Froggy Pond is shown in orange. Image created using Google maps.

Table 3.1: Fieldwork study sites, and the number of tadpoles sampled for gene expression and histology. Tadpoles used are the same as those from the 2021 **Chapter 2** dataset. Site locations also shown in **Figure 3.1**.

Site Name	Site Type	GPS co-ordinates	No. Tadpoles (morphometrics)
Arcadia	Rural	NS 47954 88310	23
Craigmore	Suburban garden	NS 41741 66565	20
Endfield Avenue	Urban garden	NS 55828 68695	10
Erik's Pond	Agricultural/Rural	NS 62971 51066	30
Froggy Pond	Suburban park	NT 05106 65871	20
Glasgow University	Urban park	NS 56758 66936	20
Ravenswood Bog	Suburban nature reserve	NS 74559 73765	20
Victoria Park	Urban park	NS 53782 67339	20
		Total	163

Gene expression methodology

Homogenisation optimisation

In order to extract RNA from the gonad samples, two methodologies for gonad homogenisation were explored. One method involved an electric homogeniser and pestle, and the other involved the use of steel ball homogenisation and shaking. Prior to the application of either method of homogenisation, gonad samples were defrosted at room temperature and removed from the RNAlater storage solution. 350 μ l of RLT lysis buffer was made up according to the manufacturer's instructions (in a 100:1 ratio of RLT buffer to 2-mercaptoethanol) from the Qiagen RNeasy Micro kit (product code: 74004), and added to either a 1.5 ml Eppendorf for the electric homogeniser and pestle, or a 2 ml Eppendorf for the

steel ball homogenisation. Electric homogenisation involved using an electric pestle gun (Battery-Operated Pestle Motor Mixer from Cole Parmer, product code: WZ-44468-25) which vibrated at high frequency within the Eppendorf tube in order to lyse the tissue. The pestles were shaped to fit the conical bottom of a 1.5 ml Eppendorf tube to aid in a more complete homogenisation. Steel ball homogenisation involved the addition of a sterile 5 mm steel ball (Qiagen, product code: 69989) to each 2 ml Eppendorf tube and then using a Tissue Lyser II (Qiagen, product code: 85300) to shake the tubes at high speed to lyse the tissue. The use of 2 ml Eppendorf tubes ensured that the steel ball would not become trapped in the bottom of the tube. The shaking was carried out in 30 s bursts to prevent overheating and degradation of the samples. Through visual inspection of the lysed product, it was possible to determine that the steel ball methodology produced more complete homogenisation, so this method was used for the remainder of the study samples.

RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis

Following steel ball homogenisation, a Qiagen RNeasy Micro kit (product code: 74104) was used to extract RNA from the tadpole gonads according to the manufacturer's instructions. A Qiagen RNase-Free DNase set (product code: 79254) was also used to remove any genomic DNA from samples. Total RNA yields were measured using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, model number: 2000), and ranged in concentration from 2.1-1311.1 µg/µl. RNA was then diluted to the appropriate concentration. Depending on RNA yield, samples were diluted to 50 or 100 ng/µl prior to reverse transcription. For samples with yields <50 ng/µl, all extracted RNA was reverse transcribed. The RNA was then converted to cDNA for qPCR processing using M-MLV (moloney murine leukemia virus) reverse transcriptase (Promega, product code: M1701) following the manufacturer's instructions.

Primer design

Two genes associated with feminisation (*foxL2*, *cyp19*) and two genes associated with masculinisation (*cyp17* and *amh*), along with *rpl8* as a reference gene were selected for this study (see **Table 3.2**). These genes have importance in sexual differentiation and determination pathways in the model amphibian species, *Xenopus tropicalis*, as well as other

amphibian species (Oshima *et al.*, 2008, Piprek *et al.*, 2013, Orton *et al.*, 2018). Primers were designed by comparing existing sequences of the genes of interest in different species of the Ranidae family using the Nucleotide database from NCBI, filtering for mRNA sequences, and the selected sequences aligned using Clustal Omega (Analysis Tool Web Services from the EMBL-EBI; (McWilliam *et al.*, 2013). Sequences determined to be adequately aligned were uploaded to OligoArchitect for qPCR design in order to generate *R. temporaria* primers for each gene of interest. The most suitable primers were selected (based on length, GC content, and melting temperature) and put into Nucleotide blast in order to determine if any other products are likely to bind to these primers, especially other *R. temporaria* genes.

Table 3.2: Details of the function of each gene selected for this study. Masculinising genes are denoted ‘Male’, and feminising genes ‘Female’.

Gene selected	Other names	Gene function	Gene expression	References
<i>rp18</i>	Ribosomal protein L8	Housekeeping, or reference gene – catalyses protein synthesis	Expressed in both males and females	(Filby and Tyler, 2007, Orton <i>et al.</i> , 2018, NCBI, 2023)
<i>amh</i>	Anti-Mullerian hormone or Müllerian inhibiting substance	Sexual differentiation of the male embryo. Binding of AMH protein to receptor induces apoptosis of the Müllerian duct cells, which would have been the precursor to the female reproductive organs	Male	(van Houten, Themmen and Visser, 2010, Orton <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>cyp17</i>	cytochrome 17 α -hydroxylase/17,20 lyase	Converts progestogens to androgens	Male	(Orton <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>cyp19</i>	Cytochrome P450 aromatase	Converts androgens to estrogens	Female	(Orton <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
<i>foxL2</i>	Forkhead box protein L2	Transcription factor genes involved in ovarian differentiation	Female	(Uhlenhaut and Treier, 2006, Norris and Lopez, 2011, Orton <i>et al.</i> , 2018)

Intron/exon boundaries of all primers were checked by comparing primer sequences to the genome of *R. temporaria* using the Genome Data Viewer on the NCBI website to see if the primer positions fell between the coding regions (exons) of the genome. The final primers were ordered from Eurofins Genomics (see **Table 4.3**). Primers were rehydrated in RNase free water to 100 pmol/ μ l and diluted to 10 pmol/ μ l working solutions before use.

Table 3.3: Details of the final primers used for each gene

Gene	Sense/Antisense primer	Primer Sequence (5' – 3')	Primer length (bp)	Optimum melting temperature (°C)
<i>rpl8</i>	F1	GTGGACGTATTGATAAGC	18	51.4
	R1	GTTCTACAGGATTCATAGC	19	52.4
<i>amh</i>	F1	CATCTTCTTCTATTCATCTTCCT	23	55.3
	R1	GATTCAACCAGCCATTCC	18	53.7
<i>cyp17</i>	F1	GTGCTTCAACACCAGATA	19	51.4
	R1	CCACTGTATCCACTATGC	18	53.7
<i>cyp19</i>	F1	CGATGGCTATTATGTGAAG	18	52.4
	R1	AAATGGCTGAAAGTAACG	18	49.1
<i>foxL2</i>	F1	CTGTCTGCCATCTACCAAT	19	54.5
	R1	GTTGTGCCTTATACTGTTCTG	21	55.9

qPCR optimisation

Quantification of gene expression was carried out using real time quantitative PCR (qPCR) and SYBRGreen chemistry. The optimal primer product temperature was determined using a temperature gradient, and the assay specificity and efficiency were determined using a standard curve. Melt curves were also produced to check for the amplification of a single PCR product. Primers were optimised using cDNA from the top 10 tadpole samples across all sites with the highest cDNA quantities. For the optimisation of *cyp19* samples were pooled in order to look for more ‘masculine’ and more ‘feminine’ individuals based on grouped differences in expression in the other genes. The individuals determined to be more ‘feminine’ based on higher *foxL2* expression and lower *cyp17* and *amh* expression were used for standard curve optimisation of this gene.

Sample sorting and gene amplification

The tadpole gonad cDNA samples (163) were divided randomly into groups of 30 (to accommodate samples in triplicate with controls on a 96 well plate), and amplified using qPCR with each primer pair. The average Ct (cycle threshold) was recorded. Samples were all run in triplicate, and as part of the data clean-up process, any sample gene amplification where only one of the triplicates amplified was discarded. Any samples with anomalies (where average cq values were deemed to be abnormally high or low, or where there was no amplification) were discarded (*rpl8*: 3, *amh*: 41, *cyp17*: 49, *foxl2*: 26, *cyp19*: 141).

Amplification efficiencies for each gene can be found in **Table 3.4**. To calculate the relative expression of each gene for each sample, the Pfaffl method was used as opposed to the traditional 2-delta delta cq method, because of a greater than 5% difference in amplification efficiency between primers (Pfaffl, 2004, see **Table 3.4**). The calculated relative gene expression results were reviewed, and anomalies (where average cq values were deemed to be abnormally high or low compared to other samples from that site) were removed (eight samples removed, leaving 155 samples in total).

Table 3.4: qPCR optimisation results following standard curve creation for each gene.

Gene	Final qPCR temperature	R ² value	Amplification efficiency (%)	Samples that amplified successfully (%)
<i>rpl8</i>	56.5	0.994	105.4	98.5
<i>amh</i>	56	0.974	107.6	92
<i>cyp17</i>	56	0.972	119.9	91
<i>foxL2</i>	55.5	0.98	112.1	96
<i>cyp19</i>	56	0.8	119.2	70

Final average relative expression of each gene for each sample was calculated relative to the control housekeeping gene (*rpl8*) using the following equations:

$$X = (\% \text{ amplification efficiency for target gene} / 100) + 1$$

$$Y = \text{Power}(X, \text{average Ct for each sample})$$

$$\text{Final average gene expression per sample} = \text{Relative } rpl8 \text{ gene expression for the sample} / Y$$

Histology

The methodology for histology is outlined in **Appendix 3.1**. Gonads were embedded, sectioned and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin-Y. Hematoxylin stains acidic structures within the cell such as the nucleus, ribosomes, and the endoplasmic reticulum, and Eosin-Y stains alkaline structures such as cytoplasm and cell walls (Fischer *et al.*, 2008). Slides were analysed visually at 400x magnification using an Optika B-159 Binocular LED Microscope (product code: B8R05564). Gonad morphology was determined using gross morphological structures, and not cell types, as there was not enough clarity in the histology at higher magnifications due to issues with staining. Each individual tadpole was categorised based on its gonad histology as ‘undifferentiated’, ‘female’, ‘male’, or ‘intersex’. Several published sources on anuran gonad histology were used as reference images for comparison in order to

aid identification of the key structures, including the presence of testicular oocytes (Hayes *et al.*, 2002, Crabtree, Smith and Carr, 2003, Mackenzie *et al.*, 2003, Coady *et al.*, 2004, Murphy *et al.*, 2006, Orton, Carr and Handy, 2006, Orton, 2008, Gyllenhammar *et al.*, 2009, Wolf *et al.*, 2010, Griffing, 2017, Liu *et al.*, 2017, Orton *et al.*, 2018, 2020, Brannelly *et al.*, 2021).

An undifferentiated gonad appears as an organ that has not started development to express either masculine or feminine morphology (Gramapurohit, Shanbhag and Saidapur, 2000b, Ogielska, 2009). A female gonad is comparatively bigger than a male gonad, and has begun to express feminine characteristics; the presence of an opening within the gonad that develops into the ovarian cavity (Murphy *et al.*, 2006, Orton, 2008, Haczkiwicz and Ogielska, 2013). A male gonad is comparatively smaller than a female gonad, and has begun to develop into a teste (Orton, 2008, Haczkiwicz and Ogielska, 2013, Alkaya and Şereflişan, 2021, Sánchez-Ferreira, Rincón-Barón and Rueda-Solano, 2021). Intersex individuals would have been identified as male testes with the presence of at least one oocyte within the tissue, but none were identified within this dataset and have therefore not been considered in the statistical analysis of this Chapter (Mackenzie *et al.*, 2003, Storrs-Méndez and Semlitsch, 2010, Griffing, 2017). Out of 147 samples analysed, 12 did not have identifiable gonad tissue, likely due to the very small gonad being misplaced during the dissection process (see **Table 3.5**). Tadpole individuals were coded, and analysed blind and in a random order to avoid any observer bias between sites.

Table 3.5: Summary of outcomes from histological analysis of tadpole gonad samples across all sites, compared to final numbers used in analysis with complete gene expression data

Category	Number of samples	Number of samples with complete gene expression data
Female	53	47
Male	52	45
Undifferentiated	30	22
Intersex	0	0
Could not be identified	12	-
Total samples	147	114
Total that could be Identified	135	-

Overview of statistical analysis

A two-way MANCOVA was performed to determine whether levels of gene expression (*amh* and *cyp17* (masculinising genes) and *foxL2* and *cyp19* (feminising genes)) differed with gonad morphology of the associated tadpole gonad (i.e. male, female, and undifferentiated). The developmental (Gosner) stage of the tadpole was included as a covariate, and site was included as a random effect. The data were visually explored to ensure they met assumptions of linearity and homogeneity of regression and residuals. Levene's test for homogeneity of variances was run to test for homogeneity between all of the variance-covariance matrices (i.e. all variables that are included within the MANCOVA). The data were also plotted to visualise how relative gene expression changed with Gosner stage within the different gonad morphological categories, but due to a lack of concrete data within the literature to compare this to, this was not formally analysed.

To determine any differences in gene expression of the associated tadpole gonad between sites, a one-way ANCOVA was then performed for each gene. The developmental (Gosner) stage of the tadpole was again included as a covariate. The data were again explored to ensure all assumptions of linearity and homogeneity of regression and residuals were met. Given that the distribution of gonad morphological categories at each site would be affected greatly by developmental stage which is not well understood in this species, and the predicted sex ratio of wild *R. temporaria* tadpoles is also unknown, the occurrence of different gonad morphological categories per site was represented graphically to provide baseline data for future studies, but not analysed further.

As *amh* was found to vary between sites, the data were then further explored to see whether there were correlations between *amh* expression and land use characteristics (land use percentages and water quality data) collected in **Chapter 2**. The land use types ‘Urban Fabric’, ‘Green Urban’, ‘Industrial Urban’, and ‘Pastures’ were selected for this analysis, as these land use types were commonly found at sites utilised in this Chapter, including at the only two sites where a significant difference in *amh* expression was seen. These land use types in particular, have a high likelihood of chemical pollutants that may be able to enter natal breeding ponds. For definitions of each land use type, see **Table 2.2** in **Chapter 2**. Salinity, conductivity, and pH were the only water quality parameters that affected tadpole morphometrics in **Chapter 2**, and therefore are the water quality variables considered here. With the data meeting all required assumptions, simple linear regressions were run to investigate any correlations between *amh* expression, land use (‘Urban Fabric’, ‘Green Urban’, ‘Industrial Urban’, ‘Pastures’), and water quality (‘Salinity’, ‘Conductivity’, and ‘pH’). A simple linear regression was used rather than the more complex GLMMs used in **Chapter 2**, as only significant variables from **Chapter 2** are being considered.

Results

Effect of gonadal morphology on gene expression

Figure 3.2 shows a higher expression of the masculinising genes *amh* and *cyp19* in male identified gonads, and higher expression of the feminising gene *foxL2* in female identified gonads. Expression of the other feminising gene (*cyp17*) was found to be far more variable, with low levels identified in all three groups, but the highest levels being found in male identified gonads. This gene may be a less reliable biomarker than the other genes used in this study. The undifferentiated gonad shows equally high levels of *cyp19* and *foxL2*, possibly suggesting a mix of designated male and female individuals where the gonad has not yet differentiated, but genes are still being expressed.

Levene's test for homogeneity of variances revealed a weak correlation between tadpole developmental stage between individuals for a given site ($F_{7,43} = 3.32$, $P = 7.79 \times 10^{-1}$), however this is to be expected as tadpoles collected from each site are expected to be roughly at the same developmental stage. The two-way MANCOVA revealed no significant difference in gene expression ($F_{8,212} = 1.677$, $P = 0.106$; Pillai's trace test statistic (V) = 0.119; see **Figure 3.5**) or relationship between developmental stage ($F_{8,212} = 0.822$, $P = 0.584$; $V = 0.06$) and sex (as determined by histology). How relative gene expression changed with Gosner stage within the different histological categories was explored visually (see **Figure 3.6**).

Figure 3.2: Relative expression of the masculinising genes (*amh* shown in blue, *cyp17* shown in green), the feminising genes (*foxL2* shown in red, and *cyp19* shown in yellow) against the three gonadal morphologies identified: female, male, and undifferentiated. Error bars show standard error. Female: $n=47$; Male: $n=45$; Undifferentiated: $n=22$.

Changes in gene expression with developmental stage

When looking at gene expression per Gosner stage of development (**Figure 3.3**), there is a clear cluster of individuals ranging from Gosner stages 33-35. This may be due to increased expression during these stages of development, or may be a by-product of sampling tadpoles at only one time point where this developmental stage was the most common stage sampled. For *amh*, *cyp17*, and *foxL2*, there is variable expression in male and female individuals across stages, but for *cyp19*, there is a very narrow band of expression. This is likely due to unoptimized primer action for this gene. Undifferentiated gonads show much more variable expression of all genes, which is expected if both male and female designated individuals who have not developed yet are within the same group.

A: *amh*

B: *cyp17*

C: *foxL2*

D: *cyp19*

Figure 3.3: Graphs showing relative expression of the masculinising genes (A: *amh* and B: *cyp17*), the feminising genes (C: *foxL2*, and D: *cyp19*) for the three gonadal morphologies identified: female, male, and undifferentiated against developmental (Gosner) stage of the tadpole.

Changes in gene expression between sites

There was a significant difference in *amh* expression between sites, but not for any other genes (see **Table 3.6**, **Figure 3.4**). A post-hoc Tukey test identified that this difference was driven by differences in *amh* expression between Erik's Pond and Glasgow University (P=0.031), but no other sites. The total number of tadpoles in each gonadal morphological category found at each site are presented in **Figure 3.5**.

Table 3.6: Results from one-way ANCOVAs of differences in relative gene expression between sites for each gene, as well as the result of the covariate (developmental stage). Significance codes are as follows: P < 0.001 ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

Gene	Factor	Degrees of Freedom	F value	P value	Significance Code
<i>amh</i>	Site	7, 105	2.296	0.032	*
	Developmental stage	1,105	2.701	0.103	NS
<i>cyp19</i>	Site	7, 105	0.54	0.802	NS
	Developmental stage	1,105	2.255	0.136	NS
<i>foxL2</i>	Site	7, 105	1.005	0.432	NS
	Developmental stage	1,105	1.111	0.294	NS
<i>cyp17</i>	Site	7, 105	1.126	0.352	NS
	Developmental stage	1,105	1.001	0.973	NS

Figures 3.4 and 3.5 show variable expression of genes and numbers of individuals identified as Female, Male, and Undifferentiated between different sites used in this Chapter. Endfield Avenue, for example, shows very low levels of gene expression of all genes, whereas Glasgow University shows very high levels of genes, especially *amh* (although with high expression variability, as shown by error bars). Endfield Avenue also has lower numbers of individuals that were able to be categorised as either Male, Female, or Undifferentiated.

Figure 3.4: Average relative expression of the masculinising genes (*amh* shown in blue, *cyp17* shown in green), the feminising genes (*foxL2* shown in red, and *cyp19* shown in yellow) at each site. Error bars show standard error. *N* numbers as follows: Arcadia (18), Craigmore (11), Endfield Avenue (6), Erik's Pond (20), Froggy Pond (20), Glasgow University (14), Ravenswood Bog (11), Victoria Park (14).

Figure 3.5: Number of individuals identified as female (shown in blue), male (shown in orange), and undifferentiated (shown in green) at each site.

Sex ratio of tadpoles

Table 3.7 shows variable sex ratios identified at different sites sampled during this Chapter. There is very little literature on tadpole sex ratios with which to compare these figures, but sex ratio appears to vary from 0.6:1 to 2:1 females to males.

Table 3.7: Table showing the recorded sex ratio of male and female tadpoles that have been identified through histology from each site.

Site	Female	Male	Sex Ratio
Arcadia	8	4	2:1
Craigmore	4	5	0.8:1
Endfield Avenue	3	2	1.5:1
Erik's Pond	6	8	0.6:1
Froggy Pond	10	6	1.7:1
Glasgow University	5	8	0.6:1
Ravenswood Bog	8	4	2:1
Victoria Park	5	8	0.6:1

Effect of land use type and water quality on *amh* expression

There was only a significant positive relationship between *amh* expression and ‘Urban Fabric’ land use percentage, but no other land use type or water quality parameter (**Table 3.8, Figures 3.6 and 3.7**).

Table 3.8: Results from linear regression of *amh* expression between land use and water quality parameters collected in **Chapter 2**. Significance codes are as follows: P < 0.001 ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

Category	Variable	Linear regression against <i>amh</i> levels		Significance code
		t Value	P Value	
Land Use Type	Urban Fabric	2.127	0.036	*
	Green Urban	0.356	0.722	NS
	Industrial Urban	-0.386	0.7	NS
	Pastures	-0.919	0.36	NS
Water Quality Parameter	Salinity	-0.711	0.479	NS
	Conductivity	-0.949	0.345	NS
	pH	-0.711	0.479	NS

Figure 3.6: Relative *amh* expression from tadpole gonads against different percentages of land use types around each site: (A), 'Urban Fabric', (B) 'Green Urban', (C) 'Industrial Urban', and (D), 'Pastures'. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the linear regression output.

Figure 3.7: Relative *amh* expression from tadpole gonads against different water quality parameters at each site: (A), Salinity, (B) Conductivity, (C) pH. The black line is the line of best fit, and R^2 values and line equations are displayed on each graph. P value represents the linear regression output.

Discussion

The aim of this Chapter was to assess the relationship between site characteristics (i.e. land use, water quality) and the expression of genes involved in sexual determination and differentiation of tadpoles. There was no significant difference in relative expression of any of the four genes measured (*amh*, *cyp17* (the two masculinising gene); *foxL2*, *cyp19* (the two feminising genes)) when compared with different the gonad morphologies identified (**Figure 3.2**). There were no confounding issues with primer optimisation for any gene except *cyp19*, which had a lower success rate than the other genes tested. Due to time constraints, the *cyp19* gene was optimised as much as possible within the given research visit time, but ultimately this particular primer amplified this gene in fewer individuals (70% success) compared to the other genes (91-98.5% success) (see **Table 3.4**). This may have affected the results obtained for *cyp19* when compared to the gonad morphology, as this primer is likely to have been less effective at binding to the cDNA of the samples compared to the other genes.

The gene expression in each tadpole according to Gosner stage of development and gonad morphology can be found in **Figure 3.3**. Stages 27-43 were collected, with all genes being expressed in the majority of individuals between Gosner stages 32-36. During these developmental stages, the hind limb of the tadpole undergoes digit differentiation from the foot paddle (see **Appendix 1.1**). In *X. laevis*, the period of gonad undifferentiation is between Nieuwkoop-Faber (NF) stages 49-53, and sex determination is between NF 50-52 (Yoshimoto *et al.*, 2008, Piprek *et al.*, 2017). Both of these bands are equivalent to Gosner stages 26-30 (Simmons and Horowitz, 2006). Other studies have cited sex determination in *Xenopus* spp. as being between NF 51-53 (Gosner stage 26-30), and sex differentiation as being between NF 55-58 (Gosner stage 31-41) (Villalpando and Merchant-Larios, 1990, El Jamil *et al.*, 2008, Orton *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the expression of the sex differentiation genes used in this study are expressed at roughly the same developmental stages as *Xenopus* species cited within the literature. More data from laboratory studies on the precise expression of genes involved in sex determination and differentiation at different developmental stages for *R. temporaria* is needed. This could not be achieved during this study due to disproportionate *n* numbers of tadpoles at each developmental stage, and the

additional confounding factors that may affect gene expression when collecting tadpoles from the wild.

Although male and female gonad morphologies were identified during the histological analysis, as well as some individuals with undifferentiated gonads, no evidence of intersex was found. This is perhaps surprising, as there is evidence that intersex is naturally found in the early stages of development (tadpoles and early metamorphosis), especially in Ranid species which employ undifferentiated forms of sexual development whereby all individuals develop ovarian structures, and then genetic males will later develop testicular tissue (Abdelmoneim *et al.*, 2015; Orton and Tyler, 2015). However, this could have been due to the quality of the histological staining, and so less focus is given within this discussion to the interpretation of these results. There is a lack of data to suggest how common intersex is in wild tadpoles, which makes interpretation of this finding difficult. Intersex has previously been observed in *R. temporaria* (Witschi, 1929). Several factors, both natural (population, age, species) and anthropogenic (EDCs), are associated with the occurrence of intersex, which makes interpretation of intersex as a biomarker very difficult (Orton and Tyler, 2015). It has also been demonstrated that tadpole age has an effect on incidence of intersex, with the highest incidence occurring in tadpoles, and a lower incidence in new metamorphs (80 days post-metamorphosis) (Storrs-Méndez and Semlitsch, 2010). As a result, intersex is less expected in adult anurans, and so has higher potential as a biomarker for EDC exposure (Orton and Tyler, 2015).

There is also a significant lack of evidence to suggest that fertility declines with intersex, so it is unclear if the presence of intersex individuals within a population has wider implications for population fecundity or sex ratios (Orton and Tyler, 2015). A study in wild roach (*Rutilus rutilus*) has shown that most intersex fish are able to breed, although with varying degrees of success, with reproductive performance negatively correlated with the severity of the intersex condition (Harris *et al.*, 2011). Crew (1921) reports an individual *R. temporaria* with ‘ovotestes’ having reproduced with a female, and producing offspring. Interestingly, all of the offspring were female, meaning that the individual frog with ‘ovotestes’ had to also be a female. There have been several papers discussing sex and phenotypes of wild adult common frogs and interactions with temperature, geographic variation, and genetics, and it is clear that

it is incredibly complex (Crew, 1921, Witschi, 1929, Alho, 2010, Alho, Matsuba and Merilä, 2010, Rodrigues *et al.*, 2016). For future research into this area, it is important to have a large, robust data set and a better understanding of ‘normal’ common frog biology. More evidence is needed on levels of natural intersex within amphibian populations, so that inflated levels due to anthropogenic EDC exposure can be identified, and more data on the wider implications of intersex for individual fertility are needed. Out of 135 tadpoles that could be categorised according to gonadal morphology from this study, none were determined to show signs of intersex (**Table 3.5**). This is in comparison to 20 %, and 13 % in green frogs (*Rana clamitans*) observed in Skelly, Bolden and Dion (2010), and Smits, Skelly and Bolden (2014) respectively, and 11 % observed in cricket frogs (*Acris crepitans*) by Reeder *et al.*, (2005). Within the context of the wider literature, it is unlikely that low levels of intersex are of particular concern for populations.

The data range collected as part of this study provides a first insight into the developmental stages involved in *R. temporaria* sex differentiation for these genes in the wild. In addition, data on the sex ratio of male to female tadpoles from each site has been reported (see **Table 3.7**). Sex ratio is often reported in adult frogs and is less commonly calculated in tadpoles. Alho, Matsuba and Merilä (2010) report a sex ratio in wild *R. temporaria* adults from Finland as being mostly equal (1:1), but with some all-female clutches or clutches which produced a strong female bias. Schmeller and Merilä (2007) report a sex ratio of wild adult *R. temporaria* (also from Finland) of approximately 3:1 females to males. Gibbons and McCarthy (1984) report 57 % of 1560 common frogs collected from Ireland being male, which extrapolates to a sex ratio of 1:1.3 females to males. The tadpole sex ratios identified in this study vary between 0.6:1 and 2:1 females to males at different sites. Pettersson and Berg (2007) demonstrated that exposure to 0.007 nM EE2 at metamorphosis (Gosner stage 46) resulted in approximately 60 % females, 25 % intersex, and 15 % males, and exposure at a higher concentration (0.9 nM) produced a female biased sex ratio of 90 % females, 5 % intersex, and 5 % undifferentiated. This is in comparison to the control group that consisted of 75 % females, 5 % intersex, and 20 % male. This demonstrates the effects that some endocrine disruptors can have in altering the sex ratios of populations. However, as natural variability of expected sex ratio of wild *R. temporaria* as seen in the literature, makes interpretation of the results from this study challenging.

A one-way ANCOVA was also carried out to determine if there were differences in relative gene expression, between the eight sites (**Table 3.8, Figure 3.4**). The only gene found to differ between sites was *amh*. Post-hoc analysis revealed a difference in *amh* expression between Glasgow University and Erik's Pond (**Figure 3.4**). In order to investigate other environmental factors that could affect gene expression profiles between sites, further analysis into potential effects of land-use type were carried out. The main land use types seen at sites used in this Chapter were selected for further investigation and a positive correlation between *amh* expression and levels of 'Urban Fabric' was found. Glasgow University was one of the two joint sites with the second highest levels of 'Urban Fabric' land use. There could potentially be EDC pollutants present at this site from close proximity to urbanisation, contributing to high *amh* expression at this site. Further investigation of the water quality profile of this site, and others, over time could provide further insight. Despite salinity, conductivity, and pH affecting tadpole mass and total length in **Chapter 2**, there were no effects on *amh* expression. There could possibly be endocrine disrupting activity present at sites that interacts with the thyroid (HPT) axis that controls metamorphic development rather than the reproductive (HPG) axis, leading to different effects in the same tadpoles. Overall, the sites sampled in this thesis may not be significantly polluted with enough endocrine disrupting chemical pollutants to induce changes in gene expression or morphology of the tadpole gonads.

This Chapter aimed to assess the interrelationships between the expression of genes involved in sexual determination and differentiation of tadpoles, and gonadal morphology of wild *R. temporaria* tadpoles. It was intended that the androgenic/anti-androgenic potential of the pond water samples collected during **Chapter 2** and processed using the luminescent cell-based assay would be incorporated into this Chapter to provide a better understanding of which ponds are 'reference' ponds, and which ponds are polluted and are likely to impact the sex determination of these tadpoles. Unfortunately, the assay could not be optimised within the timescale of this Ph.D. and so this information is unavailable; whether these tadpoles were exposed to EDCs is unclear. The fact that there was little significant difference in gonad morphology or gene expression between sites would suggest that none of the sites chosen are significantly polluted with EDCs. Further studies that sample both gonad morphology and gonad gene expression in wild tadpoles should incorporate other such ecological factors into their analyses in order to better interpret results. Further research seeking to replicate the

work of this chapter should ensure that the resulting histological analysis is robust enough to be analysed and interpreted.

The destructive methods utilised in this Chapter required the euthanasia of tadpoles in order to collect data, and so as much data as possible should be gathered from the samples collected. Time and financial constraints prevented further analysis of these samples, but future work could consider additional use of the samples, such as histological analysis of the brain and thyroid and relative gene expression in these tissues, or plasma hormone analysis from blood samples (Orton and Routledge, 2011b, Orton *et al.*, 2014, 2018). Destructive methods only allow analysis of data from one time point, which does not allow for longer term ecological monitoring which is important for obtaining an understanding of long term trends within the environment. This study provides preliminary data lacking within the body of literature on *R. temporaria*: the developmental stages of expression of *amh*, *cyp17*, *foxL2*, and *cyp19*, as well as the sex ratio of tadpoles collected from the wild. This study also provides a framework for carrying out both gene expression and histological analysis of gonad morphology on wild collected tadpoles, which has not been previously reported within the literature.

Chapter four: Use of non-destructive biomarkers to assess the impacts of water chemistry and water quality on growth and development of wild *Rana temporaria* tadpoles

Introduction

Amphibians are the most endangered group of vertebrates, with over 40% of species threatened with extinction (Stuart *et al.*, 2005; Luedtke *et al.*, 2023). Chemical pollution is a significant factor in their decline (Bongaarts, 2019; Luedtke *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, biomonitoring for the assessment of the effects of chemical pollution on amphibians presents a useful tool to delineate potential causes of decline. There are many biomarkers used throughout the amphibian ecotoxicology literature with a large body of research dedicated to the development and validation of these techniques (Venturino *et al.*, 2003; Venturino and Pechen de D'Angelo, 2005). Amphibian biomarkers for chemical pollutant exposure, such as looking at changes in morphology through histology or gene expression (as used in **Chapter 3**), are often destructive in nature and are the main type of biomarkers that have been used historically (Orton and Tyler, 2015). However, biomarkers that are non-destructive (do not cause harm or require sacrifice of the organism to collect data) have been utilised less (Orton, Baynes, *et al.*, 2014). As amphibians are already seriously threatened, there is a need for validation of non-destructive biomarkers that can be used in the field to determine the *in-situ* effects of chemical pollutant exposure.

Development of biomarkers usually occurs through laboratory studies, which often focus on controlled exposures of single compounds at different concentrations, or a small number of compounds in mixtures (e.g. Hayes *et al.*, 2006, 2010, Herek *et al.*, 2020). However, chemical pollutants are always present as complex mixtures in the environment, therefore, aquatic organisms are subject to chemical pollutant mixtures (Jin, Gaus, and Escher, 2015). Therefore, the ability to examine species-specific *in situ* effects of chemical pollutants in the natural environment provides a more ecologically relevant reflection of environmental exposures, compared to effects observed in laboratory-based studies where all variables are controlled (Spurgeon *et al.*, 2010). However, analysis of *in situ* exposures can be challenging, largely due to the fact that many environmental variables cannot be controlled or accounted for within analyses, and the ability to assign causation of exposure to the effects observed requires careful interpretation of data (Chaousis, Leusch and van de Merwe, 2018).

In addition to the development of non-destructive biomarkers and their response to environmentally-relevant exposures, there is a need for more long-term studies, looking beyond a single time point, as was used in **Chapter 2**. More long term data are also needed to corroborate whether biomarkers and biomonitoring tools provide meaningful outcomes. Measurements taken at only one time point may not be fully representative of ecosystem dynamics (Müller *et al.*, 2010). In amphibians, most studies regarding chemical pollution carrying out repeated *in situ* measurements have looked at tadpoles, and have used cages to ensure that the same tadpoles are measured (Karasov *et al.*, 2005; Peltzer *et al.*, 2008; Ortiz-Santaliestra *et al.*, 2011). This may cause additional stress to the tadpoles through restriction of movement and normal behaviours. As ectotherms, tadpoles need to regulate their body temperature by moving to alternate areas within a pond that confinement in a cage can prevent. Although cages may reduce predation, the ability to see or sense small predators may still induce predation stress which could exacerbate the effects of toxicant exposure and affect growth and development of tadpoles. For example, Teplitsky *et al.* (2005) showed that the combined effects of predator stress (dragonfly larvae, *Aeshna* spp.) and a fungicide (fenpropinomorph) resulted in delayed metamorphosis and a smaller metamorph body size in *Rana temporaria*. Additionally, caging has also been shown to affect growth and development in *Xenopus laevis* tadpoles (Rose, 2014). Studies carried out without the use of caging could reduce additional stressors that could interfere with results. Therefore, studies investigating the effects of toxicant exposures would ideally use non-destructive, repeated measurements of tadpoles *in situ* without the need for cage confinement.

The effects of metal contaminants on amphibians have been well studied (Freda, 1991, Croteau *et al.*, 2008, Egea-Serrano *et al.*, 2012, Hill *et al.*, 2022, see **Table 4.1**). While metals are found naturally, metal pollution resulting from anthropogenic activities within the environment can come from several different sources (e.g. pesticide and herbicide use in agriculture, smelting and industrial runoff, mining) resulting in metal contamination of soil, air, and water bodies (Garrett, 2000; Briffa, Sinagra and Blundell, 2020). Some herbicides (such as glyphosate-based herbicides) contain metals and are often applied in agricultural areas where amphibians are found, and can run-off into amphibian habitats, such as breeding ponds (see also **Chapter 1, Table 1.1**). For example, Defarge *et al.* (2018) analysed 14 formulations of glyphosate-based herbicides, and identified arsenic, chromium, cobalt, lead, and nickel, along with petroleum-based compounds. The metals identified and measured in

their study are known to be toxic to amphibians at environmentally-relevant concentrations. They can also have endocrine disrupting properties, interfering with the hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid HPT axis in tadpoles, that controls metamorphic growth and development (Slaby *et al.*, 2019; Ruthsatz and Glosv, 2023; de Almeida and Freitas, 2024). However, not all metals are toxic; some, such as calcium and magnesium, are major ions that are essential for normal growth and physiological development (Whatley *et al.*, 2020; Rose, 2021). While these elements are not considered as pollutants, fluctuations in their concentrations still have the potential to affect amphibian physiology and are relevant components of the physiochemistry of ponds.

Table 4.1 demonstrates the complex impacts of metal exposures in amphibian tadpoles, with a wide variety of effects that encompass both endocrine disrupting pathways, and other toxic effects. While there is a mix of both laboratory and wild studies into the effects of metals on amphibians, most studies have been carried out under laboratory conditions and have considered a single element. However, there are some studies that have considered the effects of metals as mixtures, for example as constituents of waste-water effluents. Lanctôt *et al.* (2016) exposed striped marsh frog tadpoles (*Limnodynastes peronii*) to 25, 50, and 100 % coal mine wastewater from two different holding dams (Dam 1 and Dam 2). Water from Dam 1 had higher turbidity, nutrients, total and dissolved organic carbon, alkalinity, and arsenic concentrations. Water from Dam 2 had higher conductivity, salinity, TDS, hardness, and sulphate concentrations. Tadpoles exposed to water from Dam 1 experienced 5 % mortality, and showed delayed development, but this did not affect growth overall. Tadpoles exposed to water from Dam 2 experienced 40 and 50 % mortality at the 50 and 100% concentrations, respectively. There was no mortality in the control groups (consisting of aerated reconstituted water), and tadpoles from both exposed groups had significant levels of selenium, cobalt, and arsenic within their tail and liver tissues.

Table 4.1 also highlights the wide range of concentrations that have been used in metal exposure studies, ranging from µg/L to mg/L. It is unclear in many of these studies if exposure levels are based on environmentally-relevant concentrations. In particular, many tadpole morphometric variables such as mass and length are shown to be affected in different (and sometimes contrasting) ways, by many different elements across many different species.

This highlights the use of tadpole morphometrics as a potential non-destructive biomarker for metal exposure. Reviews of the lethal and sublethal effects of metals during amphibian metamorphosis can be found in Hill *et al.*, (2022) and de Almeida and Freitas (2024). For metal toxicants, it is also important to account for their bioavailability within the water body. Bioavailability is dependent upon many factors including water chemistry (e.g. pH), presence of other chemical pollutants, and available binding sites of the exposed organism (McGeer *et al.*, 2004, Adams *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, analysis of water chemistry and chemical pollutant profiles of a water body, are important factors for understanding potential effects of metals on aquatic organisms.

Table 4.1: Lethal and sublethal effects of exposures to anuran tadpoles for all elements measured within this Chapter. The LC50 (96 h) has been recorded where reported within the literature. Please note that some elements had opposite effects in different species and at different concentrations within the literature, and some metals (barium, bismuth, calcium, magnesium, strontium, and tellurium) had no appropriate exposure literature that could be found. Some of these effects are observed as co-exposures, and with differing water chemistry, but individual element effects have been reported where identified.

Periodic symbol	Metal	Range of Exposures or Bioaccumulation Identified Within Literature	Lab or Wild Study	Effects on Growth and Development	LC50 (96 h), Toxicity, and Other Effects	References
Ag	Silver	0.018 - 10 mg/L	Mostly lab with some wild samples or wild collected tadpoles	Delayed metamorphosis, reduced SVL, and increased/decreased hindlimb length	Bioaccumulation of nanoparticles, altered blood parameters, and increased stress markers	Lefcort <i>et al.</i> , 1998, Hinthner <i>et al.</i> , 2010, Heyes, Rowe and Conrad, 2014, Carew <i>et al.</i> , 2015, Murthy <i>et al.</i> , 2022, Costa Motta <i>et al.</i> , 2023
Al	Aluminium	0.1-80 mg/L	Lab, wild, and lab exposure to wild samples	Increased mass, decreased body size, reduced fertilisation of eggs, no change in SVL or mass, decreased body length and reduced gill length	LC 50 (96 h) at 1.9 mg/L. Increased mortality	Tyler-Jones, Beattie and Aston, 1989, Beattie, Aston and Milner, 1991, Bradford, Swanson and Gordon, 1992, Rowe, Sadinski and Dunson, 1992, Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Giroto <i>et al.</i> , 2020, de Albuquerque <i>et al.</i> , 2024
As	Arsenic	0.001-1 mg/L	Lab and wild	No effect on growth, or metamorphosis, delayed metamorphosis, accelerated metamorphosis, reduced size, reduced SVL, TH-dependent tail shrinkage inhibited in dose-dependent manner	Mortality at high concentrations, Glutathione S-transferase (GST) activity (a toxicity enzyme), significantly inhibited, loss of limbs, increased hepatosomatic indices, bioaccumulation	Clark <i>et al.</i> , 1998, Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2008, Davey <i>et al.</i> , 2008, Heyes, Rowe and Conrad, 2014, Singha <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Lanctôt <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Ellen Hinck <i>et al.</i> , 2017, Samanta <i>et al.</i> , 2020
B	Boron	50-100 mg/L	Lab	Increased growth rate	Reduced hatching success, and swelling of the thoracic region and altered gill morphology	Laposata and Dunson, 1998, Evariste <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Ba	Barium				None	

Be	Beryllium	0.4 µg/g dry mass bioaccumulation	Lab		Bioaccumulation	(Sparling and Lowe, 1996)
Bi	Bismuth				None	
Ca	Calcium				None	
Cd	Cadmium	0.25 µg/L - 200 mg/L	All lab with one wild sample exposure	Increased and decreased growth and development, decreased mass, increased and decreased body length, decreased percentage metamorphosis, increased body condition, reduced tail length, decreased hind limb length	LC50 of 1567.9 µg/L. Mortality at high concentrations, genotoxic effects, altered gut histopathology and reduced diversity of gut microbiota, decreased locomotor performance, higher internal water content, decreased hepatic enzymatic activity and GSH content, bioaccumulation, reduced cardiac function, impacts on skin microbiome, reduced thyroid activity, delayed bone formation	Loumbourdis, Kyriakopoulou-Sklavounou and Zachariadis, 1999, James and Little, 2003, James, Little and Semlitsch, 2005, Gross, Chen and Karasov, 2007, Sharma and Patino, 2008, Gross <i>et al.</i> , 2009, Dal-Medico <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Patar <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Hu <i>et al.</i> , 2019, Ya <i>et al.</i> , 2019, Lu <i>et al.</i> , 2021, Jiang <i>et al.</i> , 2023, Marchand <i>et al.</i> , 2024
Co	Cobalt	Unknown	Wild		Bioaccumulation in tail and liver	Lanctôt <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Cr	Chromium	0.001 - 90 mg/L	Mostly lab with some wild samples or wild collected tadpoles	Decreased growth and development, lower mass, smaller body size, smaller interocular distance, altered tail morphology	LC50 of 141.99 mg/L. Increased mortality, anaemic conditions, genotoxicity, suppressed skeletal ossification, altered thyroid morphology, changes to gut microbiome	Natale <i>et al.</i> , 2006, Heyes, Rowe and Conrad, 2014, Fernando <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Montalvao <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Samanta <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2021, Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2023
Cu	Copper	1 µg/L - 13.5 mg/L	Lab	Reduced growth and development, reduced total length and mass, increased tail length and hind limb length	LC50 of 0.03 mg/L. Increased mortality, hepatocyte degeneration in liver, reduced thyroid size, reduced avoidance behaviours, changes to gut microbiome, increased stress biomarkers, reduced swimming performance	Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2008, Barry, 2011, Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Araujo <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Chai <i>et al.</i> , 2014, 2014, Christenson <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Gaietto, Rumschlag and Boone, 2014, Zheng <i>et al.</i> , 2021, Murthy <i>et al.</i> , 2023

Fe	Iron	0.51 - 100 mg/L	All lab with one wild sample exposure	Delayed development, increased tail length, no change to SVL or mass	LC50 of 1.9 mg/L. Bioaccumulation, increased GST activity, genotoxicity, lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress, neurotoxicity through inhibition of AChE activity	Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012, da Silva Veronez <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Giroto <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Meddeb <i>et al.</i> , 2023, Murthy <i>et al.</i> , 2023
K	Potassium	0.1 - 1.5 µg/L	Lab	No effect on growth and development	Shrinkage of kidney tissue, degeneration of hepatocytes, degeneration of oocytes, altered gene expression, altered respiratory function, altered skin morphology	Lancotot <i>et al.</i> , 2013, Rissoli <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Buncharoen <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Li	Lithium	2.5 - 412.5 mg/L	Lab	No effect on mass, SVL, or hindlimb length, increased developmental rate	Decreased tadpole activity, up-regulation of thyroid gland, alterations in enzymes related to detoxification, antioxidant, and hepatic mechanisms, endocrine disruption of thyroid hormones, genotoxicity, effects on the physiology of the heart and gastrointestinal systems. alterations in glucose and lipid metabolism	Pinto- Vidal <i>et al.</i> , 2021 (a), Pinto-Vidal <i>et al.</i> , 2021 (b), Peltzer <i>et al.</i> , 2024
Mg	Magnesium				None	
Mn	Manganese	1.35 - 13.5 mg/L	Lab, wild, and lab with wild samples	Increased body length, delayed metamorphosis, no change in SVL or mass, increased body condition	LC50 of 39 mg/L. No mortality, ingestion of metals, bioaccumulation in liver and tail, genotoxicity, increased GST activity	Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012, da Silva Veronez <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Lancôt <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Giroto <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Mo	Molybdenum	Exposure of bitumen during cage study. 23.1 - 38.1 µg/L Mo bioaccumulated.	Wild		Bioaccumulation	Krohn, Palace, and Smits, 2021

Na	Sodium	250 µg/L - 125 mg/L	Lab	Delayed metamorphosis, increased/decreased SVL, and increased/decreased hindlimb length, increased mass	LC50 of 647 mg/L. Increased/decreased susceptibility to NaCl. Increased lipid peroxidation, increased GST, higher oxidative stress, altered liver morphology, thyroid gene inhibition, histological changes to the femur and tibia-fibula	Bulaeva <i>et al.</i> , 2015, Pal <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2019, Meindl <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Zheng <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Li <i>et al.</i> , 2023
Ni	Nickel	1.35 - 13.5 mg/L	Lab		LC50 of 8.8 mg/L	Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012
Pb	Lead	3 µg/L - 13.5 mg/L	Lab	Delayed metamorphosis, reduced SVL, mass, and forelimb length	LC50 of 1.5 mg/L. Mortality, spinal deformity, abnormal swimming behaviour, reduced swimming and jumping speed, bioaccumulation, no effect on sex ratio and gonadal histology, reduced learning and retention, increased buccal ventilation rates, increased time at water's surface	Rice <i>et al.</i> , 1999, Steele, Strickler-Shaw and Taylor, 1999, Berzins and Bundy, 2002, Chen, Gross and Karasov, 2006, Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Huang, Duan and Ji, 2014
Sb	Antimony	Unknown	Wild	Delayed development, reduced size at metamorphosis	Bioaccumulation	Dovick <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Se	Selenium	10 µg/L - 10 mg/L	Lab and Wild	Increased mass and SVL, increased metamorphic rate,	Reduced activity level, upregulation of thyroid, Bioaccumulation in liver and tail, alterations in glucose and lipid metabolism	Lanctôt <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Masse, Muscatello and Janz, 2016, Lanctôt <i>et al.</i> , 2017, Pinto-Vidal <i>et al.</i> , 2021(a), Pinto-Vidal <i>et al.</i> , 2021 (b), Pinto-Vidal <i>et al.</i> 2022
Sr	Strontium				None	
Ti	Titanium	0.31 - 1000 mg/L	Lab	Delayed development, decreased body length, increased mass	LC50 of 74.9 µg/L. Increased mortality, histological alterations in intestine and liver	Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Al Mahrouqi, Al Riyami and Barry, 2018, Ruvinda and Pathiratne, 2021
Tl	Tellurium				None	

V	Vanadium	10 - 160 mg/L	Lab and wild	Delayed metamorphosis	Reduced lipid storage, severe embryo malformations, bioaccumulation in toe bones	Rowe, Heyes and Hopkins, 2009, Simon <i>et al.</i> , 2017, Dahms-Verster <i>et al.</i> , 2023
Zi	Zinc	10 µg/L - 13.5 mg/L	Lab and wild	Increased/decreased body length, increased/decreased mass	LC50 of 3.61 mg/L. Genotoxic effects, bioaccumulation, lack of oral disk structures, changes in position and coiling of intestine, malformations of the chondrocranium, reduced fitness and mobility, increased stress biomarkers	Clark <i>et al.</i> , 1998, Barry, 2011, Shuhaimi-Othman <i>et al.</i> , 2012, Patar <i>et al.</i> , 2021, Costa Motta <i>et al.</i> , 2023, de Albuquerque <i>et al.</i> , 2024

As ponds are dynamic environments, water quality parameters such as pH and conductivity can vary through environmental processes such as runoff, rainfall, and desiccation. This will in turn have significant effects on the bioavailability of the metal contaminants found in these ponds and their effects on tadpoles, as well as direct effects of water quality on the tadpoles. As previously explored in **Chapter 2**, water quality parameters of natal pondwater can have a significant effect on tadpole growth and development and so are considered as additional factors in this Chapter. In this Chapter, a non-destructive method was used to assess possible relationships between concentrations of different elements, other water quality parameters and *Rana temporaria* tadpole morphometrics as a biomonitoring tool for assessing *R. temporaria* growth and development. The work in this Chapter involved repeated visits to six sites, to measure the growth and development of tadpoles *in-situ*, but individual tadpoles were not tracked over time. The study aimed to sample a high *n* number (~50) of tadpoles from each site each week to obtain average values per site, using the same methodology as Ficetola and De Bernardi (2005). Tadpole morphology was then analysed in the context of water quality and element concentrations using a PCA (principal component analysis) approach to reduce dimensionality of the water quality and element concentration data. It was hypothesised that exposure to any metals found in the pond water and known to be toxic to amphibians would affect tadpole morphometrics, and that changes in conductivity, salinity, and pH would also affect tadpole morphometrics, as seen in **Chapter 2**.

Methodology

Field sites

Six pond sites from across the central belt of Scotland were identified that had *Rana temporaria* tadpoles present (see **Figure 4.1**). There were limited sites available that contained *R. temporaria* tadpoles, and so all sites found to contain *R. temporaria* tadpoles in high enough numbers were used. Ficetola and De Bernardi, (2005) utilised an n number of 50 tadpoles for their *in situ* measurement study, and so this was the target number for this study, but only a consistent n number of 20 tadpoles per site could be found, so this is the number of tadpoles that were repeatedly measured per week. This number decreased as tadpoles reached metamorphosis and left the ponds. Preliminary consideration of land use surrounding the ponds, as well as the water chemistry, confirmed that selected sites contained a mixture of ‘cleaner’ reference sites and more ‘polluted’ ponds, with the understanding that a true clean reference site in the wild is difficult to determine (see **Table 4.2**). Sites were visited until either tadpoles metamorphosed and left the pond (i.e. reached Gosner stage 46), or until the pond dried out and therefore tadpoles could no longer be found (occurred at one of the sites: Langlands Gate).

Figure 4.1: Locations of the six sites from across the central belt of Scotland. Bishopton is shown in orange, Victoria Park is shown in red, Hogganfield Park is shown in green, Ravenswood Bog is shown in yellow, Langlands Gate is shown in purple, and Oldhall Ponds is shown in blue. Image created using Google maps.

Table 4.2: Site locations and descriptions for the six sites. Sites were visited until either tadpoles metamorphosed and left the pond (i.e. reached Gosner stage 46), or until the pond dried out and tadpoles died (Langlands Gate).

Site	Grid reference	Site description	Number of weeks visited
Bishopton	NS 42843 70679	Private urban pond	9
Hogganfield Park	NS 64252 66913	Urban park, some visible signs of pollution	8
Langlands Gate	NS 63922 51103	Nature reserve by golf course on industrial estate	2
Oldhall Ponds	NS 33815 36347	Nature reserve by industry and active construction work	4
Ravenswood Bog	NS 74868 74055	Nature reserve near areas of urbanisation	9
Victoria Park	NS 53751 67315	Urban park	4

Sampling optimisation procedure

In week 1, at the first site where measurements were taken (Bishopton), tadpoles were weighed both in a 50 mL beaker of pond water, and on a moist petri dish to determine the most accurate method. There was no significant difference in mass measurements depending on whether the tadpoles ($n=20$) were weighed in water or the petri dish (Paired t-test: $t(38)=0.115$, $p = 0.908$) and there was a significant relationship between the mass measurements from the two different methods (Linear regression: $F_{(1,18)} = 34.59$, $p < 0.0001$, $R^2 = 0.639$). Using a petri dish reduced the amount of time needed to take a mass measurement and allowed measurement of the tadpoles with callipers without transfer to another container. Therefore, this method was chosen for sampling throughout this Chapter, as it likely to be the least stressful to the tadpole due to the reduced amount of handling time required for data collection.

Sampling protocol

Each site was visited once per week, on the same day each week, and 20 tadpoles were collected using a hand net at random from each pond, and stored in a clean 37 x 22 x 25 cm faunarium (Exo Terra) with approximately 5 cm of pond water until measurement. As they are transparent, faunariums were covered with a clean towel to reduce tadpole stress and avoid overheating of the water. To measure tadpole mass, a single tadpole was removed by hand from the faunarium, and excess water removed with damp tissue. The tadpole was then transferred to a moist petri dish and body mass recorded in grams using a portable pocket scale (Royaltec digital pocket scale; range 0.01 to 200 g). The scale was used on a portable table (Hibtn 2ft Folding Camping Table) inside a 36 L plastic storage box to reduce potential impacts of ambient conditions (i.e. wind) on mass measurements. The table was placed in the same location at each site to ensure a flat surface, verified using a spirit level. The scale was calibrated before each use using a range of calibration weights (0.1 to 50 g; based on the fact that tadpole mass across all Gosner stages measured ranged from 0.12 to 0.77 g in **Chapter 2**), and the scale or table adjusted as necessary.

Total length, snout to vent length (SVL) and head width were recorded using digital callipers (BLOSTM 150 mm Digital Vernier Calliper). The Gosner stage of development was also recorded. The tadpole was then transferred to a recovery faunarium (37 x 22 x 25 cm, Exo Terra) filled with pond water and covered with a towel. Tadpoles were returned to the pond after all tadpoles had been measured, and all equipment was disinfected between sites to prevent potential disease transfer. At the time of sampling, a probe (Team 99 Water quality tester High Precision Pen Type H2 Meter with ATC Range) was used to measure water quality parameters: temperature (°C), salinity (ppm), pH, TDS (mg/L), conductivity (µS) and a dissolved oxygen analyser (Buyweek, product code: D09100) was used to record dissolved oxygen (DO) (%). The range of water quality parameters found across all weeks measured for each site, is presented in **Appendix 3.1**. Three replicate 50 mL water samples were collected from the same area of the pond where tadpoles were present at the time of sampling (or fewer replicates if water levels were low) in digestion tubes (Cole Parmer, WZ-53203-13) and filtered on site to remove solid particulates using a 0.45 µm pore syringe filter (Cole Parmer, WZ-35202-04). Filtered samples were then decanted into clean 50 mL Falcon tubes and returned to the lab where they were acidified to pH < 2 (max. 8 h after collection) using concentrated HNO₃. Samples were then stored at room temperature until analysis.

Water chemistry analysis

Samples were decanted into 10 mL transport tubes for ICP-OES analysis (Elkay labs, 127-T160-101). Concentrations of elements were determined by ICP-OES analysis (Perkin Elmer AVIO500) using a calibration series of a multi-element standard at 0, 2 and 10 mg/L (ME/1001/05; Fisher Scientific, UK; **Table 4.2**). Each water sample replicate was analysed in triplicate, and averages calculated for the same pond per week. ICP-OES conditions were as follows: rf generator: 1.15 kW; Plasma: 1.4 L/min; Auxillary: 0.5 L/min; Nebuliser: 0.8 L/min; sample flow rate 1.5 mL/min. Several wavelengths for each element were selected for analysis based on their Wohlers value, and the most suitable wavelength (free of interference) was used in calculations. ICP-OES analysis was carried out by a technician at the University of the West of Scotland.

Limit of detection (LOD) values were calculated using standard practices (see McLellan *et al.*, 2013) and a mean calculated. Values obtained for each element were compared to the LOD and if the value was below the calculated LOD, it was considered to be at a concentration below that which the ICP-OES analysis could detect. These values were counted as zero, but it did not guarantee that the true value was zero. The LOD values for each of the toxic metals within the multi-element analysis were compared to the literature and found to be far below environmentally-relevant concentrations based on existing literature, or concentrations likely to influence tadpole growth and development (see literature cited in **Table 4.3**). Therefore, any metal concentrations below the LOD were counted as zero. The range of element concentrations found across all weeks measured for each site, and how they relate to the literature, are presented in **Table 4.3**.

Table 4.3: Range of element concentrations (mg/L) found across all weeks measured for each site. Values recorded that fell below the LOD have been reported as 0. Values highlighted in bold indicate where the measured range falls within or above tadpole exposures found within the literature. Please note that for barium, calcium, magnesium, and strontium, no relevant exposure literature was found to compare these values against.

Periodic Symbol	Element	Site					
		Bishopton	Hogganfield	Langlands Gate	Oldhall Ponds	Ravenswood Bog	Victoria Park
Al	Aluminium	0.01 - 0.04	0.08 - 0.61	0 - 0.01	0.02 - 0.27	0 - 0.49	0.07 - 0.71
Bo	Boron	0 - 0.01	0 - 0.02	0 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.06	0.01 - 0.05	0 - 0.02
Ba	Barium	0	0 - 0.01	0.1 - 0.23	0.02 - 0.03	0.02 - 0.17	0 - 0.04
Ca	Calcium	19.86 - 31.72	6.45 - 10.08	90.65 - 94.71	31.44 - 34.94	24 - 101.46	13.26 - 19.52
Fe	Iron	1.13 - 5.53	4.32 - 10.9	2.05 - 7.54	2.06 - 6.41	0.1 - 2.72	2.59 - 6.3
K	Potassium	0.36 - 3.07	0.77 - 22.43	3.48 - 5.49	4.58 - 5.6	0.99 - 5.47	1.08 - 6.33
Li	Lithium	0.01 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.05	0.01 - 0.02	0.01	0.01 - 0.02	0.01 - 0.21
Mg	Magnesium	0.98 - 2.28	1.59 - 2.62	8.65 - 12.14	6.28 - 7.07	4.51 - 19.95	1.67 - 2.69
Mn	Manganese	0.01 - 1.38	0 - 0.858	5.97 - 9.27	0.05 - 0.25	0 - 4	0.18 - 0.46
Na	Sodium	0.45 - 3.28	5.08 - 10.67	8.37 - 11.91	29.89 - 31.80	5.12 - 10.96	3.06 - 5.03
St	Strontium	0.07 - 0.11	0.02 - 0.05	0.28	0.21 - 0.23	0.08 - 0.29	0.03 - 0.05
Ti	Titanium	0	0	0	0	0	0.003
Zi	Zinc	0	0	0	0	0	0.002

Statistical approach

A principal component analysis (PCA) approach was selected to analyse data in this Chapter. PCAs are used to reduce dimensionality of the data, by reducing the number of variables in a data set while still preserving the most important trend information. They can be used for dealing with data sets where collinearity is a perceived issue by taking a large number of environmental predictors measured and extracting one or more components to use in lieu of the original predictors (Vanhove, 2021). Throughout the Chapter, PCA is used to reduce the dimensionality of the metal concentrations measured within the ponds, and then a separate PCA to reduce the dimensionality of the water quality parameters measured. Principle components (PCs) are generated, which are new linear combinations of the original variables that best explain the variance within the dataset, in this case, trace metal concentrations and water quality (Greenacre *et al.*, 2022). In each PCA analysis, 10 principal components are generated, with PC1 contributing the most to the overall variation of the dataset, and subsequent PCs decreasing in their explanation of the overall variation. The number of PCs used in subsequent analyses, in the case of this Chapter to see how they influence tadpole morphometrics, will vary depending on the data set and questions asked. Usually, only a few PCs are considered in further analyses (e.g. just PC1 and PC2) as these account for a high proportion of variation (usually over 70%) within the dataset.

As discussed in **Chapter 2**, collinearity of the environmental parameters measured in this Chapter is to be expected. With collinearity, one approach can be to remove variables responsible for the least amount of variation within a dataset. However, in this Chapter, all variables have been kept in the statistical analyses, using each PC as a proxy for the pond water mixture that the tadpoles were exposed to, with the specific component loading scores for each variable interpreted as the amount of influence that variable has within the data, and subsequently on the tadpole morphometrics. This allows for a more ecologically-relevant approach than removing variables, especially when there is no *a priori* rationale for the removal of particular variables. Using PCs to test the effect of elements and water quality parameters on tadpole morphometrics was chosen as a way of representing the pond water profiles these tadpoles are exposed to in the wild. A higher (> 0.4 or < -0.4) component loading score (i.e. eigenvalue) indicates that a particular variable is responsible for more variation

within a PC. Each PC has one dimension, with the mid-point value being 0. The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. A value over 0.4 in either direction is considered to be a significant distance away from the mid-point value of 0. These values are presented in bold throughout the results. PCA analysis was firstly performed separately on the element concentrations and then on the water quality data from all sites and weeks to allow visual comparison of sites for the whole experimental period, and provide information on how element concentrations and water quality changed at *R. temporaria* breeding sites over time.

Following generation of PCs to represent elements and water quality, these were then analysed against different tadpole morphometric measurements using a generalised linear mixed-effects model (GLMER). A GLMER was used as the data are non-parametrically distributed, and include a combination of random effects (site) and fixed effects (elements and water quality). The data are also hierarchical in nature, as the tadpoles are within different sites.

An additional complexity of the data collected in this Chapter was that the tadpoles were developing over time, and going through metamorphosis which is not a linear process in terms of morphology and size. It was considered too complex to include development of the tadpoles at each site over time in one statistical model; instead, tadpoles were binned into different Gosner stage bands (see **Appendix 1.1**), in order to allow comparison between developmental stages across sites despite differences in the timings of stages between sites. Sites were all sampled within the same time frame, but spawn will have been laid at different times. This approach also accounted for inherent differences in morphology at different phases of metamorphic development, while also allowing for robust *n* numbers for statistical analysis. The tadpole Gosner stage bands selected (see **Table 4.4**) match the stages in tadpole development that are potentially subject to endocrine disruption of the thyroid axis. Most background literature on this topic is carried out on *Xenopus* as a model species, and so this process is less understood in Ranidae species such as *R. temporaria* (Yamauchi *et al.*, 2002; Sugiyama *et al.*, 2005; Helbing *et al.*, 2007; Heimeier and Shi, 2010; Carr and Patiño, 2011; Searcy *et al.*, 2012; Ziková *et al.*, 2017).

Table 4.4: Gosner stage bands that tadpoles were divided into, along with the associated stage of metamorphosis and examples of genes identified in *Xenopus* as contributing to these different stages in metamorphosis. Please note this is not an exhaustive list.

Gosner Stages	Stage of Metamorphosis	Genes expressed
25-30	Limb bud formation	Abdominal B-type Hox genes (<i>Xhoxa9</i> , <i>Xhoxd9</i> , <i>Xhoxd10</i> , <i>Xhoxa11</i> , <i>Xhoxc13</i>) (Lombardo and Slack, 2001)
31-35	Limb development	<i>NβT/TRDN</i> (Brown <i>et al.</i> , 2005)
36-40	Digit differentiation	Genes A-W (Buckbinder and Brown, 1992)
41-46	Tail reabsorption and metamorphic climax	<i>Shh</i> and <i>Hip</i> (Hasebe <i>et al.</i> , 2008)

Following the decision to bin the tadpole morphometric data into Gosner stages, analysis of the data by Gosner stage was carried out by first rerunning the PCA analyses to represent the elements and water quality that tadpoles were exposed to at a particular developmental stages. Therefore, tadpole morphometric data were separated into different Gosner stages (25-30, 31-35, 36-40, and 41-46) as described above, and matched with the PCs generated for water quality and metal concentrations taken at the sites for those specific weeks. Separate PCAs were therefore run for each Gosner stage band, using only data for the associated element concentrations and water quality at that stage. Throughout, PC 1 and PC 2 together contributed ~ 60-80 % of all variation, so only PC 1 and PC 2 were used within the GLMERs with tadpole morphometrics. The inclusion of more PCs would complicate interpretation of the results, when the highest proportion of variation is realised through the first two PCs. As with **Chapter 2**, GLMER models were chosen as the most appropriate for data analysis; in the results section relationships between PCs and tadpole morphometrics are visually represented as linear regressions. In some cases, while a significant effect is found through the model, this is not seen to be a linear relationship.

Statistical analysis

PCA analysis was carried out in R Studio (version 2023.09.1) using the factoextra, FactoMineR, and ggplot2 packages. PC 1 and PC 2 component loadings for elements and water quality parameters for each Gosner stage were extracted, and used in generalised linear mixed models (GLMERs) with an identity link function, with site included as a random effect. In these models, the tadpole morphometric data were the independent variables, and the element (as PC1 and PC2) and the water quality parameters (as PC1 and PC2) were the dependent variables. GLMER models were validated using the DHARMA package in R studio. Graphs were created using R studio.

Results

Element concentrations across sites over time

The following metals from the multi element standard were not detected in any water samples collected as part of this study, and so were not included in further analyses: antimony, arsenic, beryllium, bismuth, cadmium, cobalt, chromium, copper, molybdenum, nickel, lead, selenium, silver, tellurium, and vanadium. Only the following elements were present in water samples obtained from sites at high enough concentrations to be detected: aluminium, boron, barium, calcium, iron, potassium, lithium, magnesium, manganese, sodium, strontium, titanium, and zinc (**Appendix 4.2**).

Figure 4.2 provides a visual representation of elements detected at the sites across the weeks of sampling, with some sites (Bishopton, Ravenswood Bog, Hogganfield Park) varying in concentrations of a particular element, such as calcium, across the weeks, while some sites (Oldhall Ponds and Victoria Park) were more stable in concentrations across the weeks. There are only two weeks of data collection for Langlands Gate, so variability over time cannot be commented on. Ravenswood Bog had variable concentrations of elements across the weeks (**Figure 4.2**). As described in the **Statistical Approach** section, these data were then analysed using PCA, and as expected based on **Figure 4.2**, samples from Ravenswood

Bog at different weeks did not cluster together (**Figure 4.3**). Samples from different weeks at Victoria Park also did not cluster together (**Figure 4.3**). Overall, PCA analysis of the metal data resulted in six separate clusters (**Figure 4.3**). Langlands Gate (only two weeks of data collected before the pond desiccated), Oldhall Ponds, and Hogganfield Park were separate and distinct in their element concentrations and the elements at these sites were generally stable across time. Bishopton clustered in element concentration over the weeks, but overlapped with data from other sites. For this PCA analysis including data from all sites and all weeks, elements which had the most influence in PC 1 (responsible for 38.6 % of overall variation) were strontium, lithium, and calcium (**Table 4.5, Figure 4.4**). In PC 2 (18.1 % of variation), the elements having the most influence were zinc, magnesium, and manganese (**Table 4.45, Figure 4.4**).

Figure 4.2: Element concentrations (mg/L) per week at each site, where all elements are presented on the Y axis, with the exception of calcium which is presented on the secondary (right) Y axis, shown in yellow. Data are means \pm SEM, $n=3$. These data were analysed within a PCA analysis (Figure 4.3) to look for clustering between sites and weeks.

Figure 4.3: Results from cluster analysis of average element concentration measurements collected from ponds per week from all sites. Letters and numbers relate to the site code and week that the water samples were collected from: Bishopton (B) 1-9, Hogganfield (H) 1-8, Langlands Gate (L) 1 and 2, Oldhall Ponds (O) 1-4, Ravenswood Bog (R) 1-9, and Victoria Park (V) 1-4. Actual concentrations of elements can be seen in **Figure 4.2**.

Table 4.5: PCA outputs from element concentration data (all sites, all time points) comprising component loadings of metals on two orthogonally rotated principal components (PC1 and PC2). Values in bold indicate elements that contribute significantly to either PC1 or PC2 (loading of at least +/- 0.4). Each PC has one dimension, with the mid-point value being 0. The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. PCA 1 and 2 explain >50 % of variation, and so only these two dimensions are considered.

	Metal	PC1	PC2
Elements	Aluminium	-0.12	0.462
	Boron	0.715	0.177
	Barium	0.814	-0.015
	Calcium	0.903	-0.197
	Iron	-0.417	0.072
	Potassium	0.667	0.547
	Lithium	0.912	0.006
	Magnesium	-0.103	0.902
	Manganese	-0.082	0.611
	Sodium	0.179	0.527
	Strontium	0.953	-0.144
	Titanium	-0.138	0.159
	Zinc	-0.014	0.913
	% Variation explained	38.6	18.1
	% Total variation explained	56.7	

Figure 4.4: PCA output of component loadings from collated element measurements from all sites. A higher \cos^2 value indicates a higher component loading value.

Water quality parameters across sites and weeks

Figure 4.5 is a visual representation of how water quality changed between sites across the weeks of sampling, with some sites (Bishopton, and Ravenswood Bog) varying in water quality across weeks, while some sites (Oldhall Ponds and Victoria Park) were more stable in their overall water physiochemical variables across the weeks. There are only two weeks of data collection for Langlands Gate, so variability over time cannot be commented on. Water quality data from Ravenswood Bog were very variable across the weeks (**Figure 4.5**). As described in the **Statistical Approach** section, these data were then analysed using PCA, and as expected based on **Figure 4.5**, samples from Ravenswood Bog were spread out across several cluster points (**Figure 4.6**). Victoria Park had outliers spread across the dimensions. Bishopton water quality data clustered together across the weeks, but overlapped with other sites as seen for this site in the metal PCA analysis. PCA analysis based on the water quality parameters resulted in five separate clusters of data (**Figure 4.6**). Compared to the overall PCA for the metal concentrations (**Figure 4.3**), the water quality clusters are more spread out and show less uniformity between sites. Langlands Gate (with two weeks of data before desiccation), separated into different clusters. Data across weeks from Oldhall Ponds and Hogganfield Park were mostly separate from other sites, as different weeks for the site tended to cluster together. The range of values of water quality parameters measured at each site across the weeks can be found in **Appendix 3.1**. For this PCA including data from all sites and all weeks, the water quality variables having the most influence in PCA 1 (responsible for 54.4 % of overall variation) were conductivity, TDS and salinity and in PCA 2 (responsible for 20.1 % variation) DO and pH (**Figure 4.7, Table 4.6**). Conductivity, TDS, and salinity were all highly correlated as might be expected with very similar component loading scores. Temperature was not seen to account for any variation when the water quality data were considered with all time points included.

Figure 4.5: Water quality parameters per week from each site. Units for each parameter are as follows: Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH (none), Conductivity (μ), TDS (mg/L), Salinity (ppm), DO (%). These data were analysed within a PCA analysis (Figure 4.3) to look for clustering between sites and weeks. Only one measurement taken per site per week.

Figure 4.6: Results from cluster analysis of water quality measurements per week from all sites. Letters and numbers relate to the site code and week that the water samples were collected from: Bishopton (B) 1-9, Hogganfield (H) 1-8, Langlands Gate (L) 1 and 2, Oldhall Ponds (O) 1-4, Ravenswood Bog (R) 1-9, and Victoria Park (V) 1-4. Water quality values are given in **Figure 4.5**.

Table 4.6: PCA outputs from water quality data (all sites, all time points) comprising two orthogonally rotated principal components (PC 1 and PC 2). Values in bold indicate water quality variables that contribute significantly to either PC 1 or PC 2 (loading of at least +/- 0.4). The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. PC 1 and 2 explain >50 % of variation, and so only these two dimensions are considered. Temperature did not contribute to either PC and so a score was not generated or presented.

	Water quality parameter	PC 1	PC 2
Water Quality	Conductivity	0.987	-0.114
	TDS	0.986	-0.101
	Salinity	0.985	-0.106
	DO	-0.049	0.893
	pH	0.538	0.556
	% Variation explained	54.4	20.1
	% Total variation explained		74.5

Figure 4.7: PCA output of component loadings from collated water quality measurements from all sites. A higher \cos^2 value indicates a higher component loading value.

The PCA analyses including data from all sites and all time points are useful in understanding how these parameters change over time at each site. However, as described in the **Statistical Approach** section, analysis of how these parameters were related to tadpole morphology accounted for tadpole development by binning tadpole morphology into Gosner stages. To generate PCs for the GLMERs that represented element concentration and water quality that tadpoles were exposed to at each Gosner stage, PCAs were rerun for each Gosner stage using only the data collected from pond water data collected at those particular Gosner stages.

Gosner stages 25-30

During Gosner stages 25-30, tadpoles in the current study were exposed to pond water where elements having the most influence in PC 1 (49.8 % of variation) were calcium, strontium, and magnesium and in PC 2 (16.7 % of variation) iron, aluminium, and lithium (**Table 4.7**). At Gosner stages 25-30 the tadpoles were inhabiting ponds where the water quality variables having the most influence in PC 1 (56.9 % of variation) were conductivity, TDS and salinity and in PC 2 (18.1 % of variation) DO and pH. Loading plots for these PCA analyses are presented in **Appendix 3.3**.

Both PC 1 and PC 2 calculated for elements had no effect on any of the morphometric variables (**Table 4.8**). PC 1 calculated for water quality had no effect on any of the morphometric variables (**Table 4.8**). PC 2 for water quality had a significant effect on tadpole total length, SVL, tail length, and head width (**Table 4.8**), where total length and tail length was higher with increased PC 2 score (**Figure 4.8 A,C; Table 4.8**), and head width and SVL was lower with increased water quality PC 2 score (**Figure 4.8 B,D; Table 4.8**).

Table 4.7: PCA outputs from elements and water quality variables tadpoles were exposed to from Gosner stages 25-30 consisting of component loadings of elements observed on two orthogonally rotated principal components (PC1 and PC2). Values in bold indicate elements and water quality that contribute significantly to either PC 1 or PC 2 (loading of at least ± 0.4). The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. PC 1 and 2 explain $> 50\%$ of variation, and so only these two dimensions are considered. Titanium and zinc were not present in any of the water samples that tadpoles from these developmental stages were exposed to, and so have not been considered here.

Gosner stage	Elements	PC 1	PC 2
25-30	Aluminium	0.029	0.8
	Boron	0.658	-0.273
	Barium	0.879	0.105
	Calcium	0.95	-0.085
	Iron	-0.302	0.824
	Potassium	0.824	0.203
	Lithium	0.077	-0.445
	Magnesium	0.923	0.056
	Manganese	0.748	0.213
	Sodium	0.502	0.362
	Strontium	0.929	0.008
	% Variation explained	49.8	16.7
	% Total variation explained	66.5	
	Water Quality parameter	PC 1	PC 2
	Conductivity	0.98	-0.137
	DO	-0.028	0.848
	pH	0.639	0.391
	Salinity	0.975	-0.126
	TDS	0.976	-0.123
	Temperature	-0.376	-0.402
% Variation explained	56.9	18.1	
% Total variation explained	75		

Table 4.8: GLMER results of element and water quality PCA outputs against tadpole morphometric data from Gosner stages 25-30. Significance codes are as follows: NS = $P > 0.05$, $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

PCA 1						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
25-30	Elements	Mass	8.9971	1.395	0.163	NS
		Total Length	64.9177	1.152	0.249	NS
		SVL	64.9835	-1.158	0.247	NS
		Tail Length	64.87	-1.152	0.249	NS
		Head Width	0.841	-0.157	0.875	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	14.165	0.895	0.371	NS
		Total Length	94.591	0.24	0.810	NS
		SVL	94.716	-0.241	0.809	NS
		Tail Length	94.521	-0.24	0.811	NS
		Head Width	1.298	-0.775	0.438	NS
PCA 2						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
25-30	Elements	Mass	8.9005	-1.747	0.081	NS
		Total Length	15.0034	0.051	0.960	NS
		SVL	15.02	-0.076	0.940	NS
		Tail Length	14.9929	-0.054	0.957	NS
		Head Width	0.7717	1.504	0.133	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	9.239	0.939	0.348	NS
		Total Length	2.535	-27.551	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		SVL	2.593	27.116	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Tail Length	2.536	27.621	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Head Width	0.611	-3.336	0.001	***

Figure 4.8: Tadpole total length (A), SVL (B), tail length (C) and head width (D) for Gosner stages 25-30 against water quality PC 2 score (driven by DO and pH). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 25-30 for Victoria Park as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Gosner stages 31-35

During Gosner stages 31-35 the three elements having the most influence in PC 1 were magnesium, barium, and calcium (**Table 4.9**). In PC 2 (responsible for 19.1 % of variation), the elements having the most influence were lithium, potassium, and aluminium. Loading plots for these PCA analyses are presented in **Appendix 3.3**.

There were no significant effects of PC 1 from the elements on tadpole morphometrics (**Table 4.10**) but element PC 2 significantly affected tadpole mass, with a higher mass as PC 2 score increased (**Figure 4.9**). Both PC 1 and PC 2 had no effect on any of the morphometric variables measured for water quality (**Table 4.10**).

Table 4.9: PCA outputs from elements and water quality variables exposed to tadpoles from Gosner stages 31-35 consisting of component loadings of elements observed on two orthogonally rotated principal components (PC 1 and PC 2). Values in bold indicate elements that contribute significantly to either PC 1 or PC 2 (loading of at least ± 0.4). The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. PC 1 and 2 explain >50 % of variation, and so only these two dimensions are considered.

Gosner stage	Elements	PC 1	PC 2	
31-35	Aluminium	0.103	0.527	
	Boron	0.872	0.03	
	Barium	0.913	0.045	
	Calcium	0.905	-0.235	
	Iron	-0.541	0.187	
	Potassium	0.581	0.629	
	Lithium	0.047	0.884	
	Magnesium	0.937	-0.159	
	Manganese	0.603	0.109	
	Sodium	0.464	0.123	
	Strontium	0.831	0.052	
	Titanium	0.008	0.038	
	Zinc	0.002	0.079	
	% Variation explained		41.2	19.1
	% Total variation explained		60.3	
	Water Quality parameter		PC 1	PC 2
	Conductivity		0.984	-0.168
	DO		0.116	0.811
	pH		0.312	0.731
	Salinity		0.983	-0.167
TDS		0.984	-0.16	
Temperature		-0.341	-0.486	
% Variation explained		52.1	25.2	
% Total variation explained		77.3		

Table 4.10: GLMER results of element and water quality PCA outputs against tadpole morphometric data from Gosner stages 31-35. Significance codes are as follows: NS = $P > 0.05$, $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

PCA 1						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
31-35	Elements	Mass	9.603	0.672	0.501	NS
		Total Length	82.850	0.771	0.441	NS
		SVL	82.840	-0.770	0.442	NS
		Tail Length	82.870	-0.773	0.439	NS
		Head Width	0.844	-0.087	0.931	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	7.545	0.645	0.519	NS
		Total Length	37.777	0.528	0.598	NS
		SVL	37.776	-0.532	0.595	NS
		Tail Length	37.789	-0.529	0.597	NS
		Head Width	0.616	0.666	0.506	NS
PCA 2						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
31-35	Elements	Mass	5.313	-5.226	1.73×10^{-7}	***
		Total Length	25.555	0.286	0.775	NS
		SVL	25.555	-0.263	0.792	NS
		Tail Length	25.563	-0.267	0.789	NS
		Head Width	0.444	1.003	0.316	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	9.853	-1.694	0.090	NS
		Total Length	21.545	-1.011	0.312	NS
		SVL	21.531	1.009	0.313	NS
		Tail Length	21.559	1.026	0.305	NS
		Head Width	0.716	1.410	0.159	NS

Figure 4.9: Tadpole mass for Gosner stages 31-35 against element concentration PC 2 score (driven by lithium, potassium, and aluminium). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 31-35 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Gosner stages 36-40

For the Gosner stage 36-40, element PC1 (40.2 % of variation) was most influenced by magnesium, boron and calcium (**Table 4.11**) and PC 2 (18.7 % of variation) by lithium, zinc, and potassium. For Gosner stage 36-40, the water quality variables with the most influence in PC 1 (53.7 % of variation) were TDS, conductivity, and salinity (**Table 4.11**) and for PC 2 (23.4 % of variation) were DO and pH. Loading plots for these PCA analyses are presented in **Appendix 3.3**.

For elements, PC1 had a highly significant positive effect on tadpole mass (**Table 4.12, Figure 4.10**), and PC 2 had a significant positive effect on tadpole mass, total length, SVL, and tail length (**Table 4.12, Figure 4.11**). Tadpole mass was higher with increased PC 1 score for elements. Tadpole mass, total length, SVL, and tail length was higher with increased PC 2 score. For water quality, PC 1 had a significant negative effect on tadpole mass (**Table 4.12, Figure 4.12**), and PC 2 had a highly significant negative effect on tadpole SVL, and a significant effect on total length and tail length (**Table 4.12, Figure 4.13**).

Table 4.11: PCA outputs from elements and water quality variables from Gosner stages 36-40 consisting of component loadings of elements observed on two orthogonally rotated principal components (PC 1 and PC 2). Values in bold indicate that these elements are considered to contribute significantly to either PC 1 or PC 2 (loading of at least ± 0.4). The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. PC 1 and 2 explain a large proportion (over 50 %) of variation, and so only these two dimensions are considered.

Gosner stage	Elements	PC 1	PC 2	
36-40	Aluminium	-0.073	0.499	
	Boron	0.887	0.083	
	Barium	0.843	0.086	
	Calcium	0.887	-0.185	
	Iron	-0.637	0.11	
	Potassium	0.554	0.59	
	Lithium	0.004	0.918	
	Magnesium	0.926	-0.136	
	Manganese	0.479	0.15	
	Sodium	0.499	0.077	
	Strontium	0.866	0.023	
	Titanium	0.025	0.029	
	Zinc	0.001	0.833	
	% Variation explained		40.2	18.7
	% Total variation explained		58.9	
	Water Quality parameter		PC 1	PC 2
	Conductivity		0.976	-0.207
	DO		0.219	0.856
	pH		0.481	0.646
	Salinity		0.976	-0.205
TDS		0.977	-0.203	
Temperature		-0.286	-0.356	
% Variation explained		53.7	23.4	
% Total variation explained		77.1		

Table 4.12: GLMER results of element and water quality PCA outputs against tadpole morphometric data from Gosner stages 36-40. Only significant results have been plotted. Significance codes are as follows: NS = $P > 0.05$, $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

PCA 1						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
36-40	Elements	Mass	6.936	2.205	0.028	*
		Total Length	64.614	-0.681	0.496	NS
		SVL	64.596	0.679	0.497	NS
		Tail Length	64.553	0.673	0.501	NS
		Head Width	0.544	-0.875	0.382	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	4.847	2.632	0.008	**
		Total Length	33.257	-0.336	0.737	NS
		SVL	33.257	0.341	0.733	NS
		Tail Length	33.226	0.323	0.747	NS
		Head Width	0.373	-1.304	0.192	NS
PCA 2						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
36-40	Elements	Mass	5.185	3.475	0.001	***
		Total Length	1.657	-8.917	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		SVL	1.733	7.763	8.3×10^{-15}	***
		Tail Length	1.660	8.815	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Head Width	0.417	-0.929	0.353	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	4.831	1.204	0.228	NS
		Total Length	1.441	3.088	0.002	**
		SVL	1.516	-3.496	4.72×10^{-4}	***
		Tail Length	1.444	-3.093	0.002	**
		Head Width	0.388	0.335	0.738	NS

Figure 4.10: Tadpole mass for Gosner stages 36-40 against element concentration PC 1 score (driven by magnesium, boron, and calcium). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 36-40 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Figure 4.11: Tadpole mass (A), total length (B), SVL (C) and tail length (D) for Gosner stages 36-40 against element PC 2 score (driven by lithium, zinc, and potassium). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 36-40 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Figure 4.11: Tadpole mass for Gosner stages 36-40 against water quality PC 1 score (driven by TDS, conductivity, and salinity). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 36-40 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Figure 4.13: Tadpole total length (A), SVL (B), and head width (C) for Gosner stages 36-40 against water quality PC 2 score (driven by DO and pH). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 36-40 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Gosner stages 41-46

For Gosner stages 41-46, the elements with most influence in PC 1 (48.4 % of variation) were magnesium, boron and strontium and in PC 2 (18.8 % of variation) potassium, aluminium and sodium (**Table 4.13**). For these final Gosner stages, water quality variables with most influence in PC 1 (56.9 % of variation) were TDS, salinity and conductivity and in PC 2 (26 % of variation) DO, temperature, and pH. Loading plots for these PCA analyses are presented in **Appendix 3.3**.

For elements, PC 1 had a highly significant effect on all tadpole morphometrics (tadpole mass, total length, SVL, tail length, and head width) (**Table 4.14, Figure 4.14**). Mass, total length, and tail length were all lower with increasing PC 1 score for elements, and SVL and head width were both higher both with increased element PC 1 score. An increase in element PC 2 score also had a highly significant positive effect on tadpole total length, SVL and tail length (**Figure 4.15**).

For water quality, PC 1 had a highly significant negative effect on tadpole total length, SVL, and tail length (**Table 4.14, Figure 4.16**). As PC 1 score for water quality increased, tadpole total length, SVL, and tail length were lower. PC 2 also had a significant negative effect on tadpole mass (although less significant than other morphometric measurements), total length, SVL, and tail length (**Table 4.14, Figure 4.17**). As PC 2 score for water quality increased, tadpole mass, total length, SVL, and tail length were lower.

Table 4.13: PCA outputs from elements and water quality variables exposed to tadpoles from Gosner stages 41-46 consisting of component loadings of metals observed on two orthogonally rotated principal components (PC 1 and PC 2). Values in bold indicate that these metals are considered to contribute significantly to either PC 1 or PC 2 (loading of at least ± 0.4). The sign (positive or negative) indicates the direction that a given variable in that PC is going, and the value indicates the strength of that relationship. PC 1 and 2 explain $>50\%$ of variation, and so only these two dimensions are considered. Zinc was not found in any of the water samples that tadpoles from these developmental stages were exposed to, and so has not been considered here.

Gosner stage	Elements	PC 1	PC 2	
41-46	Aluminium	-0.452	0.624	
	Boron	0.872	0.302	
	Barium	0.807	-0.105	
	Calcium	0.857	-0.3	
	Iron	-0.825	0.282	
	Potassium	0.378	0.677	
	Lithium	0.489	0.569	
	Magnesium	0.916	-0.188	
	Manganese	-0.582	0.081	
	Sodium	0.551	0.576	
	Strontium	0.869	0.013	
	Titanium	0.049	0.426	
	% Variation explained		48.4	18.8
	% Total variation explained		67.2	
	Water Quality parameter	PC 1	PC 2	
	Conductivity	0.981	-0.13	
	DO	0.168	0.811	
	pH	0.679	0.51	
	Salinity	0.984	-0.115	
	TDS	0.984	-0.12	
Temperature	-0.159	0.771		
% Variation explained		56.9	26	
% Total variation explained		82.9		

Table 4.14: GLMER results of element and water quality PCA outputs against tadpole morphometric data from Gosner stages 41-46. Please note that only significant results have been reported. Significance codes are as follows: NS = $P > 0.05$, $P < 0.001$ ***, 0.01 **, 0.05 *.

PCA 1						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
41-46	Elements	Mass	0.987	6.727	1.74×10^{-11}	***
		Total Length	1.036	-38.797	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		SVL	1.038	38.781	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Tail Length	1.035	38.764	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Head Width	0.040	-3.665	2.48×10^{-4}	***
	Water Quality	Mass	1.442	-0.279	0.780	NS
		Total Length	2.165	84.570	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		SVL	2.163	-84.583	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Tail Length	2.164	-84.593	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Head Width	0.058	1.085	0.278	NS
PCA 2						
Gosner stage	Variable	Tadpole Morphometric	Standard Error	t Value	z value	Significance Level
41-46	Elements	Mass	4.050	1.508	0.132	NS
		Total Length	2.918	-46.754	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		SVL	2.932	46.575	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Tail Length	2.917	46.729	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Head Width	0.175	-1.243	0.214	NS
	Water Quality	Mass	3.661	2.241	0.025	*
		Total Length	2.358	-54.541	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		SVL	2.374	54.028	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Tail Length	2.358	54.491	$< 2 \times 10^{-16}$	***
		Head Width	0.158	-1.147	0.251	NS

Site

- Bishopton
- Ravenswood Bog
- Hogganfield Park
- Victoria Park
- Oldhall Ponds

Figure 4.14: Tadpole mass (A), total length (B), SVL (C), tail length (D), and head width (E) for Gosner stages 41-46 against element concentration PC 1 score (driven by magnesium, boron, and strontium). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 41-46 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Figure 4.15: Tadpole total length (A), SVL (B), and tail length (C) for Gosner stages 41-46 against element concentration PC 2 score (driven by potassium, aluminium, and sodium). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 41-46 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Figure 4.16: Tadpole total length (A), SVL (B), and tail length (C) for Gosner stages 41-46 against water quality PC 1 score (driven by TDS, salinity, and conductivity). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 41-46 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Figure 4.17: Tadpole mass (A), total length (B), SVL (C) and tail length (D) for Gosner stages 36-40 against water quality PC 2 score (Driven by DO, temperature, and pH). The black dotted line is the line of best fit, and the grey shaded area represents the interquartile range of the data. There are no data for Gosner stages 41-46 for Langlands Gate as no tadpoles collected from this site were between these Gosner stages.

Discussion

Many pollutant metals cited within the literature as most toxic to amphibians, such as arsenic, cadmium and lead (see **Table 4.1**), were below detectable levels at the study sites (see **Table 4.3**), which is positive for the amphibian populations surveyed here. However, many variables can contribute to the toxicity of a particular metal, and laboratory studies reporting LC50 values or similar, are rarely applicable to wild studies regarding toxicity assumptions and comparisons (see **Table 4.1**). Metal analysis in the present study included essential (such as calcium and magnesium) and non-essential (such as lithium and aluminium) elements, and therefore the PCA outputs represent the mixture of elements found in natural habitats. PC 1 and PC 2 outputs are reported throughout in the context of the top three contributing metals or water quality variables for conciseness; however, it should be noted that each principal component score will be made up of more than three contributing metal or water quality variables that are found within a water body. Given the complexity of the mixtures occurring within the ponds, the top three are considered for simplicity, as those that are most likely driving relationships between said metals or water quality parameters and the tadpole morphometrics. These wild tadpoles are exposed to mixtures of metals within these ponds as well as varied water chemistry and other environmental stressors, which are rarely studied in their totality within the literature. Most research focused on toxicity of trace metals to amphibians has been carried out in the laboratory, with exposure either to metals in isolation or to a mixture of a few metals at known concentrations (see **Table 4.1**).

When the data from all weeks and sites were combined together in the PCA, metals which had the most influence in PC 1, and therefore explained the most variation between sites, were strontium, lithium, and calcium (**Table 4.5**), and in PC 2, zinc, magnesium, and manganese (**Table 4.5, Figure 4.4**). Of these metals, only manganese and potassium were found at exposure levels seen within the literature (Lanctot *et al.*, 2013; da Silva Veronez *et al.*, 2016, see **Table 4.3**). Laboratory exposures of manganese to amphibians were reported to result in increased body length, delayed metamorphosis, and increased body condition (with no change in SVL or mass) within an exposure range of 1.35 – 13.5 mg/L, with a 96 h LC50 of 39 mg/L (Shuhaimi-Othman *et al.*, 2012, da Silva Veronez *et al.*, 2016, Lanctôt *et al.*, 2016, Giroto *et al.*, 2020). Potassium has been found to have toxic effects on amphibians

within an exposure range of 0.1 – 1.5 µg/L but with no effect on growth and development (Lanctot *et al.*, 2013; Rissoli *et al.*, 2016; Buncharoen *et al.*, 2022).

Strontium was the metal identified overall as accounting for the most variation in the whole dataset, and was present in water samples from all sites at concentrations ranging from 0.02 – 0.28 mg/L, with the highest level found at Langlands Gate (0.28 mg/L; see **Table 4.3**). However, no relevant exposure literature could be identified with which to compare these results. It is unclear where the strontium present in the water samples originates from, but there are several potential sources identified in Scotland, such as from radiation or from granite mining (Davidson *et al.*, 2005; Natural Scotland, 2015). As there is no relevant exposure literature, it is difficult to conclude whether strontium is having an effect on tadpoles at the study sites investigated within this Chapter. More research is needed into the effects of strontium on tadpoles, as well as identifying how it is entering *R. temporaria* breeding ponds. Also contributing to PC 1, although not found at toxic concentrations in the present study, lithium exposure can cause endocrine disruption of the thyroid gland in anuran tadpoles, although no effects on mass, SVL or hindlimb length were found (Pinto Vidal *et al.*, 2021 (a), Pinto-Vidal *et al.*, 2021 (b), Peltzer *et al.*, 2024). No studies on the effects of calcium or magnesium concentrations on tadpoles were found within the literature. Both calcium and magnesium are major ions and essential for development. While they are not considered here as pollutants, their concentrations could still be significant to the growth and development of tadpoles. They are essential for processes such as ossification of bone, vitamin D3 production, and other metabolic processes (Whatley *et al.*, 2020; Rose, 2021). These metals also frequently contributed to the principal components generated for metals at different Gosner stages.

The water quality variables driving PCA 1 when all the data were considered together, were conductivity, TDS and salinity (**Figure 4.7, Table 4.6**), and for PCA 2, DO and pH. Temperature did not account for any variation in either PC 1 or PC 2 when the whole dataset was included. For principal component analysis, PC 1 is responsible for a higher share of the overall variation compared to PC 2 (Demšar *et al.*, 2013) suggesting that conductivity, TDS, and salinity represent the greatest differences in water quality between sites, followed by DO and pH. These water quality parameters are all commonly measured when assessing water

quality in the context of amphibian habitats (Odum and Zippel, 2008; Omer, 2019) and are influenced by the external environment (e.g. rainfall, habitat type, proximity to coast; Hopkins *et al.*, 2016, Sønderup *et al.*, 2016, Kirkpatrick Baird *et al.*, 2023). Changes to these parameters will affect tadpole growth, development, and health. For example, cold temperatures increase susceptibility to chytridiomycosis, as well as *Saprolegnia* fungal infections of amphibian eggs (Beattie, Aston and Milner, 1991; Hamilton *et al.*, 2012). High temperatures can cause accelerated developmental rates as well as reduction in antipredator behaviours, and outperformance by competing amphibian species (Hamilton *et al.*, 2012; Fong *et al.*, 2023). Low pH can decrease body size, decrease fertilisation success, increase mortality, exacerbate metal toxicity, increase body mass, and increase growth rate and developmental rate (Tyler-Jones, Beattie and Aston, 1989; Beattie, Aston and Milner, 1991; Bradford, Swanson and Gordon, 1992; Freda and McDonald, 1993; Fioramonti *et al.*, 1997; Lu *et al.*, 2021). High conductivity can decrease amphibian survival (Brand *et al.*, 2010) and high salinity can negatively affect growth, rate of metamorphosis, metamorph size, mortality and gill integrity (Bernabò *et al.*, 2013; Hsu *et al.*, 2018; Welch *et al.*, 2019). Pond water chemistry is far less studied than other water bodies such as rivers, and so there are very little baseline data available (Biggs and Williams, 2024).

The earliest Gosner stage considered here was stages 25-30 of development, where the tadpole is forming a limb bud which is growing, that will eventually become the hind limbs of the frog (**Appendix 1.1**). Between Gosner stages 25-30, PC 2 for water quality (driven by DO and temperature) had a significant positive relationship with tadpole total length, SVL, tail length, and head width and a significant negative effect on head width and SVL. This may suggest that as DO concentrations and the temperature of the pond water increase, total length and tail length increases while head width and SVL decreases for this Gosner stage. While the effects of DO on tadpole morphometrics are unknown, this aligns with previous studies showing that decreasing temperature decreases developmental rate (Hamilton *et al.*, 2012; Fong *et al.*, 2023). Element concentrations had no effect on tadpole morphometrics for this Gosner stage band. This is in contrast to a previous study on the effects of cadmium on northern leopard frogs (*Lithobates pipiens*) that showed greatest sensitivity of growth and development parameters to cadmium during Gosner stages 25-30 (Gross *et al.*, 2009).

For the next Gosner stages considered (stages 31-35), there were no effects of water quality (as PC 1 or 2) on tadpole morphometrics but there were effects of elements. Between Gosner stages 31-35, the tadpole limb bud, which is now at full size, forms a foot paddle and then four indentations which separate five areas that will eventually become the toes of the frog (**Appendix 1.1**). Tadpole mass got higher with increased element PC 2 (which was driven by concentration of lithium, potassium, and aluminium). Lithium ranged in concentration across the sites from 0.01 to 0.21 mg/L, with the greatest range found at Victoria Park, an urban Park in the centre of Glasgow. The highest concentrations of lithium were recorded at this site (**see Table 4.3**). Lithium can interact with the thyroid axis and so may have effects on the development of tadpoles (Pinto Vidal *et al.*, 2021). Exposure to 2.5 mg/L of lithium increased developmental rate in *Lithobates catesbeianus* (American bullfrog) tadpoles, but with no effect on mass, SVL, or hindlimb length (Pinto Vidal *et al.*, 2021). Although lithium concentrations were much lower than those used by Pinto Vidal *et al.* (2021), if chronic low levels of lithium, or greater variations in lithium concentration, contributed to the increased rate of metamorphosis at this site, this could explain why no tadpoles from Gosner stages 25-30 were found at Victoria Park. This site is an urban park with no obvious sources of pollutants other than litter that was observed within the pond. The reason for the higher lithium concentrations recorded at this site is unknown. Potassium exposure has not been shown to affect amphibian growth and development (Lanctot *et al.*, 2013), however aluminium can increase mass, decrease body size and body length, with no change in SVL (Tyler-Jones and Beattie, 1988, Bradford *et al.* 1992, Giroto *et al.* 2020, de Albuquerque *et al.* 2024). The combined effects of lithium and aluminium within the pond water may be driving these changes in tadpole mass during Gosner stages 31-35.

Between Gosner stages 36-40 of development, the tadpole's foot paddle with indentations separates into five individual digits and becomes a fully formed hind limb with limb size also increasing during these stages (**Appendix 1.1**). Both principal components generated for the elements and for water quality had a significant effect on tadpole morphology during these stages. For elements there was a significant positive effect of PC 1 (driven by magnesium, boron and calcium) on tadpole mass, and a significant positive effect of PC 2 (driven by lithium, zinc, and potassium) on tadpole mass, total length, SVL, and tail length. For PC 1, as previously discussed, there is no relevant exposure literature for magnesium and calcium. However, boron exposure from 50-100 mg/L (concentrations far higher than levels found

within the present study) increases tadpole growth rate (Laposata and Dunson, 1998; Evariste *et al.*, 2021). Zinc can cause both increased and decreased body length and mass as well as toxic effects to amphibians, within an exposure range of 10 µg/L – 13.5 mg/L and a 96 h LC50 of 3.61 mg/L (Clark *et al.*, 1998; Barry, 2011; Shuhaimi-Othman *et al.*, 2012; Patar *et al.*, 2021; Costa Motta *et al.*, 2023; de Albuquerque *et al.*, 2024). In contrast, tadpole mass was negatively affected by water quality PC 1 (driven by TDS, conductivity, and salinity) and total length, SVL, and tail length were all negatively affected by water quality PC2 (driven by DO and pH). Conductivity and TDS have not been shown to decrease tadpole mass, but decreased developmental rates have been observed at high salinity levels (3-12 ppt) (Hsu *et al.*, 2018).

The final Gosner stages considered were 41-46, where the tadpole undergoes its final phase of metamorphosis, with the tail being fully reabsorbed, emergence of the forelimbs, and configuration of the face and body into an adult frog morphology. At stage 46, a froglet has completed its metamorphosis and is ready to leave the pond and become terrestrial (**Appendix 1.1**). As with Gosner stages 36-40, both principal components generated for elements and water quality had a significant effect on tadpole morphology. Element PC1 (driven by magnesium, boron, and strontium) was negatively related to mass, total length, and tail length but positively related to SVL and head width. The decline in mass, total length, and tail length may result at this stage from the re-absorption of the tail and reconfiguration of tadpole morphology during metamorphosis at these stages (Buskirk and Saxer, 2001) and it is difficult to disentangle this from the effects of the elements available. There also may be unknown effects of strontium exposure causing these effects. Element PC 2 (potassium, aluminium and sodium) had a significant positive effect on tadpole total length, SVL and tail length. Water quality PC 1 (driven by TDS, salinity and conductivity) was negatively related to tadpole total length, SVL, and tail length whereas PC 2 (DO, temperature and pH) was negatively related to tadpole mass, total length, SVL, and tail length. As with the element exposure for this stage, declines in mass, total length, and tail length are likely a product of this particular developmental stage. At this Gosner stage, tadpoles are leaving the pond following successful metamorphosis and are a greater risk from desiccation (Gervasi and Foufopoulos, 2008; Székely *et al.*, 2017, 2020). The PCA cluster analysis on the complete set of water chemistry data, revealed that Hogganfield Park, Victoria Park, and Bishopton overlap in element concentrations and water quality across the

weeks. Oldhall Ponds, Ravenswood Bog, and Langlands Gate varied much more from week to week (see **Figures 4.4 and 4.7**). Although not statistically analysed by site, the figures of tadpole morphometrics suggest that Ravenswood Bog and Victoria Park consistently had bigger, heavier tadpoles than other sites, whereas Hogganfield Park consistently had smaller, lighter tadpoles (see **Figures 4.8-4.18**). This could affect the survival and health of tadpoles from these sites in the future (Beck and Congdon, 2000; Székely *et al.*, 2020).

For the latter two Gosner stage bands, both elements and water quality appeared to have a greater influence on morphology, suggesting an increased sensitivity parameters as metamorphosis progresses. This is in contrast to a previous study that showed greatest sensitivity of growth and development parameters during pre-metamorphosis in leopard frogs (*Rana pipiens*) (Gosner stages 25-30) (Gross *et al.*, 2009). The most sensitive stages of development to chemical pollutants and water quality is a factor that may vary between species and genera. For Gosner stage bands where both PC 1 and PC 2 had significant effects on morphology, PC 1 is likely to be having a greater effect. In addition to those elements already discussed, although iron did not appear to account for a large amount of variability between sites, this metal was found at concentrations that may be toxic to amphibian tadpoles, or to have EDC effects (**Figure 4.2, Table 4.1, Table 4.3**). Iron delays development and increases tail length (with no change to SVL and mass), along with other toxic effects reported at concentrations ranging from 0.51 – 100 mg/L and a 96 h LC50 of 1.9 mg/L (Shuhaimi-Othman *et al.*, 2012; da Silva Veronez *et al.*, 2016; Giroto *et al.*, 2020; Meddeb *et al.*, 2023; Murthy *et al.*, 2023).

The low number of variables used in the PCA for water quality may have influenced the robustness of these models. Collecting data on a greater number of water quality parameters, such as turbidity or BOD (biological oxygen demand) may increase the robustness of this approach and provide information on how these parameters affect tadpole growth and development. While element concentration and water quality were considered separately here, bioavailability of the elements is affected by water quality, and differing water quality can exacerbate the effects of metal toxicity (Lu *et al.*, 2021). Future studies could explore whether a combined PCA analysis of element and water quality parameters would be beneficial. The use of the PCA approach in this Chapter allowed for the consideration of

ecologically relevant mixtures of elements and water quality in order to determine their potential effects on different tadpole morphometric measurements, and to evaluate the use of tadpole morphometrics as a non-destructive biomonitoring tool.

Deciding which tadpole morphometrics to measure is important when considering method development for *in situ* sampling. Those morphometrics most affected by elements and water quality were tadpole mass and tadpole total length, with both increases and decreases seen at different Gosner stages. These variables are often seen to be correlated within other ecotoxicological studies spanning different metals; cadmium (Sun *et al.*, 2018), chromium (Montalvao *et al.*, 2018), copper (Zheng *et al.*, 2021), and zinc (de Albuquerque *et al.*, 2024). Tadpole total length is usually correlated with SVL and tail length, as well as tadpole mass, and so perhaps unsurprisingly these morphometrics frequently demonstrated significance within the same PC. Tadpole head width was the parameter affected least by the PCs tested, but there were no variables that were not affected and so all tadpole morphometrics tested in this study have been shown to be valuable. These measurements have been used previously within amphibian ecotoxicology literature (see **Table 4.1**), but not they are not necessarily all used in every study. There are also other morphometric measurements such as hindlimb length which were not recorded here. Minimising stress to the tadpole during sampling is an important consideration for this type of study and finding a balance between the number of parameters measured, versus the stress to the animal.

A total of six sites from across the central belt of Glasgow were surveyed as part of this Chapter. These sites varied in location and other factors not measured in this study which may have also influenced tadpole morphometrics. The sites consisted of a private garden pond (Bishopton), urban parks (Hogganfield Park and Victoria Park) and nature reserves surrounded by a golf course and industry (Langlands Gate), industry and construction work (Oldhall Ponds) and urbanised areas (Ravenswood Bog). All of the sites had potential sources for trace metal contaminants to enter ponds through runoff and leaching. Agricultural sites were also visited to try and identify sites that might be affected by agricultural run-off, however no sites with high enough numbers of *R. temporaria* tadpoles were found. No fish were observed in any of the ponds, although Oldhall Ponds was of significant enough size that it could support fish populations. Other amphibians (common toads (*Bufo bufo*), smooth

newts (*Lissotriton vulgaris*) and palmate newts (*Lissotriton helveticus*) were observed at all sites, alongside a wide range of invertebrate predators of tadpoles such as great diving beetle larvae (*Dytiscus marginalis*). The presence of this species provides a relevant predation stressor and source of competition for resources such as food and oxygen, which is also known to affect tadpole morphometrics (Katzmann, Waringer-Löschenkohl and Waringer, 2003; Collier *et al.*, 2008; Middlemis Maher, Werner and Denver, 2013). Tadpoles feed on substrate and algae, and pass water across their gills for respiration. This exposes them to trace metals bound within the sediment, bioaccumulated within their food sources, or dissolved within the water body. Understanding how tadpoles bioaccumulate trace metals is crucial, as tadpoles are an important food source for other organisms. Tadpoles have a high mass conversion efficiency, (i.e. they consume a high volume of food compared to their body mass) leading to a high level of bioaccumulation within their bodies, driving a transfer of trace metals from aquatic to terrestrial habitats (Rowe, 2014; Lanctôt *et al.*, 2017; Obiakor *et al.*, 2017). Consumption of contaminated tadpoles by their predators can then transfer contamination to other parts of the food web.

Fieldwork for this Chapter took place during unseasonably warm weather in June/July 2023, with the warmest June on record for Scotland, combined with weeks of no rainfall (Met Office, 2023). Desiccation was a factor that could not be controlled as part of the study, which decreased water levels and altered the water chemistry of the ponds. Data for Langlands Gate could only be collected for 2 weeks as the pond desiccated completely; tadpoles from this site only reached Gosner stage 25-30. Conversely, data for Gosner Stages 25-30 could not be collected from Victoria Park, as tadpoles at this site were already developed past this stage at the beginning of sampling.

There is a significant bias within ecotoxicological literature towards *Xenopus* as a model species (Cannatella and De Sá, 1993; Schiesari, Grillitsch and Grillitsch, 2007; da Silva *et al.*, 2020). The endocrine processes involved in metamorphosis are also better studied in *Xenopus* than other amphibian taxa (Bevan, Prasad and Henderson, 2000; Orton and Tyler, 2015; Svanholm, 2022). Despite the knowledge gaps in how EDC disruption affects a wider range of amphibian species, there is still significant evidence that endocrine disruptors, such as trace metals, found in the environment can affect the thyroid axis and alter the metamorphic

process in larval amphibians, as well as having other toxic effects (Kloas *et al.*, 2009; Carr and Patiño, 2011; Trudeau *et al.*, 2020; Dang, 2022). This has potential consequences for amphibians, as smaller tadpoles (due to direct effects of endocrine disruption or as a consequence of increased metamorphic rate or sublethal toxicity) tend to become smaller adults. Smaller adults have poorer survival and fecundity (Semlitsch, Scott and Pechmann, 1988; Altwegg and Reyer, 2003; Cabrera-Guzmán *et al.*, 2013) with consequences for continued recruitment of amphibian populations, already in decline through a multitude of threats. Several ponds thought to be highly polluted based on visual inspection were identified and visited as part of the site selection process, however none of these sites contained *R. temporaria* tadpoles. As a result, it is possible that *R. temporaria* avoids breeding activity and spawn laying in chemically polluted ponds if their semi-permeable skin allows them to detect this, as has been shown for water quality variables such as salinity, pH, and conductivity (Aston, Beattie and Milner, 1987; Viertel, 1999; Håkansson and Loman, 2004). Spawn has also been shown to die in chemically polluted water bodies (Manson, 2002; Severtsova, Kormilitsin and Severtsov, 2016). Avoidance of chemically polluted water bodies would provide a significant advantage when it comes to offspring survival and fitness, however in a changing climate where ponds are disappearing and becoming more ephemeral, choice of ponds may become more limited for future generations.

In conclusion, this study aimed to contribute to the limited literature on wild exposure of amphibians to metals, and presents an example of non-destructive methodology for evaluating the effects of elements and water quality on *R. temporaria* tadpole morphometrics. Refined methodologies for detecting the sublethal effects of chemical pollutant toxicity and endocrine disruption over time in wild amphibians are essential for environmental monitoring. The approach used here was relatively quick and inexpensive compared to other destructive methodologies such as molecular methods and histology. It would be useful to build on the use of tadpole morphometrics to monitor toxicant effects by comparing exposures in the lab to data collected from the wild. As previously discussed throughout this thesis (see **Chapter 1**), many ecotoxicological studies are lab-based, and very few studies are carried out using data collected from the wild. These studies tend to expose individuals to concentrations of chemical pollutants far above those they experience in the wild, and often consist of a single pollutant or a mixture of a few pollutants under tightly controlled conditions. As such, there is a lack of data regarding what is ecologically relevant, such as

contaminant mixtures occurring where tadpoles are actually found, and the effects that they have. There is also a lack of data on baseline metal levels in reference ponds, including the levels of essential metals such as calcium and magnesium which developing tadpoles need at different life stages. The lack of published literature on these areas for amphibians, makes the interpretation of this study challenging in many ways.

The data collected in this Chapter provide initial baseline data for element concentrations and water quality parameters found in natal pond water during the breeding season at *R. temporaria* breeding ponds in Scotland. It also trialled the use of tadpole morphometrics of *R. temporaria* as a biomonitoring tool in a non-destructive way that analyses wild data over time, which is a beneficial addition to the literature. A wide range of data from many different ponds is now needed in order to build a bigger picture across landscapes and to elucidate patterns of elements that are commonly found, combined with GIS land use methodologies such as that used in **Chapter 2** to hypothesise methods of entry into the environment and the tadpole morphometrics they affect. This methodology could also incorporate other types of contaminant to further our understanding of the effects of ecologically relevant environmental mixtures on amphibian metamorphosis. For example, data from the androgenic cell assay utilised in **Appendix 2.4** or other similar assays carried out on natal pond water could be incorporated.

Chapter five: General discussion

Topic overview

Amphibians are the most threatened group of vertebrates, with an estimated 42 % of all species threatened with extinction (Díaz *et al.*, 2019). Chemical pollution exposure is the second biggest threat to amphibians, due to the semi-permeable nature of their skin that easily allows pollutants to enter their bodies. Their biphasic lifestyle is tied to water bodies, and the pond environments where they are found are often at risk from pollution events (Quaranta *et al.*, 2009; Orton and Tyler, 2015; Luedtke *et al.*, 2023). Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are chemical pollutants that disrupt hormone systems that control key bodily processes (Norris, 2011). EDCs can come from many sources, such as pharmaceuticals, agricultural and road runoff, and industrial processes, and exposure has been demonstrated to have wide ranging effects in anurans (frogs and toads), such as cancer, altered skin microbiomes, reduced immune system function, changes to sex ratios, reduced fertility, deformities, and effects on metamorphosis and growth and development (Sower, Reed and Babbitt, 2000; Heimeier and Shi, 2010; Lambert *et al.*, 2015; Orton and Tyler, 2015; Hoffmann and Kloas, 2016; Tamschick *et al.*, 2016; Bókony *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2020; Burden *et al.*, 2022; McGuire and Robert, 2023; Norris, 2024). Both reproduction and the growth and development of anurans are important functions that are heavily dependent upon the endocrine system, and have been shown to be affected by EDCs, and so these processes provide excellent opportunities for studying the effects of EDC exposure (Orton and Tyler, 2015).

Destructive methods that are often utilised within the literature go against the aims of conservation efforts, and so there is a need for non-destructive ways of monitoring reproductive success and the growth and development of anurans in the wild (Orton *et al.*, 2023). This thesis aimed to develop non-destructive biomarkers or biomonitoring tools for the effects of EDC exposure on the reproduction and growth and development of wild *Rana temporaria*. This species was chosen because a wealth of information about its natural ecology and biology is known, its widespread nature across much of Europe and northern Asia, as well as its previous use as a non-model species for amphibian ecotoxicological

literature (Dabagyan and Sleptsova, 1991; Hayes, 1998; Pettersson and Berg, 2007; Brande-Lavridsen, Christensen-Dalsgaard and Korsgaard, 2008).

Key findings of the thesis

Chapter 1 provided a literature review of existing biomarkers and biomonitoring tools (both destructive and non-destructive in nature) for reproduction and growth and development in anurans, and critically evaluated existing techniques. *Xenopus* species are often overused as a model organism, despite its unique ecology that makes comparison with other anuran species difficult (Cannatella and de Sá, 1993; Hunter, 2008). This Chapter therefore also provided an overview of the target species for this thesis, the common frog (*Rana temporaria*), as well as its ecology, potential exposure to endocrine disruptors in Scotland, and use as a model organism within ecotoxicological studies.

The literature examined highlighted how the natural ecology of amphibians (through both their biology and their habitat requirements) makes them especially vulnerable to chemical pollutants (Boone *et al.*, 2024). The review also highlighted how little we know about the effects of EDCs in wild amphibians, due to most literature being lab-based with very few wild studies (Venturino *et al.*, 2003; Venturino and Pechen de D'Angelo, 2005). It is difficult to extrapolate the findings of lab-based data to wild population level data, highlighting the need for more field-based biomarkers for amphibian ecotoxicology (Beebee and Griffiths, 2005). There is also a need for more long term data collection, both at the individual level (such as through life stages) and at the population level, which cannot be achieved through destructive methods in the wild (Magurran *et al.*, 2010; Lindenmayer *et al.*, 2012). From these findings, it was decided that the first focus of this thesis would be to investigate the relationships between characteristics of amphibian breeding ponds and the surrounding environment and adult and larval amphibian morphometrics, to investigate how these environmental characteristics may be associated with EDC pollution, and to allow comparisons of existing biomarkers within an environmental context.

Chapter 2 investigated the relationships between land use surrounding amphibian breeding ponds, the water quality of these ponds, and different morphometric measurements of tadpoles. This Chapter provided a better understanding of the complex relationships between environmental parameters and potential pollution exposures and the growth and development of *R. temporaria* tadpoles. Additionally, a methodology for measuring the percentage land use surrounding ponds was developed. **Chapter 2** demonstrated that both tadpole and adult frog mass, tadpole length, and adult male nuptial pad length were altered by different land use types around ponds, and differences in water quality between ponds. For example, in adults, mass and nuptial pad length both increased with increased levels ‘urban fabric’, ‘green urban’, and ‘arable land’ surrounding ponds, and were negatively correlated with ‘industrial urban’ and ‘pastures’. Although levels of androgenic activity could not be measured in the ponds increased areas of urbanisation and agriculture can lead to contamination of ecosystems with chemical pollutants, could potentially be eliciting endocrine disrupting effects on *R. temporaria* at these sites (Wyk, Pool and Leslie, 2003; Jackson and Sutton, 2008; Dabrowski, 2015; Dittrich *et al.*, 2018). However, the water quality parameters measured were related to different morphometric measurements in different ways which made the data harder to interpret. For example, increased water temperature was correlated with increased mass, but a reduced nuptial pad length and colour. As mass and nuptial pad characteristics are both under androgenic control, it would be expected that any changes to these parameters would occur in the same direction as they are under the same hormonal control (Burger and Nel, 2008, Orton *et al.*, 2014, Orton *et al.*, 2023). Water quality of ponds is very complex and poorly understood. More regular monitoring along with a better understanding of pond water chemistry and how it interacts with amphibians in the presence of chemical pollutants is needed for clearer interpretation of these data (Biggs and Williams, 2024). In combination, these results may suggest that land use is perhaps a better, more consistent measure of a particular site’s endocrine disrupting potential.

For this Ph.D. project, instead of measuring concentrations of particular chemical pollutants from the environment, the focus was on measuring the particular effects that environmental factors were having on *R. temporaria*. The effects of chemical pollutants vary depending on many factors such as bioavailability, temperature, other chemical interactions, and water chemistry, and so determining the exact effect of a particular concentration of a chemical in the natural environment is very difficult, and poorly understood (Arenas-Sánchez, Rico and

Vighi, 2016; Posthuma *et al.*, 2020; Biggs and Williams, 2024). Another original aim of this thesis was to develop and optimise an amphibian androgen receptor assay using transfected HepG2 cells, in order to determine androgenic/anti-androgenic activity of *R. temporaria* pond water samples from **Chapter 2**, indicated through luminescence of the cells. This assay could not be optimised within the scope of this Ph.D. project, and so a different assay using a human androgen receptor via MDA-kb2 cells was trialled to achieve the same outcomes, however this assay also could not be optimised. Results from this work can be found in **Appendix 2.4**. Further work into utilising these assays to analyse the potential endocrine disrupting effects related to pond water could provide valuable baseline data for the androgenic/anti-androgenic potential of amphibian breeding ponds.

Chapter 2 data were collected at one specific time point with tadpoles sampled destructively for use in **Chapter 3**. As the same samples were utilised between **Chapter 2** and **Chapter 3**, the land use and water quality pond characteristics of the ponds were compared to the results from this Chapter. **Chapter 3** aimed to evaluate the use of existing destructive methods discussed within the literature for sexual determination and differentiation (see **Chapter 1**), by looking at the gonad morphology (via histology) and gene expression of *R. temporaria* gonads. These are methods that have previously been used in amphibian studies, but have only been used in combination within lab studies (e.g. Orton *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, this was the first time that gonad morphology and gene expression have been combined to analyse wild amphibian samples. **Chapter 3** was also the only Chapter of this Ph.D. that utilised any destructive methods. Processes related to sexual differentiation and development in tadpoles are highly dependent upon the endocrine system, and so are sensitive to the effects of EDCs (Woodley, 2015).

The results from this Chapter did not identify any relationship between gonad morphology and expression of any of the genes investigated (*amh*, *cyp17*, *foxL2*, and *cyp19*). No intersex individuals could be identified from any of the histological samples analysed. Intersex individuals are found naturally within amphibian populations, although there is a lack of baseline data regarding how common intersex is within amphibian populations (Orton and Tyler, 2015). Low levels of intersex are therefore unlikely to cause concern for the health and fertility of populations (Orton and Tyler, 2015). Intersex is also found less often in adult frogs

compared to tadpoles, so monitoring of these intersex individuals through metamorphosis into metamorphs and beyond would be useful to understand the long term effects of the intersex condition, but this presents many challenges in wild studies and uses destructive methods. The sex ratio of tadpoles at these sites has also been reported, although this has been shown to vary between populations of *R. temporaria*, so interpretation of sex ratios that are not close to 100 % male or female, and therefore unlikely to affect fertility or breeding dynamics, is challenging (Pettersson and Berg, 2007; Alho, Matsuba and Merilä, 2010).

There was a small significant difference identified in *amh*, or anti-mullerian hormone, expression between two sites, Erik's Pond (a rural farmland pond near a nature reserve and golf course) and Glasgow University (an urban pond in a small area of green space in the centre of Glasgow). Visual inspection of the data shows a higher level of *amh* expression at Glasgow University, compared to Erik's Pond. In order to investigate this result further, the relationship between *amh* expression and environmental characteristics of these sites was explored. Four land use types were selected (Urban Fabric, Green Urban, Industrial Urban, and Pastures) that were commonly found surrounding amphibian breeding ponds, including Erik's Pond and Glasgow University, as well as water quality characteristics (pH, conductivity, and salinity) that were shown to affect tadpole morphometrics in **Chapter 2**. Linear regressions were carried out to determine if any of these factors were related to *amh* expression. There was only a weak relationship between levels of Urban Fabric surrounding a site, and levels of *amh* expression, which could potentially indicate that sites with higher levels of urbanisation (such as that found around Glasgow University) are exposed to endocrine disrupting activity that is increasing *amh* expression. Much more exploration into the endocrine disrupting potential of ponds and subsequent effects on gene expression is needed to further explore this hypothesis.

As identified in **Chapter 1**, here is a need for more longitudinal data collection from wild amphibians, to understand how exposure and morphology change over time (Biek *et al.*, 2002; Storfer, 2003). Therefore, **Chapter 4** expanded on **Chapter 2**, by looking at the effects of water chemistry and water quality on *R. temporaria* tadpole morphometrics, non-destructively, *in situ*, over time. This is the first study that looks at potential contaminant effects in wild tadpoles over time without the use of a cage. This methodology allows for

wild tadpoles to be repeatedly measured and compared between sites without the use of caging, or destructive methods, in a relatively cheap and inexpensive way. **Chapter 4** also provided crucial baseline information on element concentrations and water quality of *R. temporaria* breeding ponds over time in Scotland. The elements found in these ponds included both essential and non-essential metals, many of which have previously been demonstrated to have endocrine disrupting and/or toxic effects on anuran larvae. Mass and length of tadpoles were affected by different element concentrations and water quality parameters, as found in **Chapter 2**. Different developmental stages were shown to be affected by different elements and water quality parameters. For the two latest Gosner stage bands (36-40 and 41-46), both elements and water quality appeared to have a greater influence on tadpole morphology compared to the earlier stages, suggesting an increased sensitivity to different parameters as metamorphosis reaches its climax. Pond water chemistry clearly changed during tadpole development, and although different time points were sampled, a much larger dataset is needed to better understand these relationships. The comparison of different developmental stages across ponds (in comparison to **Chapter 2** where only one time point was measured) allows for more long term monitoring of ponds throughout the period of metamorphosis, which is highly controlled by the endocrine system, and so is vulnerable to endocrine disruption (Hill *et al.*, 2022; de Almeida and Freitas, 2024).

Limitations of thesis

The original plan for this thesis was to compare biomarker data collected from **Chapters 2, 3, and 4** to the results of the androgenic/anti-androgenic assay. This would have provided an understanding of the androgenic/anti-androgenic activity present in pond water and its effects on *R. temporaria*. The amphibian androgen receptor assay (using transfected HepG2 cells) was intended to provide a more ecologically-relevant alternative to the human androgen receptor assays (using stably transfected MDA-kb2 cells) that have previously been used in similar studies (Aït-Aïssa *et al.*, 2010; Blake *et al.*, 2010; Klopčič, Kolšek and Dolenc, 2015). Unfortunately, neither of the two assays could not be optimised within the time-frame of this Ph.D. Firstly, the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic meant that a planned research visit to the University of Tokyo for three months could not be carried out. This trip was to include training and assay optimisation of the amphibian androgen receptor assay, with research

partners at the University who had created the amphibian androgen receptor plasmid, and specialised in transfection of cells. This meant that the training in cell culture techniques and cell transfection had to take place at UWS, without all of the necessary equipment and expertise that would have increased chances for success. Although the amphibian androgen receptor assay could produce luminescence, there were inconsistent readings produced across different dilutions of the androgenic and anti-androgenic controls. Several different theories were explored as to why this may be the case, such as inconsistent cell seeding, human error, and contamination, but no obvious cause could be found. It was also hypothesised that there were issues with the luminometer producing incorrect readings, but as only one luminometer was available there was no way to conclusively assess this with another machine. I believe that the main cause of inconsistency comes from cells inconsistently taking up different plasmids, that produced different levels of *Renilla*/firefly luminescence, and so produced inconsistent results. The next step in investigating this would be the use of a FACS machine to determine which plasmids are taken up by different cells, but this technology was unavailable for use, and so it was decided to use the remaining time and resources on the human androgen receptor assay. The level of ethanol solvent used may also have been too high, as was found to be the case with the human androgen receptor assay.

More success was achieved using the human androgen receptor assay, with a more optimised standard curve showing a clear dose-response curve being achieved for one experiment. During this series of experiments, more alternative testing was carried out to determine the correct experimental parameters, such as the appropriate ethanol level for use, looking at MTT cell toxicity, and the potential for mycoplasma contamination. No mycoplasma contamination was found for either the MDA-kb2 cells, or the last passage of HepG2 cells that were used previously, so this is not believed to be a factor in the failure of the assays. There was also no evidence that the levels of MTT used were causing cell toxicity. It was identified however that the level of ethanol that was being used (1 %) was too high, and the appropriate level should have been 0.5 %. This may have been decreasing cell viability and producing inconsistencies in the luminescence results. However, as this was rectified, the luminescent reagent (steady-glo) was reaching the limit of its shelf stability, and had dropped in efficacy, so this was likely also a factor in the inconsistency of results. As neither assay could be optimised, there was no androgenic/anti-androgenic potential (or other endocrine potential measure) from the pond water that could be used to compare with results from other

Chapters. This meant that the potential for a pond to be contaminated was estimated using other indirect assumptions, such as the pond location, accounts from locals familiar with the area, and visual inspection of the ponds.

Despite *R. temporaria* being listed as Least Concern in Scotland by the latest IUCN Red List assessment, there was a consistent issue with finding *R. temporaria* breeding sites for study sampling with individuals present at high enough numbers (Foster *et al.*, 2021). Like most amphibians, *R. temporaria* ecology is not only affected by different environmental factors, but is also affected by a multitude of threats such as habitat loss, disease, and pollution (Foster *et al.*, 2021). Although their name implies they are a common species, a series of poor years for breeding and survival (as observed throughout this Ph.D. period and within the literature) combined with additional stressors could mean that this species is not as common as presumed, especially not in the numbers required for robust statistical analysis (Cooke and Arnold, 1982; Carrier and Beebee, 2003; Scott, Pithart and Adamson, 2008). It is possible that common frogs are able to detect and avoid polluted water bodies which could have contributed to their elusiveness during this Ph.D. programme.

Future directions

There are several areas of research identified throughout this thesis that could be explored further and expanded upon. Further research into combining differences in land use surrounding ponds, combined with water quality sampling for endocrine disruption would be useful to be able to use land use calculations from GIS as a non-destructive biomonitoring tool. It would also be of interest to look into how different land use percentages have changed over time compared with historic and present population data, to identify if any declines could be related to potential chemical pollution events.

Further study into the field of amphibian ecotoxicology in Scotland could combine analysis of different tadpole morphometric variables with water quality data, the land use GIS analysis from **Chapter 2**, with metal concentrations from ICP-OES analysis (as in **Chapter 4**) and/or androgenic/anti-androgenic activity (from an assay such as those attempted as part of this

thesis). This would require further statistical analysis comparing different Gosner stage bands across a much bigger subset of ponds to try and distinguish common patterns and better understand the complex relationships between water quality, endocrine disruption, and tadpole morphometrics. Collecting data regarding the mass of tadpoles and adults and nuptial pad morphometrics of the adult male frogs has promise as non-destructive biomonitoring tools for growth and development, and reproductive potential regarding EDC exposure. Pond water samples could be analysed using an assay similar to those attempted in **this thesis** on the water samples collected from the two sites from **Chapter 3** where *amh* expression was significantly different, and so could provide an insight about the endocrine disrupting potential of these ponds and whether this is the cause of changes in the expression of this gene. The water samples collected and processed for use in the androgenic/anti-androgenic assays have been stored for future analysis, so future results could be compared to the results from sites surveyed within this thesis.

Finally, research looking into how *R. temporaria* choose breeding ponds, to study potential avoidance of polluted breeding ponds is another potential avenue for future research. If *R. temporaria* are able to detect the presence of pollutants within ponds and selectively choose where to breed, their presence could be used as a biomonitoring tool for determining if ponds are polluted.

Conclusions

The interpretation of results from wild animal research can be difficult, as there are a multitude of factors such as genetics, climate, diet, and anthropogenic influences that could affect the results observed (Köhler and Triebkorn, 2013; Mateo, Lacorte and Taggart, 2016). However, wild studies are crucial within conservation research to produce more ecologically relevant results that better reflect the conditions experienced by the organisms targeted for conservation (Köhler and Triebkorn, 2013). Proper interpretation of the results of wild studies comes from having a good understanding of a species' ecology, so this, along with good baseline data, is a crucial factor in the success of using particular species for biomonitoring (Peterson *et al.*, 2017; Romero-Blanco and Alonso, 2022). While amphibian

lab studies are valuable and have their place in animal research, they are often over reliant on ‘model’ species such as *Xenopus* spp., and apply their findings to all species from that taxon as a result, despite sometimes vast differences in their biology and natural ecology (Hunter, 2008). *Rana temporaria* has been shown within this thesis to have potential as an effective non-model organism for chemical pollution exposure studies, and the results of these studies provide some novel approaches to carrying out this work non-destructively. *Rana temporaria* also has a more similar ecology to other anurans than *Xenopus* spp., and so results are more ecologically transferrable to other species (Cannatella and de Sá, 1993). Measuring morphometrics such as the mass of adults and tadpoles was identified as having the most potential as an effective biomonitoring tool for chemical contaminant exposure, but more data and longer term studies are needed to corroborate these findings. Tadpoles also showed more potential than adults for biomonitoring as they were easier to sample and find, and they are at a life stage where they are exposed to potentially polluted water bodies for an extended amount of time. The destructive methods utilised in this thesis were not deemed effective enough in this case to justify the sampling of individuals, but provided an important contrast between more traditional methods of data collection, and the novel methodologies trialled in this thesis.

Sub-lethal effects of chemical pollutants on amphibians can have devastating effects for recruitment and the overall fitness of populations, and as amphibians are important components of the food web as both predators and prey, their declines have implications for the wider ecosystem. More long-term baseline and subsequent trend data are key to understanding the potential effects of chemical pollutants on amphibian populations.

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Appendices

Appendix 1.1: Gosner stages of tadpole development

Figure I: Stages are according to Gosner (1960) and table is reproduced from Duellman and Trueb (1994). Stages 1 to 25 have been omitted as none of these stages are represented throughout this thesis. Printed with publisher's permission.

Appendix 2.1: Chapter 2 methodology for measuring nuptial pad size and colour using Adobe Photoshop

Measuring size of nuptial pad

- Open photoshop
- Open image and note image number, date, and frog ID number
- Zoom in to appropriate level so nuptial pad and scale are visible and clear
- Image
 - Analysis
 - Set measurement scale
 - Custom
- Icon should have changed to a ruler
- Use it to measure out a scale and note the pixel length shown. Change pixels to whatever measurement your scale is in (cm, mm etc) and click ok
- Use the line icon (under rectangle)
- Draw length of the nuptial pad and record the number given (number will disappear when you let go)
- Repeat three times and take an average
- Put into the equation: (length % pixels) x 1
- Record

Measuring colour of nuptial pad

- Open photoshop
- Open CR2 image and click 'open image' on 'Camera Raw'
- Note image number, date, site, and frog number
- Enlarge photo so nuptial pad is visible using the magnifying glass tool
- Use the magic wand tool to highlight the areas of the nuptial pad with the same colouration, cutting around the reflection and any other anomalies
 - You can alter the tolerance (20 ish works well but play around with it). Lower and adding more sections is easier than taking away
 - Use shift and click to add areas, and Alt and click to subtract from the magic wand tool
- Click on the histogram on the right-hand side and record the RGB mean, SD, average, and pixel number
 - Windows > histogram. Will appear on right hand side. Open expanded view, and set to RGB
- Once done all photos, go back and repeat all steps

- Find the coefficient of variation between the measurements – if there is a more than 10% discrepancy, then repeat again.

Appendix 2.2: Chapter 2 QGIS methodology

1. Prepare site data in an Excel file with Northing and Easting site location references in separate columns
2. Open QGIS
3. Set EPSG to Mercator 27700
4. Add Corine land use 2018 map as a layer.
5. Change the style by uploading the provided style file, and set its value to 'Code_18' indicating the different land cover classes (see **Figures II and III**).

Figure II: Original land use classifications and their associated map colours from the Corine 2018 UK land cover dataset.

Figure III: Map of the UK coloured according to the land use classifications from the Corine land cover dataset (see **Figure II**).

6. Upload spreadsheet of site data as a delimited text file layer, setting the X and Y coordinates to Northing and Easting to ensure the locations are overlaid in the correct place on the UK map
 - a. Points can be formatted
7. Add a vector layer of buffering around each of the points using the geoprocessing tool. Set buffer zone to 804.672m (0.5 miles) around each site.
 - a. Buffer zones can be formatted
8. Open the attribute table of the buffer layer

- a. Add a column labelled ID, and use the code *\$id* to assign a random number ID to each site
 - b. Add a column labelled Catch Area, and use code *\$area* to calculate the area of each buffer zone in m²
9. Intersect the buffer zones with the Corine land use map by using the intersection geoprocessing tool, and set the style according to step 5 (see **Figure IV**)

Figure IV: Three Scottish sites with a 0.5 mile buffer zone, demonstrating different land use cover.

10. Remove all other layers leaving only the intersected layer (see **Figure V**)

Figure V: The buffer zone of three Scottish sites intersected with the Corine land cover dataset.

11. Open the attribute table of the buffer layer
 - a. Add a column labelled Class Area, and use the code *\$Area* to calculate the area of each type of land use type within the buffer zone in m²
 - b. Add a column labelled Percentage and use the code $(\text{"ClassArea"} / \text{"CatchArea"}) * 100$ to calculate the percentage of each land use type within the 0.5 mile buffer zone of each site
12. Export attribute table to Excel for data clean up.

Appendix 2.3: Summary of Chapter 2 tadpole morphometrics by site

Tadpole Mass

Glasgow University

Ravenswood Bog

Endfield Avenue

Erik's Pond

Victoria Park

Craigmore

Figure VI: Mass of tadpoles from different sites in relation to their Gosner stage of development. N number is presented above each bar.

Tadpole Total Length

Glasgow University

Ravenswood Bog

Endfield Avenue

Langlands Gate

Erik's Pond

Victoria Park

Craigmore

Hunterstone

Figure VII: Total length of tadpoles from different sites in relation to their Gosner stage of development. N number is presented above each bar.

Tadpole Snout to Vent Length

Glasgow University

Ravenswood Bog

Endfield Avenue

Langlands Gate

Erik's Pond

Victoria Park

Craigmore

Hunterstone

Figure VIII: Snout to vent length of tadpoles from different sites in relation to their Gosner stage of development. N number is presented above each bar.

Tadpole Tail Length

Glasgow University

Ravenswood Bog

Endfield Avenue

Langlands Gate

Erik's Pond

Victoria Park

Craigmore

Hunterstone

Froggy Pond

Arcadia

Irvine

Laurieston

Figure IX: Tail length of tadpoles from different sites in relation to their Gosner stage of development. N number is presented above each bar.

Appendix 2.4: Method optimisation of cell-based luminescence transactivation assays for determining androgenic/anti-androgenic effects of *Rana temporaria* pond water

Introduction

Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are common pollutants that can be found in every environment, and can have negative consequences for both human and animal health, including amphibians (Robitaille *et al.*, 2022). As the actions of hormonal signals are so crucial in the development and maintenance of the reproductive system, exposure to endocrine disruptors can have negative consequences for amphibian reproductive health and development. For example, Cevalco *et al.* (2008) exposed juvenile *Xenopus laevis* to the known EDCs EE2, tamoxifen, methylidihydrotestosterone (MDHT), and flutamide at a concentration of 10^{-8} M, along with water from the river Lambro, a water source from northern Italy suspected to be contaminated with agricultural, domestic, and industrial waste. Following exposure, gonadal histopathology was carried out. Exposure to EE2 and water from the river Lambro in males resulted in a reduction in mean seminiferous tubule diameter, a breakdown of spermatogenic nests, and thickening of the interlobal walls. In both males and females, oocytes were found in the seminiferous tubules, which is an indicator of intersex characteristics. Exposure to tamoxifen and MDHT in females resulted in oocyte atresia, and the development of spermatogenic nests.

It is crucial that we are able to detect the presence of endocrine disrupting chemicals in nature, in order to be able to study and mitigate their effects. One way this can be achieved is through the use of cell-based luminescence assays to test either quantities of known chemicals, or to test samples collected from the environment (Robitaille *et al.*, 2022). Cell-based luminescent assays can be used to detect the presence of endocrine disrupting chemicals by utilising cells transfected with promoter regions encoding for hormone receptor production within the cell nucleus, along with a reporter gene promoter for production of chemiluminescence when this receptor is activated by a substance binding to the receptor. These cells can be introduced to test substances such as chemicals or water extracts, and

levels of luminescence detected using commercially purchased kits (Liu *et al.*, 2009). Thus cell-based luminescent assays represent a method of non-destructive biomonitoring. There are many types of luminescence assay that have been developed for this purpose, such as using human breast carcinoma cells (MDA-kb2) to determine anti(androgenic) and glucocorticoid responses (Ma *et al.*, 2003; Aït-Aïssa *et al.*, 2010) or the MELN assay using human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7) to determine anti(estrogenic), progesterone, and glucocorticoid responses (Berckmans *et al.*, 2007).

Cell-based luminescence assays have previously been used in lab studies (Ma *et al.*, 2003; Stoker *et al.*, 2005; Aït-Aïssa *et al.*, 2010; Blake *et al.*, 2010; Orton *et al.*, 2011, 2012; Orton *et al.*, 2014; Klopčič, Kolšek and Dolenc, 2015; Skledar *et al.*, 2019) and on unknown samples such as waste-water effluents (Ole Kusk *et al.*, 2011; Jones *et al.*, 2020; Stavreva *et al.*, 2021). Using these assays instead of, or in combination with measuring concentrations of contaminants allows us to infer the effects that exposure may have on a particular organism based on the endocrine disrupting nature measured by a particular assay. This allows more in-depth study than simply knowing what an organism has been exposed to and at what concentration. These cell-based luminescent assays can also be used in a tiered approach in combination with other biomonitoring techniques and morphological endpoints such as histology and dissection to determine the specific effects that these chemicals are having on an organism.

This Chapter focuses on the development of two cell-based luminescence assays that could be used to assess water samples collected from *Rana temporaria* breeding ponds for the presence of androgenic/anti-androgenic activity. As this Ph.D. was focused on *Rana temporaria*, an amphibian, it was determined that the development of an assay using the specific amphibian androgen receptor would produce the most accurate and ecologically relevant results indicating the androgenic/anti-androgenic effects of these water samples. Unfortunately, although several amphibian cell lines have been developed, very few are commercially available, mostly being found within the Frozen Zoos in San Diego (Strand *et al.*, 2022). Only one tissue reported is developed from the testes of the striped marsh frog (*Limnodynastes peronii*), an anuran from a different genus to our target species, and is not available for commercial purchase (Robinson and Stephenson, 1967; Strand *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the first assay attempted was the development of an amphibian androgen receptor assay using HepG2 cells (human hepatocellular carcinoma), which involved transfecting

human HepG2 cells with an amphibian androgen receptor plasmid developed by project partners from the University of Tokyo. The disadvantage of using this cell-based luminescence assay specific to amphibians, is that it has not been fully developed and researched. Therefore, a second cell-based luminescence assay was also attempted which uses the established MDA-kb2 assay with a human androgen receptor (Wilson, Bobseine and Lambright, 2002). This is a standardised cell-based luminescence assay. The human androgen receptor assay uses commercially available MDA-kb2 human breast cells, which are stably transfected with an androgen-responsive luciferase reporter plasmid driven by the MMTV promoter (Wilson, Bobseine and Lambright, 2002). The MDA-kb2 cell line was derived from the breast cancer cell line, MDA-MB-453 (see ATCC HTB-131) by stable transfection with a mouse mammary tumor virus (MMTV) luciferase-neo reporter gene construct. This cell line expresses firefly luciferase under control of the MMTV promoter that contains response elements for both glucocorticoid receptors (GR) and androgen receptors (AR).

Cell-based luminescence assay 1: Amphibian androgen receptor

The first assay was an amphibian androgen receptor assay using HepG2 cells (human hepatocellular carcinoma), which involved transfecting human HepG2 cells with an amphibian androgen receptor plasmid developed by project partners from the University of Tokyo. This plasmid contains a promoter for the amphibian androgen receptor derived from *Glandiana rugosa*, the Japanese wrinkled frog, as well as a promoter encoding for an ampicillin resistance gene allowing for amplification of this plasmid using *E.coli* colonies.

Creation of the amphibian AR plasmid

The creation of the amphibian AR plasmid was carried out prior to the Ph.D. by project partners from the University of Tokyo. Amphibian AR sequences were introduced into the mammalian expression vector plasmid pcDNA3.1(+) (commercially purchased from Promega, product code: V79020) with the restriction enzymes BamHI (commercially purchased from Takara Bio, product code: 1010BH) and XhoI (commercially purchased from

Takara Bio, product code: 1094BH). Insert and vector DNAs cut with BamHI and XhoI were extracted from gels (using the QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit from QIAGEN, product code: 28706X4) after gel electrophoresis. The insert and vector DNAs were then ligated using the DNA Ligation Kit (commercially purchased from Takara Bio, product code: 6023) and transformed into DH5a competent cells (commercially purchased from TOYOBO, product code: DNA-903F).

Below is the base pair sequence for the amphibian AR plasmid provided by colleagues at the University of Tokyo:

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1 GGATCCATGG AGGtGCACAT AGGGCTCGGT GGGGTATACA AGCAGCCTCC CGGGAAGATG
 61 ATCAGGGGCG CATTGAGAA CCTTCTCTG AGTGTGCGGG AAGCGCTGCA AGGGGAGCGT
121 AGAGCCCTAG AGGGGTCCA GCGGCGCGGA GCTTGGAGCG AACCCCAAG CACTCAGCGC
181 CCCCTGTCA CCTGGAGCGA AGCCTCTCCG CAAGAAGCAA CCCCTGAA CCCCTGGGTG
241 ACACACACCC CTGCCGTTG GAGAGAAGCA GAGGCAGCAG CACCCAGAG TCCCGCGGG
301 CGCACACAAG GAGCGCAATT CCCTGCGCTG GGAGACTGCC CCACTGAGCT CAAGGAGATC
361 CTGGGGGAGC AGAGCGGGG GATACTGGAG AGCGAAGAGC CCCCGCGGA CAAGGAAAGC
421 TTCCCGGAG CCCCCAAGG CATCTCCGAT AGCGCCAAGG AGCTGTGTAA AGCCGTGTCA
481 GTGTCCCTGG GGCTGAGCAT GGAGGCGCTG GAGCATCTGA GCGCAGGAGG GGAGGCGCAG
541 CAGAGAGGGG ACTGTATGTA CGCGGCGCCC CCCGCACACC CTCCGGACAC CCACAAGTGC
601 CAAGTGGCAG AGGAAGAGAA GAGCGACACC CGGGACGGGC CATTAGGAG GAGCAGCCAG
661 AACAACTTTC CAACTGGCAA GAGCCAGAT GATGGTAGCA GCGCAGGGGG CTCGGAGGAG
721 AAGGAGCAGC AGTGACAGA CTTGGCACTA CCGGAGCCAG CAGGGTACAG ACACCGAGCT
781 ATGGAGCTCA CGCCTAGCCT CACCCTGTAC AAGCCCACCG CCTTCATGGA GGAGAGCCCT
841 GGCTATCCTG CCAGAGACTT TTACAGCTT CAGATGGCCC TGGCACCCA TGGCCGATA
901 AAGGTGGAGA GCCCATGGA GTACGGTGGC AGCGCTTGGG GGGCAGCGGG CAGGTACAGC
961 GAACTGTCAG GCTTGCCCA TTGTGGTGCC ACCGCCAGCT GGCACCTCTCT GTTTGAGGAA
1021 GGCAGGCCA GCGGCTCGTT TGCAGAGGCC GGCCCTTACA GCTACCCTCG CAGCCATGGA
1081 CCTGCGGGAC CCGATGGGGA ATTTCCCTCT GACGCCTGGT ACCCAGCACC AACCATGATA
1141 GGCAGGGTGC CCTATGGTGG GCCTATGAAAG GCTGAGATGG GACCTTGGAT GGAAGGATAC
1201 CCTGGAGCCT TTGGGAAAT GAGGCTAGAA GGAGGCAGAG ATCACCTGCT GCCCATTGAT
1261 TATTACTTCC CACCGAAAA AACCTGTCTG ATCTGTGGAG ATGAGGCTTC TGGCTGCCAC
1321 TATGGGGCCC TGACGTGTGG CAGCTGCAA GTCTTCTTTA AGAGAGCAGC TGAAGGGAAA
1381 CAAAAGTATC TTTGCGCCAG CAGAAATGAC TGCACAATTG ACAAGTCCG GAGGAAAAAC
1441 TGCCATCTT GCCGCTTGC GAAATGTTAT GAGGCTGAA TGACATTAGG AGCTCGTAAG
1501 CTAAAGAAGC TGGGGAACCT TAAGGCACAG GAAGAGTTGG AGGGATCTCC AGTGCAAGGT
1561 GAAGGAAGCA AAGACCTGGC CCCTGGTATG GGTATTCCAC AGCTTGAGGG CTACAGCTGC
1621 CAGCCTATCT TCCTGAATGT GCTGGAGGCC ATTGAACCTG TTGTGGTGTG TGCTGGGCAT
1681 GACAACAACC AACAGACAG CTTTGCTTTG CTCTTGAGCA GCCTAACGA GCTGGGTGAA
1741 AGGCAGCTTG TGCACGTCGT AAAGTGGGCA AAGGCTTTGC CAGGTTCCG AAATCTACAT
1801 GTAAGCGACC AAATGACTGT TATCAGTAC TCCTGGATGG GACTCATGAT ATTTGCCATG
1861 GGTTGGAGGT CATTCAAAA CGTCAACTCC AGGATGCTCT ATTTGCCCC GGACCTGGTG
1921 TTTAATGAGT ATCGCATGCA CAAGTCACGT ATGTACAGTC AGTGTGTCG GCTCCGACAC
1981 CTCTCCAGG AGTTTGGCTG GCTCCAGATC ACTCCGAGG AGTTCCTCTG CATGAAGCT
2041 CTCCTTCTCT TTAGCATTAT TCCTGTGAA GGTCTGAAGG ACCAGAAGTG CTTTGATGAA

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2101 TTGCGGATGA ATTATATCAA AGAGCTGGAC AGAGTCATCT CATGCAAGAG GAACAATCCA
2161 GCATCCAGCT CTAGACGCTT TTTCCAGCTC ACTAAGCTCC TGGATTCCGT GCAGCCGATT
2221 GCCCGGGAGC TCCACCAGTT CACATTTGAC CTGTTTGTGA AGGCCAGAT GGTGAGCGTG
2281 GATTTTCCCG AAATGATGTC AGAGATCATA TCCGTGCAGG TGCCCAAGAT CCTGTCTGGC
2341 AGAGTCAAGC CACTCTACTT CCACAGCTCa TGaCTCGAG.

The sequences for the primers used for cloning were as follows (underlined areas indicate BamHI and XhoI sites):

XtAR-Forward sequence: 5'-GGATCCCATGGAGGTGCACATAGGGCTC-3'

XtAR-Reverse sequence: 5'-CTCGAGTCATGAGCTGTGGAAGTAGAGTGG-3'

The amphibian plasmid was then shipped to UWS to be used alongside two other commercially available plasmids in development of the assay.

Other plasmids

This assay also required the transfection of two additional commercially available plasmids in order to provide the luminescent signal. The luminescence measured by cell-based assays is produced by firefly and *Renilla* luciferase encoding gene(s) expressed within the cells (according to how much androgen receptor binding there is) producing luciferase enzyme. This assay used the Dual-Glo luciferase assay kit from Promega (product code: E2920). The luciferin present in the first assay reagent, along with ATP (adenosine triphosphate) and molecular oxygen, reacts with the luciferase produced in varying quantities by the cell (along with Mg²⁺ provided by the cell culture media) and produces oxyluciferin, AMP (adenosine monophosphate), PPi (inorganic phosphate), CO₂, and light (which will vary according to the amount of luciferase involved in the reaction) (see **Figure X**). One photon of light is produced per mole of oxidised luciferase, and this is quantified by a luminometer to assess the degree of androgenic/anti-androgenic activity present. The luciferase expression is provided by the transfection of the MMTV-luc plasmid from Promega (product code: E1360, Genbank accession number: FJ773214) which is derived from a mouse mammary tumour virus. This plasmid acts as an androgen response viral promoter containing the promoter region encoding for luciferin transcription that will react with the firefly enzyme luciferase in

the Dual-Glo luciferase assay reagent (see **Figure XI**). The luciferase gene used is derived from *Photinus pyralis* (common eastern firefly).

Figure X: A schematic diagram showing the chemical reaction occurring with the use of the Promega Dual-Glo luciferase assay kit which provides beetle luciferin as a substrate for firefly luciferase (produced by the cells in response to androgen receptor binding) and coelenterazine (a coelenterate luciferin) as a substrate for *Renilla* luciferase (produced by all cells). Firefly luciferase emits green-yellow light at a wavelength of 550-570 nm. Diagram taken from the Promega Dual-Glo luciferase assay technical manual (Promega, 2023a).

Figure XI: A plasmid map of the MMTV-luc plasmid. The luciferase promoter region (*luc2P*) is shown in orange. Image taken from Promega website (Promega, 2023b).

The second plasmid used in this assay is the pRL-tk from Promega (product code: E2241, Genbank accession number: AF025844) which utilises *Renilla* luciferase derived from *Renilla reniformis* (sea pansy) (see **Figure XII**). *Renilla* luciferase emits blue light at a wavelength of 480-500 nm.

Figure XII: A plasmid map of the pRL-tk plasmid, the *Renilla* luciferase promoter (*Rluc*) is shown in light grey. Image taken from Promega website (Promega, 2023c).

The coelenterazine reagent from the Stop-and-Glo buffer from the Dual-Glo luciferase assay kit is broken down into coelenteramide by *Renilla* luciferase produced by the cells in the assay, producing luminescence as a by-product. This reaction quenches the firefly reaction, as well as acting as a control for cell number. Expression of *Renilla* luciferase by cells within the assay provides an internal control value to which expression of the experimental firefly luciferase reporter gene may be normalised, as it can also be used as a crude measure of cell count. The HSV-thymidine kinase promoter (TK) was chosen as the promoter for this plasmid as it is relatively weak in its expression of *Renilla* luciferase, and so is useful in providing a neutral constitutive expression of the *Renilla* luciferase as a control reporter.

This amphibian-specific cell-based luminescence assay works on the basis that, providing transfection of the cells is successful and all three plasmids are incorporated into the cell, the luciferase is produced within the cell when the androgen receptor is activated by addition of an androgen or anti/androgen. The more androgen present, the more luciferase is expressed, which produces a higher level of luminescence. All samples are run by themselves, and also

with an anti-androgen (flutamide) which will block androgens from binding to the androgen receptor and so will test for the presence of androgens in the sample. Therefore, samples with unknown androgenic activity could be tested using this assay, for example water from ponds sampled in **Chapter 2**.

Cell-based luminescence assay 2: Human androgen receptor

The background chemistry to this assay (see **Figure XIII**) is the same as the first reaction between luciferase (produced by the cells in response to androgenic/antiandrogenic activation) and luciferin provided by the Steady-Glo luciferase assay kit (commercially purchased from Promega, product code: E2510). There is no *Renilla* reaction within this protocol, and the MDA-kb2 cells are stably transfected so no transfection protocol is needed.

Figure XIII: A schematic diagram showing the chemical reaction occurring with the use of the Promega Steady-Glo luciferase assay kit which provides beetle luciferin as a substrate for firefly luciferase (produced by the cells in response to androgen receptor binding). Diagram taken from the Promega Dual-Glo luciferase assay technical manual (Promega, 2023d).

Once either of the cell-based luminescence assays had been successfully optimised, the aim of this Chapter was to determine the level of androgenic/anti-androgenic activity from some of the *Rana temporaria* natal water sites sampled in **Chapter 2**. This would allow investigation into possible associations with other biomarkers investigated within this thesis, such as development of both adults and tadpoles (**Chapter 2**), and tadpole gene expression and gonad morphology (**Chapter 3**). Further information on how water samples from **Chapter 2** were processed for cell exposure can be found in **Appendix 2.6**.

Methodology: Amphibian androgen receptor assay

Assay transfection components

As described above, this assay comprises HepG2 cells transfected with three different plasmids; one with the amphibian androgen receptor, one with the firefly luciferase promoter (MMTV-luc), and one with the *Renilla* luciferase promoter (pRL-tk). These plasmids need to be taken up into the cell using a transfection reagent. The transfection reagent used was FuGENE HD (Promega, product code: E2311) which breaks down cell membranes and allows plasmids to enter and be incorporated into the cell nucleus in order to transcribe the necessary proteins (amphibian AR, firefly luciferase, and *Renilla* luciferase).

Amplification of amphibian AR plasmid

In order to amplify the amphibian AR receptor plasmid, immunocompromised DH5 α *E. coli* cells were firstly temperature shocked to force uptake of the plasmid (see **Figure XIV**). The plasmid was added to an *E. coli* suspension in 10 ml LB media, put on ice for 30 min, heated to 42°C for 1 min, and placed on ice again for 2 min. 5 ml more LB media was then added and the suspension incubated (37°C, 1 h), and then plated on agar plates inoculated with ampicillin and grown overnight at 37°C. A control ampicillin-inoculated plate was used to check for growth of *E. coli* cells without the plasmid; the plasmid contains an ampicillin resistance gene, so only bacteria that have taken up the plasmid will survive. *E. coli* colonies were scraped off the plates following overnight incubation and added to 2-5 ml of ampicillin-inoculated LB media and incubated for 8 h at 37°C with vigorous shaking (~ 300 rpm). Bacterial cells were then harvested by centrifugation (6000 g, 15 min, 4°C). The plasmid was then extracted using a Qiagen plasmid mini kit according to the kit instructions, resuspended in TE buffer, and stored at -80°C. This was completed successfully with high DNA yields of 112-250 μ g.

Figure XIV: A diagram demonstrating the process of amplifying the amphibian AR plasmid using *E. coli*. Image created using Biorender.

Maintenance and passaging of HepG2 cells

HepG2 cells were purchased commercially from ATCC (product number: HB-8065) and thawed slowly at 37°C. The freezing media from shipping was removed, and the cells resuspended in complete growth media and plated in a 25 cm³ cell culture flask (see **Figure XV**). Complete growth media consisted of Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM, R&D Systems, product code: M12850), supplemented with 10 % unstripped foetal bovine serum (FBS), and 5 % penicillin/streptomycin to help prevent infection. The DMEM used contained low glucose, and was supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine and sodium pyruvate. The DMEM also contained no phenol red indicator, which is used in cell culture to indicate when a media change is required, as this indicator can interfere with the androgen receptor response of the assay (Ermler, Scholze and Kortenkamp, 2010). The use of unstripped FBS for growing the cells ensures that growth hormones needed for the cells to divide and multiply are present, but for running the assay, the FBS was swapped for FBS stripped using charcoal dextran to remove these growth hormones that may interfere with the androgen receptor response.

Cells were kept in sterile conditions (see **Figure XVI**) in vented cell culture flasks at 37°C supplemented with 5 % CO₂. Once cells settled and became confluent (**Figure XVII**), cells were passaged and transferred to a 75 cm³ cell culture flask (Nunc™ EasYFlask™ Cell Culture Flasks, ThermoFisher, product code: 156499). To passage the cells, every 3-4 days (or when needed), media was removed and placed in a sterile falcon tube, cells were washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Sigma Aldrich, product code: D8537) to remove any media remaining and this was added to the falcon tube. 5 ml Trypsin/EDTA (Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) (Thermo scientific, product code: 15400054) was then added to cover the bottom of the flask, which was incubated at 37°C for 5 min. The Trypsin/EDTA mixture was then added to the falcon tube which was then centrifuged to produce a cell pellet. The cells were then resuspended in fresh media, plated in fresh flasks, and returned to 37°C. Cells were also counted at this stage to ensure even seeding densities in flasks. Usually one media change (cells remain adherent to the flask and the used media is refreshed) and one passage (once the cells have reached a certain degree of confluence, usually around 80 %, using trypsinisation to lift the adherent cells off the flask so that they can be split between flasks and allow further growth) was carried out per week. The need for this was assessed by visual examination of the cells under the microscope. The passage number was recorded and written on each flask.

Figure XV: A diagram demonstrating the process of switching the unstripped media of the Hep-G2 cells to stripped media 24 h before plating. Image created using Biorender.

Figure XVI: A diagram demonstrating the process of aseptic technique used to grow the HepG2 cells while also preventing contamination. Image created using Biorender.

Figure XVII: HepG2 cells in culture at low confluence at x400 magnification. Cells are approximately 10-20 μm in length (Arzumanian, Kiseleva and Poverennaya, 2021). Image credit: Catherine Whatley. Image taken using the EVOS M5000 Imaging System.

Assay methodology

All methodologies were done under sterile conditions using aseptic techniques, with the exception of adding the assay reagents, as these kill the cells regardless. Once cells had reached an appropriate density (approximately 60-80 % confluence) and were in good health, they were counted and seeded onto a white, sterile 96 well plate at a density of 1.5×10^4 in 160 μl of complete growth medium per well (see **Figure XVIII**). At this stage the media was switched to stripped FBS, as any growth hormones present in unstripped FBS would influence the assay results. Cells were then incubated for 24 h at 37°C . It was important to make sure there were media wells on each side of the experimental wells to prevent evaporative loss.

Figure XVIII: Process of passaging and plating the cells ready to be used in the assay. At both edges of the experimental wells, wells containing just media were added to prevent evaporative loss from the experimental wells that may alter results. Image created using Biorender.

After 24 h incubation, cells were transfected with both the androgen receptor plasmid, and the firefly and *Renilla* luciferase plasmids using the transfection reagent FuGENE HD, as well as DMEM media (without any FBS added) (see **Figure XIX**). **Table 3.1** shows the reagent proportions mixed in a sterile Eppendorf tube, and then incubated at room temperature for 15 min. The reagent mixture (20 μl per well) was then added to the plate, mixed gently, and returned to the incubator for 4 h.

Table I: Table showing the correct dilutions of the receptor plasmids to be used in this assay, the correct reagent proportions, as well as the final concentration of different reagents per assay well. Please note that this is the original starting protocol, and some optimisation experiments alter these proportions/concentrations as part of the optimisation process. This table outlines the proportions of reagents needed to create enough plasmid/FuGENE mixture to produce a full assay plate at 20 μl per well. These proportions could then be altered to fill the volume of wells needed for each assay.

Reagent	Concentration of reagent	Reagent proportions needed for a full plate at 20 μl per well as an example)	Final Conc. ($\mu\text{g}/\text{well}$)
Amplified androgen receptor	(0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ in media)	20 μl	0.04
MMTV Luc (<i>firefly luciferase plasmid</i>)	(0.4 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ in media)	20 μl	0.08
pRL-tk (<i>Renilla luciferase plasmid</i>)	(0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ in media)	20 μl	0.02
FuGENE HD (<i>transfection reagent</i>)		42 μl	0.42
Media (without serum)		1.95 ml	

After 4 h, 20 μl of unknown samples to be tested (or MTT or flutamide as an androgen and an anti-androgen control, respectively) were suspended in a solvent vehicle (ethanol) and added to the media already in the well (180 μl) and incubated for 44 h at 37°C (see **Figure XIX**).

Figure XIX: Diagram demonstrating the process of making the transfection mixture, adding to the HepG2 cells and incubating for 4 h, and then adding samples along with controls and incubating for 44 h. Image created using Biorender.

After 44 h of incubation, plates were removed from the incubator and 285 µl of media discarded, leaving 75 µl in each well. To this 75 µl of Dual-Glo® luciferase assay reagent was added. The plate was then shaken in the dark (400 rpm, 10 min; room temperature) and the plate read in the luminometer (Thermofisher Varioskan Lux). Then 75 µl of Dual-Glo Stop & Glo reagent was added to each well, and the plate shaken again for 10 min as before. The plate was then read again (see **Figure XX**).

Figure XX: Process of adding the assay reagents, shaking the plates, and reading the assay results on the luminometer. Image created using Biorender.

The activity of the assay was calculated by the ratio of firefly to *Renilla* activity. Each sample was run using this assay three times, and an average luminescence result was recorded.

Testing the use of the luminometer

Prior to assay optimisation, the functioning of the luminometer used for the assay (BioTek Synergy HT) was tested using the Promega QuantiLum Recombinant Luciferase (product code: E1701) which is a concentrate of firefly luciferase (10–15 mg/ml). The Quantilum luciferase was diluted 1000-fold in complete growth media, and then 10X dilutions with complete growth media were made in a 96 well white luminometer plate. An equal volume (100 μ l) of Dual-Glo luminescence assay reagent was added and the plates were read using the luminometer (see **Figure XXI**). Results showed a high level of luminescence produced which reduced as the concentration of QuantiLum decreased, demonstrating that the luminometer was functional.

Figure XXI: Results from the QuantiLum positive control experiment. Seven 10X dilutions were plated from rows 1-7. Error bars show standard error (n=3). Control wells consist of media without QuantiLum reagent.

Assay optimisation

Once the cells had been transfected with the plasmids and the luminometer was working, the assay needed to be optimised by producing a dose response curve using an androgen (methyltestosterone or MTT) and an anti-androgen (flutamide) as controls to test the sensitivity of the assay, and to determine the 60 % level to combine with the pond water samples in the assay. This is used as a standardised comparison both across future plates tested using the assay, as well as between studies. What follows is a series of optimisation experiments.

Optimisation experiment one

This experiment was carried out using the original protocol provided by colleagues from the University of Tokyo. Concentrations of MTT ranging from 160 nm to 1.25 nm per well were plated, along with a vehicle (1% ethanol) and media controls, and empty cells with nothing inside. The luminometer settings were an integration time (the time between well readings) of

1 s and the gain (the sensitivity of the probe) was set to 135. However, there was no dose response from the cells regarding different levels of androgen (MTT) added, and no difference compared to the control wells or the empty plate wells (see **Table II**). As there was no activity detected between wells, and luminescence results were expected to be much higher than those recorded, the *Renilla* value was not measured to preserve reagents. It was hypothesised that perhaps the luminometer settings were wrong, and therefore needed further optimisation.

Table II: Table illustrating the average ($n=3$) luminescence response from each well type, along with the standard error. There is no dose response of luminescence as expected from the cells, and there is little difference in luminescence response between control wells, sample wells, and empty plate.

Well contents (MTT concentrations in nM)	Average luminescence response	Standard Error
Media	136	9.88
Vehicle	130	15.35
160	117	31.07
80	141.67	13.86
40	148.67	21.40
20	114.67	2.67
10	139.67	21.40
5	117.33	35.03
2.5	134.33	11.39
1.25	121.67	25.30
Empty wells	119.02	5.82

Optimisation experiment two

For this experiment, experimental parameters were carried out as for optimisation experiment one, but the luminometer settings were adjusted to increase the integration time to 5 s, and the gain to 200. Again, there was no clear response from the cells regarding different levels of androgen (MTT) added, but there was some luminescence produced suggesting that a limited number of cells were being transfected successfully. There was still little difference between the luminescence from the MTT cells compared to the control wells or the empty plate wells. The *Renilla* value was again not measured to preserve reagents. Although there was a higher level of luminescence compared to the control wells, and the overall levels of luminescence were higher, there was still no clear dose response. The change to luminometer settings likely improved the results (see **Table III**), but optimisation in other areas was still needed.

Table III: Table illustrating the average ($n=3$) luminescence response from each well type, along with the standard error.

Well contents (MTT concentrations in nM)	Average luminescence response	Standard Error
Media	2475.8	817.67
Vehicle	4481	748.01
160	10271.67	5442.99
80	7894	1873.39
40	3621.33	913.95
20	6183.33	2262.55
10	8776.33	6573.31
5	9829	4301.12
2.5	9012	3696.97
1.25	3805.33	1765.50
Empty wells	1659.88	316.12

Optimisation experiment three

Optimisation experiment three was the same as experiment two but in addition, a row of wells with flutamide concentrations ranging from 10 μ M to 7.8 nM, in combination with 20 nM of MTT was added, estimated to be at the 60 % level. An additional row of MTT at 20 nM was also plated as replicates. The luminometer settings were set to an integration time of 5 s, and the gain to 200. Again, there was no dose response of luminescence as expected from the cells for MTT or flutamide, and there was little difference in luminescence response between control wells and sample wells (see **Table IV**). There was no improvement from the previous optimisation experiments.

Table IV: Table illustrating the average ($n=3$) luminescence response from each well type, along with the standard error. Values shown are the ratio of the firefly luminescence to the *Renilla* luminescence.

	Well contents	Average	Standard Error
Controls	Media	0.55	0.18
	Control	0.92	0.02
MTT	160 nM	0.89	0.23
	80 nM	1.55	0.51
	40 nM	0.68	0.3
	20 nM	0.64	0.15
	10 nM	0.64	0.14
	5 nM	0.91	0.21
	2.5 nM	1.25	0.34
	1.25 nM	0.94	0.27
Flutamide	10 μ M	1.13	-
	5 μ M	0.84	-
	2.5 μ M	0.41	-
	1.25 μ M	2.47	-
	625 nM	0.99	-
	312.5 nM	0.69	-
	156.25 nM	2.87	-
	7.8 nM	0.55	-

Optimisation experiment four

In this experiment the transfection protocol was altered to optimise the protocol and improve results in order to achieve a dose response curve. Three different levels of HepG2 cells were seeded in each well (1.5×10^4 – the original protocol level, 2×10^4 and 2.5×10^4). Three levels of the FuGENE HD transfection reagent were also tested (see **Table V**: 5.25 μl – the original protocol level, 10.5 μl and 21 μl per well). Finally, three different levels of the amphibian AR were tested (5 μl – the original protocol level, 10 μl and 20 μl per well). Nine different reaction mixtures were made and tested against concentrations of MTT ranging from 160 nM to 2.5 nM, and the three cell seeding levels along with vehicle and media controls, and empty cells with nothing inside. Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results. Then the ratio of firefly: *Renilla* luminescence values was taken, and results plotted (see **Figure 3.13**).

Table V: The composition of the different transfection mixtures used in optimisation experiment four. Nine different transfection mixtures were created with differing levels of androgen receptor and FuGENE HD transfection reagent. The amount of media was adjusted to allow the same final volume of these mixtures.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Amplified androgen receptor plasmid (μl) (diluted in media to 0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	2.5	2.5	2.5	5	5	5	10	10	10
MMTV plasmid (μl) (diluted in media to 0.4 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
pRL-tk plasmid (μl) (diluted in media to 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
FuGENE HD (μl)	5.25	10.5	21	5.25	10.5	21	5.25	10.5	21
Media (no serum) (μl)	231	225.75	215.25	228.5	223.25	212.75	223.5	218.25	207.75

Results

Figure XXII: Luminescence ratio results from optimisation experiment four transfection mixtures 1-9, as shown in Table V. Seeding density of cells at 1.5×10^4 is shown in blue, 2×10^4 is shown in orange, and 2.5×10^4 is shown in grey. Values shown are the ratio of the firefly luminescence to the *Renilla* luminescence.

There was little consistency between the different transfection mixtures used (see **Figure XXII**), with no clear luminescence dose response as would be expected from a high concentration of MTT to a low concentration. There was also little difference between different cell seeding densities, androgen receptor levels, or FuGENE HD. It was hypothesised that the level of FuGENE was too high and was inducing a toxic effect within the cells, and potentially the signal from the androgen receptor was too high and so interfered with the luminescent signal. There was also potential for the TE (Tris-EDTA) buffer that the AR was stored in to produce a toxic effect in the cells.

Optimisation experiment five

In this experiment the transfection protocol was again altered to optimise the protocol and improve results in order to achieve a dose response curve. Two different levels of HepG2 cells were seeded in each well (1.5×10^4 – the original protocol level, and 2×10^4). The lowest level of the FuGENE HD transfection reagent was used (5.25 μ l – the original protocol level) as well as two different levels of the amphibian AR following dilution were tested (5 μ l – the original protocol level, and 10 μ l) (see **Table VI**). The MTT dilutions from the last experiment were expanded in range from 160 nM to 0.4 nM, and the dilutions from the previous experiment were tested against fresh dilutions to see if there was an error in preparing the dilutions. Vehicle and media controls were plated, along with empty cells with nothing inside. This was also the first experiment where plates were made in duplicate to account for edge effects. Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results. Then the ratio of firefly to *Renilla* values was taken and results plotted.

Transfection mixtures

Table VI: The composition of the different transfection mixtures used in optimisation experiment five. Four different transfection mixtures were created with differing levels of androgen receptor and FuGENE HD transfection reagent. The amount of media was adjusted to allow the same final volume of these mixtures.

	1	2	3	4
Amplified androgen receptor plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.2 µg/µl)	3.2	3.2	6.6	6.6
MMTV plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.4 µg/µl)	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.2
pRL-tk plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.1 µg/µl)	3.2	3.2	3.2	3.2
FuGENE HD (µl)	7	7	7	7
Media (no serum) (µl)	640	640	636.8	636.8

Results

Figure XXIII: Luminescence results from optimisation experiment five transfection mixtures 1-4, as shown in **Table VII**. Mixture one is shown in blue, mixture 2 is shown in dark purple, three is shown in red, and four is shown in green. Controls are shown in light purple. Shown are plates in duplicate at two cell seeding densities: Plate 1 at 1.5×10^4 (**A**) and Plate 2 at 1.5×10^4 (**B**), and Plate 1 at 2×10^4 (**C**) and Plate 2 at 2×10^4 (**D**). Values shown are the ratio of the firefly luminescence to the *Renilla* luminescence.

Some curves shown on the graphs in **Figure XXIII** were more indicative of a dose-response curve (for example, transfection mixture 1 on plate 1: 1.5×10^4 , shown in blue, see **Figure XXIII**). However, the results were still very inconsistent. There was also considerable difference between the two plates (results would be expected to be near identical).

Optimisation experiment six

Following discussion with the Japanese project partners as to how results could be improved to achieve a dose-response curve, it was suggested that the concentrations of MTT being used

were too high, and the cell seeding of the plates potentially uneven, leading to *Renilla* values that were inconsistent between wells. The cell culture protocol was modified to trypsinise the cells more gently and allow more trypsin/EDTA contact time to reduce clumping of the cells. The centrifugation time was lowered to make the pellet easier to break up, and pipetting of the pellet increased to thoroughly resuspend and prevent clumps that would make the cell count more uneven. In this experiment, MTT values were reduced to a range of 40 nM to 4 fM, but the MTT dilutions from the last study (mixtures 1 and 2) were tested against new dilutions (3 and 4) to see if there was an error in creating the dilutions. Two concentrations of the AR were used (2.5 µl and 5 µl per reaction) (see **Table VII**, and the cell seeding density was unchanged at 1.5×10^4). Plates were made in duplicate to account for edge effects. Results are plotted in **Figure XXIV**.

Transfection mixtures

Table VII: The composition of the different transfection mixtures used in optimisation experiment six and seven. Four different transfection mixtures were created with two different levels of androgen receptor. The amount of media was adjusted to allow the same final volume of these mixtures.

	1	2	3	4
Amplified androgen receptor plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.2 µg/µl)	4.2	4.2	8.4	8.4
MMTV plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.4 µg/µl)	8.4	8.4	8.4	8.4
pRL-tk plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.1 µg/µl)	8.4	8.4	8.4	8.4
FuGENE HD (µl)	17.64	17.64	17.64	17.64
Media (no serum) (µl)	823.2	823.2	819	819

Results

Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results. Then the ratio of firefly to *Renilla* values was taken and results plotted.

Figure XXIV: Luminescence results from (A) plate 1 and (B) plate 2 using optimisation experiment six transfection mixtures 1-4, as shown in **Table VII**. Mixture one is shown in blue, mixture two is shown in green, three is shown in orange, and four is shown in red. Controls are shown in purple. Values shown are the ratio of the firefly luminescence to the *Renilla* luminescence.

The results were still very inconsistent. There was a considerable difference between the two plates when the results would have been expected to be near identical. The results also

showed no clear dose response, and overall luminescence was at very low levels compared to previous experiments, with the exception of one value.

Optimisation experiment seven

In order to add the assay reagents, first some of the cell media from the wells was removed, as an equal amount of assay reagents to media is required. This optimisation experiment was a repeat of the previous experiment, except the media removed from the plates was added to a separate plate and read to determine if there were cells present that had not adhered to the plate that may have been causing variation in the luminescence values. In addition, plate 1 was plated by F. Orton, and plate 2 was plated by C. Whatley, in order to rule out human pipetting error in the results. Results are plotted in **Figure XXV**.

Results

Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results. Then the ratio of firefly to *Renilla* values was taken and results plotted.

Figure XXV: Luminescence results from optimisation experiment seven pipetted by C. Whatley (A), F. Orton (B), and (C) results with removed media from the C. Whatley plate (red) and the F. Orton plate (blue). Values shown are the ratio of the firefly luminescence to the *Renilla* luminescence. In panels (A) and (B), old MTT dilutions are shown in blue and green (1 and 2, respectively) and new MTT dilutions are shown in orange and red (3 and 4, respectively). Controls are shown in purple. Transfection mixtures 1-4 also correspond to those shown in Table 7.

There was still no consistency or dose response within the results obtained. As these two plates were plated by different people, pipetting error is unlikely to be a cause of a lack of dose response. The luminescence response from the media removed from the wells is consistent with the media control values, suggesting that minimal cells are removed during this pipetting step, and so this step should not be causing variation in the assay.

Optimisation experiment eight

In this experiment cells were plated in both a 96 well and a 24 well plate to test if the cells needed more space in the well to grow and spread out. The protocol was also modified to allow more time between transfection and the addition of samples, in order to allow transcription of the relevant proteins required for reading the assay to take place. New MTT dilutions at a range of 40 nM to 4 fM were made and compared to the previous experiments' dilutions. Results are plotted in **Figure XXVI**.

Transfection mixtures

Table VIII: The composition of the different transfection mixtures used in optimisation experiment eight. Two different transfection mixtures were created with different end volumes for a 96 well plate, and a 24 well plate. Old MTT dilutions were also tested against new dilutions.

	96 well	24 well
Amplified androgen receptor plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.2 µg/µl)	8.4	25.2
MMTV plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.4 µg/µl)	8.4	25.2
pRL-tk plasmid (µl) (diluted in media to 0.1 µg/µl)	8.4	25.2
FUGENE HD (µl)	17.64	52.92
Media (no serum) (µl)	819	2457

Results

Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results. Then the ratio of firefly to *Renilla* values was taken and results plotted.

Figure XXVI: Luminescence results from optimisation experiment eight. Values shown are the ratio of the firefly luminescence to the *Renilla* luminescence. Plates shown consist of both 96 and 24 wells, and have a transfection time of either 24 or 48 h: 96 well plate: 24 h (A), 24 well plate: 24 h (B), 96 well plate: 48 h (C) and 24 well plate: 48 h (D). Old MTT dilutions are shown in blue and green (1 and 2, respectively) and new MTT dilutions are shown in orange and red (3 and 4, respectively). Controls are shown in purple.

There was minimal difference between the transfection lasting 24 h and 48 h (see **Figure XXVI**). However, was a slight improvement in luminescence levels from the previous experiment MTT dilutions when cells were grown in a 24 well plate. However, no dose response curve was achieved.

Discussion

Despite carrying out numerous optimisation experiments adjusting different assay parameters, unfortunately a dose-response curve could not be achieved within the timeframe of this Ph.D. The initial protocol design involved a three month work visit to the University of Tokyo in Japan to undertake training in cell culture and how to carry out this assay, and then this knowledge would be brought back to UWS for samples to be tested. Unfortunately, this training could not take place in Japan due to the Covid-19 pandemic, and this has had a significant impact on this protocol and its success.

Some headway was made towards optimising the assay, with increased luminescence being recorded which may have been due to a combination of reduced human error through practice, as well as adjusting the luminometer settings. Higher luminescence in the assay wells compared to the control wells suggests that transfection of the cells was occurring, but that the levels of transfection between cells was inconsistent. Potentially some plasmids were transfected into the cells and not others. This could be assessed using a FACS (fluorescence activated cell sorting) machine, which could sort and count cells according to the different light scattering properties of the cells to determine which plasmids are taken up by different cells to check for inconsistencies. However, access to this equipment was not feasible. There may have been other potential reasons for this assay not to work, such as a potential mycoplasma infection which would not be identified with microscopy, or an incorrect level of ethanol present within the positive and negative androgen control suspensions that was having a toxic effect on the cells. At this time the resources needed to test these theories were not available. Other assay studies using HepG2 cells (McMillian *et al.*, 2001; Miret, De Groene and Klaffke, 2006; Thabrew, Hughes, and McFarlane, 2011) have shown success, but as this was the first time this protocol has been adapted and was unoptimized, there are no results within the peer-reviewed literature with which to compare the results obtained for this assay. Therefore, the decision was made to focus on the second cell-based luminescence assay. This assay is arguably less ecologically relevant as it is not focused on amphibians, which are the focus of this Ph.D., but as there is a lot of similarity between the amphibian and human androgen receptors, the human MDA-kb2 assay was considered a viable alternative to the manual transfection attempted so far.

Methodology: Human androgen receptor

Maintenance and passaging of MDA-kb2 cells

MDA-kb2 cells were purchased commercially from ATCC (product number: CRL-2713) and thawed using the same methodology as the HepG2 cells (see above). Methodologies for maintaining these cells were also identical except for a different cell culture media (consisting of Leibovitz-15 media supplemented with 10% unstripped FBS and no added antibiotics) and that cells were kept in an incubator at 37°C without additional CO₂. As with the HepG2 cells, usually one media change and one passage was carried out per week, although this was assessed by visual examination of the cells with the microscope (see **Figure XXVII**).

Figure XXVII: MDA-kb2 cells in culture at roughly 30 % confluence at 400x magnification. These cells have a classic globular shape when grown under optimal conditions. Cells are typically 10-20 μm in size. Image credit: Catherine Whatley. Image taken using the EVOS M5000 Imaging System.

Assay methodology

All methodologies were done under sterile conditions using aseptic technique in the cell culture hood, with the exception of adding the assay reagents, as these kill the cells in the process regardless (see **Figure XXVIII**).

Figure XXVIII: A diagram demonstrating the process of aseptic technique that was used to grow and maintain MDA-kb2 cells, while also preventing contamination. Image created using Biorender.

The MDA-kb2 cells used in this assay were grown and maintained using cell culture methodologies as outlined above. Once the cells had reached an appropriate density and were in good health, and 24 h before plating, the cell growth media was switched to Leibovitz-L15 media with stripped FBS, as any hormones present in unstripped FBS may bind to the androgen receptor and influence the assay results (see **Figure XXIX**).

Figure 3.XXIX: A diagram demonstrating the process of switching the unstripped media of the MDA-kb2 cells to stripped media 24 h before plating. Image created using Biorender.

Twenty four hours after the cells were switched to stripped media, cells were passaged, counted and seeded onto a white, sterile 96 well plate at a density of 1×10^5 in 100 μ l per well of complete growth medium (L-glutamine supplemented Leibovitz-15 media + 10% stripped Fetal Bovine Serum) (see **Figure XXX**). These cells were then incubated for 24 h to allow them to settle, making sure there was media wells on each side of the experimental wells to prevent evaporative loss.

Figure XXX: A diagram demonstrating the process of plating and passaging the MDA-kb2 cells for use in the assay. Image created using Biorender.

An equal volume of samples to be tested diluted in media (or MTT or flutamide as an androgen and an anti-androgen control, respectively, see **Appendix 2.7** for MTT and flutamide dilutions) was added to the volume of media already in the well (180 μ l) and incubated for 24 h (see **Figure XXXI**).

Figure XXXI: A diagram demonstrating the process of adding the samples and controls to the MDA-kb2 cells. Image created using Biorender.

All assay reagents were brought to room temperature and made up according to the kit instructions. Cells were removed from the incubator and 125 μ l of media taken from the wells using a multichannel pipette and discarded. The remaining 75 μ l of media left in the wells, was added to 75 μ l of Steady-Glo[®] luciferase assay reagent. The plate was shaken in the dark at 400 rpm for 5 min at room temperature, and the firefly luminescence produced read. This was performed three times and an average taken (see **Figure XXXII**).

Figure XXXII: A diagram demonstrating the process of adding the Steady-Glo reagent to the assay and reading the MDA-kb2 cells using the luminometer. Image created using Biorender.

Assay optimisation

The first step in optimisation of this assay was to produce a dose response curve using an androgen (MTT) and an anti-androgen (flutamide) as controls to test the sensitivity of the assay (see **Appendix 2.7** for MTT and flutamide dilutions), and to determine the 60 % level to combine with the pond water samples in the assay. All tables and graphs were created using Excel.

A positive control to test the use of the luminometer used for the assay (ThermoScientific Varioskan Lux) was carried out using the Promega QuantiLum Recombinant Luciferase (product code: E1701) which is a concentrate of firefly luciferin (10–15 mg/ml). The luminometer used was a different luminometer (Varioskan™ LUX multimode microplate reader, ThermoFisher, product code: VL0000D0) to the one used in the optimisation of the first cell-based luminescence assay, due to a change in laboratory. The Quantilum was diluted 1000-fold in complete growth media, and then 10X dilutions with complete growth media were made in a 96 well white luminometer plate. An equal volume (100 µl) of

Steady-Glo luminescence assay reagent was added and the plates were read using the luminometer (see **Figure XXXIII**). The results showed a very high level of luminescence produced which reduced as the concentration of QuantiLum decreased, demonstrating that the luminometer was functional, and likely more sensitive than the luminometer used in the HepG2 amphibian androgen receptor assay.

Figure XXXIII: Results from the QuantiLum positive control experiment. 5 rows of 10X dilutions were plated in triplicate, along with media controls. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed. Note: dilutions 1 and 2 produced a level of luminescence too high for the luminometer to quantify, and so could not be plotted.

Optimisation experiment one

For this experiment, a range of MTT concentrations from 5 nM to 3.125 pM was plated along with an estimated 60 % value of 1.25 nM of MTT. Three flutamide concentrations were also plated from 10 μ M to 0.05 μ M in conjunction with 1.25 nM MTT. Vehicle and media controls were also plated. Plates were done in duplicate to account for any edge effects. Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results (see **Figure XXXIV**).

Results

Figure XXXIV: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment one. Dose response for flutamide is shown in orange, and dose response for MTT is shown in blue. The 60% level of MTT is shown in light green. Controls are shown in purple. Dilution series 1-8 represents eight stepwise dilutions of MTT from a concentration of 5 nM to 3.125 pM, and eight stepwise dilutions of flutamide from 10 μ M to 0.05 μ M.

Although there was a clear difference in the level of luminescence produced compared to the media controls, there was no clear dose response curve from either the MTT or the flutamide curves. In particular, the four wells containing the 60% level of MTT (shown in light green) were expected to be at the same level, and the levels are seen to be inconsistent. Further optimisation was required.

Optimisation experiment two

This experiment was a repeat of optimisation experiment one, other than the concentration range of MTT was increased to a range of 100 nM to 0.2 nM, and the flutamide concentrations mixed with the 60% level of MTT at 1.25 nM were increased to a range of 20 nM to 0.1 nM.

Results

Figure XXXV: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment two. Dose response for flutamide is shown in orange, and dose response for MTT is shown in blue. The 60 % level of MTT is shown in light green. Controls are shown in purple.

Results were calculated by taking an average of the control values and subtracting them from all results (see **Figure XXXV**). Plate two produced values across the plate that were not consistent with plate 1, and showed no variation in luminescence between any of the wells. As such, only the results from plate 1 have been plotted. There was evidence of a more consistent dose response curve for both MTT and flutamide, although the range of dilutions needed to be expanded in order to see the full curve.

Optimisation experiment three

In this experiment, the concentration range of MTT was increased from 200 nM to 91.449 pM, and the flutamide concentrations mixed with the 60 % level of MTT at 1.25 nM were increased to a range of 20 nM to 32.768 nM.

Results

Figure XXXVI: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment three. Dose response for flutamide is shown in orange, and dose response for MTT is shown in blue. The 60 % level of MTT is shown in light green. Controls are shown in purple. Dilution series 1-8 represents eight stepwise dilutions of MTT from a concentration of 200 nM to 91.449 pM, and eight stepwise dilutions of flutamide from 20 nM to 32.768 nM.

As shown in **Figure XXXVI**, there is no dose response from the MTT dilutions, or from the flutamide dilutions. There is also variation in the 60% level plated, which should be shown as a straight line. This was surprising given the relative success of the previous experiment.

Following optimisation experiment three, the assay was paused and the MDA-kb2 cells were revived approximately 5 months later. Fresh cells from a low passage number (passage 2)

were thawed and grown for approximately 3 weeks, along with fresh media and new sterile white 96 well luminescence plates with lids (Thermo Scientific, product number: 10158721). The assay protocol was the same as that in previous experiments unless otherwise stated. HepG2 cells from the last passage used (passage 8) were also thawed in order to test for mycoplasma contamination that could have explained the variability in assay results obtained using these cells.

Mycoplasma testing

Mycoplasma contamination can result in many cytopathic effects that can alter the results of experimental work. Mycoplasma contaminations cannot be seen using microscopy as with bacterial or fungal contaminations of cultures, and so testing for the presence of mycoplasma should be done regularly. Effects of mycoplasma contamination upon the cells can be incredibly varied according to the type of cell, species of mycoplasma present, and severity of infection. Effects can include (but are not limited to) alterations in cell morphology, alterations in the growth and viability of cells, and altered levels of DNA, RNA, and/or protein expression (for a review of mycoplasma contamination in cell culture, see Drexler and Uphoff, 2002).

Three weeks after being thawed, MDA-kb2 cells were tested for mycoplasma contamination that could potentially have caused this assay to not work as expected in previous experiments (see **Table IX**). This testing was also carried out once all cell culture for this protocol had been completed to ensure no mycoplasma contamination had occurred that may have altered the assay results, along with the thawed HepG2 cells from the amphibian androgen receptor assay (see **Table X** and **XI**) to retrospectively assess if this may have been a cause of assay variation. Mycoplasma testing was carried out using the MycoAlert™ Mycoplasma Detection Kit (Lonza, product code: LT07-318) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The samples tested consisted of cell culture media removed from the cells during routine passaging. The media was centrifuged, and the supernatant removed in order to remove any cells present and was stored at 4°C until needed. Results presented are the ratio of background ATP luminescence in the sample to mycoplasma specific ATP luminescence found in the sample, as measured using a Varioskan Lux (Thermo Scientific). A ratio result

of below 0.9 is considered to be negative. A result between 0.9 and 1.2 is considered borderline where cultures need to be retested after 24 h. A result above 1.2 is considered to be positive for mycoplasma contamination and should be treated accordingly.

Mycoplasma test one

As shown by the results from **Table 3.IV**, all results for mycoplasma contamination were negative.

Table IV: Results from the preliminary mycoplasma testing carried out before beginning the next phase of MDA-kb2 cell assay optimisation. The negative control sample contained no mycoplasma, and the positive control contained high levels of mycoplasma ATP. The three MDA-kb2 samples were from three different flasks.

Sample	Ratio value
Negative control	0.07
Positive control	18.95
MDA-kb2 1	0.15
MDA-kb2 2	0.19
MDA-kb2 3	0.2

Mycoplasma test two

As shown by the results from **Table X**, all results for both HepG2 and MDA-kb2 samples are considered borderline. These cultures were retested after 24 h, as shown in **Table XI**.

Table X: Results from mycoplasma testing carried out on both HepG2 cells and MDA-kb2 cells at the end of cell culture work for this Chapter. The negative control sample contained no mycoplasma, and the positive control contained high levels of mycoplasma ATP. The two MDA-kb2 samples were from two different identical flasks, and the three HepG2 samples from three different identical flasks. Borderline results have been indicated in bold.

Sample	Ratio value
Negative control	0.74
Positive control	24.67
Hep G2 1	0.95
Hep G2 2	1.01
Hep G2 3	0.97
MDA-kb2 1	1.02
MDA-kb2 2	0.96

As shown by the results from **Table X**, all results for both HepG2 and MDA-kb2 samples are considered borderline. These cultures were retested after 24 h, as shown in **Table XI**.

Table XI: Results from the retesting after 24 h of samples submitted for mycoplasma testing on both HepG2 cells and MDA-kb2 cells at the end of cell culture work. The negative control sample contained no mycoplasma, and the positive control contained high levels of mycoplasma ATP. The two MDA-kb2 samples were from two different flasks, and the three HepG2 samples from three different flasks.

Sample	Ratio value
Negative control	0.29
Positive control	91.03
Hep G2 1	0.77
Hep G2 2	0.72
Hep G2 3	0.54
MDA-kb2 1	0.49
MDA-kb2 2	0.55
MDA-kb2 2	0.55

As shown by the results from **Table XI**, all results are now considered negative. This could have been due to human error in testing of the first samples from **Table X**. According to these results, there is no mycoplasma contamination present in the samples tested that could have altered the behaviour of either of the assays tested as part of this Chapter.

Optimisation experiment four

For this experiment, a range of four 6X dilutions of MTT were used (ranging in concentration from 200 nM to 247.348 pM), in order to establish a basic MTT dose response using a wide range of MTT concentrations. Vehicle and media controls were also plated. The settings on the luminometer were set as a 50 ms well interval, a 50 ms measurement time, and a 5 s lag time in-between well readings using a luminometer (Thermofisher Varioskan Lux). These settings are the default luminescence readings on this machine (see **Figure XXXVII**).

Results

Figure XXXVII: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment four. Dose response for MTT is shown in shades of red, with a media and vehicle control shown in green and yellow. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed (n=3). There are no error bars for the MTT concentrations as there is only one replicate.

As shown in **Figure XXXVII**, there is a slight dose response from the MTT dilutions, however the level of luminescence produced is increasing as MTT concentration decreases, which contrasts with expected results (decreased luminescence with decreased concentration of MTT). This may be a result of incorrect luminometer settings, which were then altered in the next optimisation experiment. There is also a small n number for the MTT concentration samples (1) which makes interpretation of these results difficult.

Optimisation experiment five

For this experiment, the same range of MTT dilutions as optimisation experiment four were tested. Vehicle and media controls were also plated. For this experiment, the settings on the luminometer were changed to a 50 ms well interval, a 10,000 ms measurement time, and a 5 s lag time in-between well readings. The measurement time was increased according to the recommendations for other Promega luminescent kits provided by the Varioskan Lux pre-programmed settings (see **Figure XXXVIII**). This experiment was also repeated after pipettes used had been calibrated by weighing water to account for any variability in replicability and human error.

Results

Figure XXXVIII: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment five before calibration (A) and after calibration (B). Dose response for MTT is shown in shades of red, with a media and vehicle control shown in green and yellow. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed (n=3). There are no error bars for the MTT concentrations as there is only one replicate.

As shown in **Figure XXXVIII**, there was a dose response from the MTT dilutions, however the level of luminescence produced is increasing as MTT concentration decreases, as seen in optimisation experiment four. There is a decrease in luminescence seen between the two lowest MTT concentrations as expected. This may be a result of incorrect luminometer settings, or pipettes that are measuring incorrect volumes. These same trends are observed after calibration of pipettes, suggesting that pipette error is not a source of variation.

Optimisation experiment six

The assay protocol was altered in several ways for this optimisation protocol to account for potential sources of variation in results. For this experiment, a range of eight 3X dilutions of MTT (ranging in concentration from 200 nM to 91.1 pM) was used to widen the range of concentrations used. Replicates of MTT were increased to three per sample to see the replicability in luminescence results between wells. In addition, the protocol was changed to increase the end well volume to raise the media level closer to the sensor in order to improve readings. This was done by removing less media on day four of the assay protocol (leaving 100 μ l media instead of 75 μ l) and by adding more Steady-glo reagent (100 μ l as per the original protocol instead of 75 μ l). All samples were done in triplicate to ensure replicability, and the edge of the plate was not used to account for any edge effects. The total ethanol concentration of the wells was also reduced from 1 % to 0.75 % in case of ethanol toxicity causing cell death that could affect the amount of luminescence produced. Vehicle and media controls were also plated (see **Figure XXXIX**).

Results

Figure XXXIX: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment six. Dose response for MTT is shown in shades of red, with a media and vehicle control shown in green and yellow. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed (n=3).

As shown in **Figure XXXIX**, there was a dose response curve as expected from high luminescence to lower luminescence according to MTT concentration. A dose response curve is expected to be shown in an 'S' sigmoidal plateau at the highest and lowest levels with decreasing response in-between (Yang *et al.*, 2021). There is also high replicability in luminescence between wells as determined by the error bars shown. The results from this experiment indicate that the whole range of MTT detectable from this assay has not yet been determined, as there is no plateau at the lower level, and luminescence has not decreased to the level of the controls. This graph also indicates that the highest range of detectability of this assay for MTT is approximately 22.22 nM as there is no increase in luminescence beyond this concentration. The lower range of MTT was expanded upon in the next optimisation experiment. The other protocol modifications made in this experiment have yielded favourable results, and so were assimilated into the protocol moving forward. From the results obtained from this graph, the 60 % luminescence level of MTT was estimated from this graph to be around 1.25 nM.

Cell viability assays

In order to determine what concentrations of methyltestosterone (MTT) and ethanol that the samples are suspended in would prove toxic to the cells used in this Chapter, an MTT assay was run to test the viability of the cells at different concentrations of these two substances. This would help us to determine the maximum level of methyltestosterone that could be used as a positive control to achieve the highest levels of luminescence, as well as the maximum amount of sample that could be added to the cells via the ethanol buffer before cell death occurred.

The viability of the cells was tested using the MTT assay, which is a standardised method of measuring cellular metabolic activity in order to indicate cell viability (Kumar, Nagarajan and Uchil, 2018). Please note that this is different from the MTT (methyltestosterone) used as the androgen positive control for both assays in this Chapter. The cell viability assay involves the conversion of MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide), a yellow water-soluble dye into insoluble purple crystals of formazan via mitochondrial reductase which are then solubilised. The more cells are alive and viable within a sample, the more crystals are produced and so a stronger coloured purple solution is created. The solution is read using a spectrophotometer using a clear plate.

Methodology

An MTT solution was made up at a concentration of 5 mg/ml using powdered MTT and sterile PBS (Kumar, Nagarajan and Uchil, 2018). This solution was then filtered through a 0.2 micron filter. For a cell assay plate to be tested, all media was removed and 100 µl fresh media without FBS and 20 µl MTT solution was added. The plate was wrapped in foil and incubated at 37°C for 4 h. After 4 h, all media was removed and 100 µl of Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) was added to solubilise the crystals that had formed. The plate was re-wrapped in foil and incubated at 37°C for 15 min. The colour of the resulting solution was read at 570 nM using a Thermoscientific Multiskan Sky (product code: A51119500C).

Cell viability ethanol toxicity test

MDA-kb2 cells were seeded in a 96 well plate with ethanol concentrations ranging from 10 % to 0.1 % along with media controls to determine the optimal ethanol concentration that would allow maximum sample exposure for the cells while preventing ethanol toxicity. The protocol for the MTT cell viability assay was followed as outlined above (see **Figure XL**).

Results

Figure XL: Absorbance results from the ethanol toxicity cell viability test. Ethanol concentrations are shown in shades of yellow and a media control is shown in green. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed ($n=3$).

As shown in **Figure XL**, as ethanol concentration decreases, absorbance increased up to around 0.5 % ethanol concentration in each well, where levels are approximate to that of the media control. This suggests that approximately 0.5 % ethanol is the optimal concentration to prevent cell death from ethanol toxicity while still allowing as much sample to be added to the MDA-kb2 cells as possible. This is half the concentration used in the original protocol (1 %) which may therefore have been causing cell death and producing variability in the results. Moving forward, ethanol concentrations within each well were reduced to 0.5 %.

Cell Viability Methyltestosterone Toxicity Test

MDA-kb2 cells were seeded in a 96 well plate with eight 3X dilutions of MTT (methyltestosterone) ranging in concentration from 200 nM to 91.1 pM in order to test for any toxic effects of MTT that may impact cell viability and produce variation in luminescence results. The protocol for the MTT cell viability assay was followed as outlined above (see **Figure XLI**).

Results

Figure XLI: Absorbance results from the methyltestosterone toxicity cell viability test. Dilution series 1-8 represents eight stepwise dilutions of MTT ranging in concentration from 200 nM to 91.1 pM. Absorbance value of MTT is shown in shades of red, with a media and vehicle control shown in green and yellow. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed ($n=3$).

As shown in **Figure XLI**, as MTT concentration changes there is no difference in cell viability compared to the media and vehicle control, so there is no toxic effect on the cells resulting from the concentrations of MTT used in this assay.

Optimisation experiment seven

For this experiment, a range of eight 4X dilutions of MTT (ranging in concentration from 50 nM to 1.25 pM) were plated to widen the range of concentrations used and establish the full MTT curve. 2.5X dilutions of flutamide were also plated in combination with the estimated 60 % MTT level of 1.25 nM (ranging in concentration from 20 μ M to 32.768 nM) as well as replicates of the estimated 60 % MTT level of 1.25 nM. Media and vehicle controls were also plated (see **Figure XLII**). This was repeated twice to test for human error and to see variability in the assay.

Results

Figure XLII: Average luminescence results from the first (A) and second (B) repeat of optimisation experiment seven. Please note, the range of values for luminescence shown on this graph has been altered to a range of 6000-1300 to better show the spread of the data. Dose response for flutamide is shown in orange, and dose response for MTT is shown in blue. The 60 % level of MTT is shown in light green and the controls are shown in purple. These values are shown as a single point as there is no dilution series. Dilution series 1-8 represents 8 stepwise dilutions of MTT from a concentration of 50 nM to 1.25 pM, and eight stepwise dilutions of flutamide (with 60 % MTT) from 20 nM to 32.768 nM. Error bars showing the standard error are displayed (n=3).

As shown in **Figure XLII**, there was a dose response curve as expected from high luminescence to lower luminescence according to MTT concentration, although again the full dose response curve appears to not be shown. There is a positive relationship between decreasing flutamide dilutions and increased luminescence as expected, however the full dose response curve has not yet been achieved. Overall luminescence levels are also lower in **B** compared to **A**. The 60% MTT level used is also much lower in **A** and **B** than the lowest concentration of MTT used in this experiment (1.25 pM). This may be a result of human error.

Machine calibration

In-between optimisation experiments nine and ten, the luminometer (Thermofisher VarioSkan) was calibrated with results sent to Thermofisher to confirm machine is operating normally. No abnormalities were found.

Optimisation experiment eight

For this experiment, the same protocol as optimisation experiment eight was followed, to test for human error and repeatability of values between experiments. The number of dilutions was however reduced from eight to six in order to preserve reagents (see **Figure XLIII**). This was repeated twice to test for human error and to see variability in the assay.

Results

Figure XLIII: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment eight. Dose response for flutamide is shown in orange, and dose response for MTT is shown in blue. The 60 % level of MTT is shown in light green. Controls are shown in purple. Dilution series 1-6 represents 6 stepwise dilutions of MTT from a concentration of 50 nM to 48.8 pM, and 3 stepwise dilutions of flutamide (with 60 % MTT) from 20 nM to 204.8 nM.

As shown in **Figure XLIII**, There is a dose response curve as expected from high luminescence to low luminescence according to MTT concentration, but there is no dose response as expected for flutamide or the 60% MTT level. The overall level of luminescence

level for all samples is much lower than previous experiments, especially between experiment **A** and **B**, likely due to the degradation of the steady-glo reagent over time.

Optimisation experiment nine

For this experiment, the same concentration of MTT (50 nM) was tested in different wells across the 96 well plate against a media control. This was to assess if there was a difference in luminescence readings from the same concentration that may be indicative of issues with the readings produced by the luminometer. The value of 50 nM was selected as it is a high concentration that should produce a high level of luminescence (see **Figure XLIV**).

Results

Figure XLIV: Average luminescence results from optimisation experiment nine. Dose response for MTT is shown in blue, with the media control values shown in purple.

As shown in **Figure XLIV**, There is a lot of variation in results obtained between cells both containing the sample and for the control wells. This could be indicative of an issue in the way the luminometer is reading the luminescence results between wells.

Despite carrying out numerous optimisation experiments adjusting different assay parameters, unfortunately a dose-response curve could not be achieved within the timeframe of this project. Therefore, following the completion of optimisation experiment twelve, the decision was made to cease work on this assay protocol in order to prioritise other Ph.D. work. Some headway was made towards optimising the assay, with some positive adjustments being made towards a finalised assay protocol, however it could not be ruled out whether there were issues with the assay protocol, degradation of the steady-glo assay reagent with a short shelf life, or with the luminometer settings or functionality itself.

The finalised MDA-kb2 cell luminescence assay protocol as it stands can be found below:

Day one:

24 h before assay starts, perform a media change from media containing unstripped FBS, to media containing stripped FBS in order to allow any remaining growth hormones that may interfere with the assay to be used.

Day two:

Plate MDA-KB2 cells at a density of 1×10^5 cells/well in 100 μ l per well of complete growth medium (Leibovitz L-15 media + 10% stripped Fetal Bovine Serum) in a white 96-well plate. Incubate at 37°C for 24 h.

Day three:

After 24 h, add samples to media:

Combine 10 μ l of each sample or positive control with 990 μ l of warmed assay media (Leibovitz L-15 media + 10% stripped fetal Bovine Serum) in a 1 ml sterile test tube and invert to mix. This will result in an ethanol concentration of 1 % (to make 0.5 % in the well after 50 % dilution to prevent cell toxicity). Add an equal quantity to that already in the well (100 μ l) along with a media control (just media), and an ethanol control (100 μ l of 10 μ l of ethanol mixed with 990 μ l of warmed assay media) and incubate at 37°C for 24 h.

Day four:

After 24 h, remove 100 μ l of media to leave 100 μ l in well, and add 100 μ l of SteadyGlo reagent. Incubate for 5 min at room temperature in the dark on plate shaker, and read results using a luminometer.

Discussion

Despite attempts to fully optimise two different assays in order to quantify the androgenic or anti-androgenic activity of the natal pond water of *Rana temporaria*, neither assay could be optimised within the timeframe of this Ph.D. Regarding the amphibian androgen receptor assay, inconsistent luminescent readings were recorded despite numerous efforts to optimise the protocol and to adjust the settings of the luminometer. I believe the most likely cause of these inconsistent results is uneven uptake of plasmids by different cells, which would affect the different *Renilla* and firefly luminescent readings (caused by different plasmids) that are recorded in order to produce a ratio of these two results. The next steps in further optimisation of this protocol would be to repeat these optimisation experiments on a different luminometer in order to rule out luminometer error, and to utilise a FACS machine to test which plasmids had been taken up by different cells. Access to a FACS machine or an alternative luminometer was not possible at the University of the West of Scotland, so these next steps could not be taken. In addition, routine mycoplasma testing was not available during the initial work using the HepG2 cells, so testing for mycoplasma contamination that could produce variations in assay results could not be carried out at the time. Mycoplasma species can survive freezing in liquid nitrogen, and so when mycoplasma testing became available, HepG2 cell samples from the last passage used were thawed and re-animated in order to retrospectively test for mycoplasma contamination, along with new cultures of MDA-kb2 cells. No mycoplasma contamination was detected in any samples, so this is unlikely to be a cause of variation in luminescence results for either assay.

Regarding the use of the MDA-kb2 human androgen receptor assay, the initial protocol utilised in this piece of work was established within the literature. Later experiments

determined that some causes of variability could be reduced through alterations to previously reported protocols, for example through reduction of the ethanol concentration of each well to increase cell viability. Although with this assay some good progress was made towards achieving a standard curve for MTT and flutamide exposure, results became inconsistent again in subsequent optimisation experiments. I believe the primary causes of these inconsistent results was degradation of the steady-glo assay reagent, which has a very short shelf life, as well as inconsistent readings obtained from the luminometer used.

It was hoped that these results would underpin results obtained from other Chapters in order to detail any endocrine disrupting effects of the pond water and how this influenced the morphometric data presented in **Chapter 2** and the gene expression and histology data from **Chapter 3**. In the absence of data on endocrine disrupting effects, the water samples have been stored for potential further analysis in the future. Use of the amphibian androgen receptor within cell based luminescent assays would be more ecologically relevant than using the human androgen receptor, and the use of an amphibian-derived cell line would have been preferable to transfection of a human cell line with an amphibian androgen receptor. This highlights the need for a range of commercially available amphibian cell lines from a range of species and tissue types.

As endocrine disrupting pollution is a significant threat to amphibians, research into optimisation of this assay should be continued. If an amphibian-specific assay is unavailable, then human-based androgen receptor assays are regarded as a suitable substitute, however more studies are needed on the utilisation of these assays with the use of wild samples.

Appendix 2.6: Water sample collection and preparation for androgenic/anti-androgenic cell based luminescence assays

Alongside development of the assays, water samples were collected and processed, ready for use in an assay once optimised. If the assay had been optimised successfully, these concentrated pond water samples would have been tested in the assay in place of the MTT (and in combination with flutamide) to detect androgenic or anti-androgenic activity that would produce luminescence. This would have acted as an indicator of endocrine disrupting properties of the pond water that could interfere with *R. temporaria* androgen receptors. The methodology by which these samples were collected and prepared is outlined below.

Ten litres of pond water (or less if water levels were low) were collected in glass jars from selected sites (both reference sites and those suspected to be polluted with EDCs) from across the central belt of Scotland. Sites used are summarised in **Table XII** and full details of fieldwork site selection can be found in **Chapter 2**. Water samples were fixed by adding ultrapure methanol to a final concentration of 1 %, and stored at in the dark at 4°C until they could be processed. Where found, tadpoles were also collected from these sites, and dissections carried out to obtain gonadal tissue for histology and gene expression analysis (See **Chapters 2 and 3** for more details). Water samples were prefiltered through glass microfibre filter papers (Whatman) under vacuum before being pulled through solid phase extraction (SPE) cartridges to capture any analytes within the matrix. Cartridges were then stored at -20°C until they could be eluted. After a pre-wash step using a 5 % methanol solution, cartridges were eluted twice using 4 ml of ultrapure ethanol into separate silanised amber glass vials, and stored at -20°C. The eluted samples were dried down using a turbovap LV (Biotage) and then reconstituted with 0.4 ml of ultrapure ethanol per 1 L of starting pond water sample, in order to ensure an even concentration of analytes in the final assay samples. Samples were stored at -20°C until use.

Table XII: Summary table of sites used in 2021/2022 as well as samples collected from each site.

Site Name	Sampling Date	Site Type	GPS co-ordinates	No. tadpoles collected for gene expression and histology (see Chapter 3)	Volume of water collected (L)
Ravenswood Bog	17/05/21	Suburban nature reserve	NS 74559 73765	20	8
Erik's Pond	19/05/21	Agricultural/Rural	NS 62971 51066	20	7.5 + 4.5
	31/05/21			10	(two separate visits)
Victoria Park	24/05/21	Urban Park	NS 53782 67339	20	8
Arcadia	19/05/21	Rural	NS 47954 88310	20	7.5
Langlands Gate	19/05/21	Suburban nature reserve	NS 63902 51108	0	8
Glasgow University	28/05/21	Urban Park	NS 56758 66936	20	10
Froggy Pond	28/05/21	Suburban Park	NT 05106 65871	20	7.5
Hundleshope Farm	31/05/21	Rural	NT 22729 36214	0	4.5
Endfield Avenue	10/06/21	Urban Garden	NS 55828 68695	10	7.5
Craigmore	18/06/21	Suburban Garden	NS 41741 66565	20	3.5
Campbridge	28/05/21	Suburban Park	NT 05130 64035	-	7.5
Irvine	06/06/22	Rural	NS 36950 42364	9	10
Hunterston	07/06/22	Industrial/Coastal	NS 19538 52178	10	10
Langlands Gate	10/06/22	Suburban nature reserve	NS 63902 51108	15	10
Arcadia	14/06/22	Rural Garden	NS 47954 88310	3	10
Laurieston	17/06/22	Rural	NX 67641 65590	7	10
Ravenswood Bog	27/06/22	Suburban nature reserve	NS 74559 73765	8	10

Appendix 2.7: Methyltestosterone and flutamide spiking used to test extraction efficiency of pond water elution in androgenic/anti-androgenic cell based luminescence assays

In order to test the extraction efficiency of any potential EDCs from the water samples, pond water and distilled water samples were spiked with MTT and flutamide (see **Table XIII**) as well as MTT and flutamide in combination, fixed with 1% methanol, and processed in the same way as the other pond water samples. Final concentrations were estimated to be 20 μ M of Flutamide, and 20 nM of MTT in the assay wells. Comparing these samples with the results of the MTT-dose response curve, would have allowed calculation of the extraction efficiency of EDCs from the water samples.

17 α -methyltestosterone (MTT) (commercially purchased from Sigma Aldrich, product number: 69240) was selected as the androgen control for this study, and flutamide (commercially purchased from Sigma Aldrich, product number: F0285600) was selected as the anti-androgen control. 40 mM stock solutions of MTT and flutamide were prepared in 4 ml of ultrapure ethanol from which all subsequent dilutions were prepared. Calculations for preparation of stock solutions are shown below:

A stock solution of **40 mM** Methyltestosterone (MTT) is made in 4 ml of ultrapure ethanol

$$\begin{aligned}0.04 \times 302.451 &= 12.09804 \text{ g/L} \times 0.004 \\(40 \text{ mM}) \times (\text{Molecular weight}) &= 12.09804 \text{ g/L} \times (4 \text{ ml}) \\&= 0.04839 \text{ or } \mathbf{0.0484 \text{ g MTT}} \text{ to add to } \mathbf{4 \text{ ml ethanol}}\end{aligned}$$

A stock solution of **40 mM** Flutamide (F) is made in 4 ml of ultrapure ethanol

$$\begin{aligned}0.04 \times 276.2118 &= 11.048472 \text{ g/L} \times 0.004 \\(40 \text{ mM}) \times (\text{Molecular weight}) &= 11.048472 \text{ g/L} \times (4 \text{ ml}) \\&= 0.04419 \text{ or } \mathbf{0.0442 \text{ g F}} \text{ to add to } \mathbf{4 \text{ ml ethanol}}\end{aligned}$$

Pond water (40 L) was collected for spiking from Ravenswood bog, a reliable clean reference site where *R. temporaria* is regularly found. Although best efforts were taken to collect all water samples in glass containers to prevent the risk of leaching of potential chemicals, plastic 10 L containers were used if glass was unavailable. As a result, an additional 10 L of distilled water was stored in a plastic container for 24 h before being spiked and processed in the same way, to determine if any EDCs leached from the plastic into the water.

Table XIII: Summary table of spiked pond and distilled water samples used to assess the extraction efficiency of MTT and Flutamide used as controls.

Sample	Purpose
Pond water	Detect background concentration of assay sensitivity from this sample and provide a blank
Pond water + Flutamide	Detect any androgenic activity in the sample and test the extraction efficiency of flutamide
Pond water + MTT	Detect any anti-androgenic activity in the sample and test the extraction efficiency of MTT
Pond water + MTT+ Flutamide	MTT and F in a mixed sample to check for interactions between them in the assay
Distilled water	Detect background concentration of assay sensitivity from this sample and provide a blank
Distilled water + plastic	Detect any leachate from plastic containers that may activate the assay
Distilled water + Flutamide	Detect any androgenic activity in the sample and test the extraction efficiency of flutamide
Distilled water + MTT	Detect any anti-androgenic activity in the sample and test the extraction efficiency of MTT
Distilled water + MTT + Flutamide	MTT and F in a mixed sample to check for interactions between them in the assay

Appendix 3.1: Histology methodology used in Chapter 3

Gonad tissue was fixed in 50% buffered formalin at the point of sampling to ensure preservation of morphological structures. For processing, gonad samples were removed from the formalin and placed in a tissue cassette (Pro Marc System 3 slotted cassette, product code: EAI-0510-10A) within a sponge to ensure tissue was not lost during processing due to their small size. Samples were then processed using a Thermoscientific Excelsior AS (product code: A82310100) which uses increasing concentrations of ethanol to dehydrate the tissue and allow paraffin wax to fill the cells. At the end of the processing procedure, the gonad samples were removed from the molten wax and transferred to wax moulds in the embedding station (Thermoscientific HistoStar, product code: HIS3350). Once the wax was sufficiently hardened, the sample cartridges were removed, and the wax blocks trimmed to remove any excess wax. Blocks were then sliced to 7 μm using a microtome (Thermoscientific Microm, product code: HM 325) to create a ribbon of wax sections. These ribbons were placed on a labelled slide in a water bath at 42°C. Once the samples were dried and stuck to the slides, they were dried in an oven in racks at 56 °C for 4 h, or overnight. This ensured the mixed tissue types within the sample adhered to the slides and did not get washed off during staining. Slides were then stained using hematoxylin (Gill no. 1) (Sigma Aldrich, product code: GHS116) and eosin-Y (1 % aqueous) (Scientific Laboratory Supplies, product code: 592-75) following the methodology in **Table XIV**.

Table XIV: Staining protocol used for the histological analysis of gonad samples

Step	Solution	Time
1. Dewaxing	Xylene	15 min
2. Dewaxing	Xylene	5 min
3. Gradual hydration	Ethanol (100%)	2 min
4. Gradual hydration	Ethanol (90%)	2 min
5. Gradual hydration	Ethanol (70%)	2 min
6. Full hydration	Double distilled water	2 min
7. First stain	Hematoxylin (Gill no. 1)	5 min
8. Removal of excess stain	Running water (current created using tap water in a tub)	30 s
9. Dechlorination	Ethanol (70%) + Hydrochloric acid (0.5%)	30 s
10. Water rinse	Running water (current created using tap water in a tub)	30 s
11. Second stain	Eosin Y (1% aqueous)	2 min
12. Removal of excess stain	Double distilled water	1 min
13. Gradual dehydration	Ethanol (70%)	1 min
14. Gradual dehydration	Ethanol (90%)	1 min
15. Gradual dehydration	Ethanol (100%)	1 min
16. Binding agent	Xylene (for 5 min or stored indefinitely until cover slipping)	5 min

Reagents were changed as regularly as possible to try to ensure good quality staining, and slides were visually assessed after each staining run to determine the quality of staining produced, and the staining times of both hematoxylin and eosin were adjusted as needed. Once the slides had been stained and stored in xylene, without allowing slides to dry out, DPX mounting medium was used to attach a cover slip to the slides for long term storage.

Appendix 4.1: Range of water quality parameters recorded across all sites across all weeks from Chapter 4

Table XV: Range of water quality parameters recorded across all sites across all weeks.

Unit	Water Quality Parameter	Site					
		Bishopton	Hogganfield	Langlands Gate	Oldhall Ponds	Ravenswood Bog	Victoria Park
µS	Conductivity	113 - 427	105 - 153	548 - 827	425 - 470	242 - 725	89 - 169
%	DO (Dissolved oxygen)	14.1 - 103.8	25.2 - 102.9	13.3 - 18	36.1 - 52.2	38.3 - 133.4	23.9 - 98.4
None	pH	6.74 - 6.97	6.71 - 7.27	7.37 - 7.39	7.06 - 7.6	6.85 - 7.56	6.18 - 7.44
ppm	Salinity	56 - 203	52 - 77	258 - 392	214 - 234	115 - 364	46 - 84
mg/L	TDS (Total dissolved solids)	66 - 203	52 - 77	264 - 402	209 - 235	119 - 366	47 - 84
°C	Temperature	13.6 - 18.6	17.5 - 29.2	12.4 - 15.6	16.8 - 26.5	14.3 - 21.5	15.2 - 26.1

Appendix 4.2: Element LOD values and wavelengths from ICP-OES analysis from Chapter 4

Table XVI: Elements contained in the multi element standard used for ICP-OES, along with the average LOD and the wavelength used for calculation.

Periodic symbol	Element	Limit of detection (LOD) ppb	Wavelength (nm)
Ag	Silver	19.88	328.068
Al	Aluminium	1.53	396.153
As	Arsenic	23.43	188.979
B	Boron	2.75	249.677
Ba	Barium	0.24	233.527
Be	Beryllium	0.23	313.107
Bi	Bismuth	9.01	223.061
Ca	Calcium	1.11	317.933
Cd	Cadmium	1.94	228.802
Co	Cobalt	0.27	228.616
Cr	Chromium	1.80	267.716
Cu	Copper	33.13	327.393
Fe	Iron	0.89	238.204
K	Potassium	0.63	766.49
Li	Lithium	0.01	670.784
Mg	Magnesium	0.11	285.213
Mn	Manganese	0.04	257.61
Mo	Molybdenum	0.49	202.031
Na	Sodium	0.54	589.592
Ni	Nickel	2.46	231.604
Pb	Lead	1.07	220.353
Sb	Antimony	6.49	206.836
Se	Selenium	68.26	196.026
Sr	Strontium	0.01	407.771
Ti	Titanium	0.06	334.94
Tl	Tellurium	3.96	190.801
V	Vanadium	1.19	290.88
Zi	Zinc	0.51	206.2

Appendix 4.3: PCA Component loadings for elements and water quality variables separated by Gosner Stage from Chapter 4

25-30

Figure XLV: PCA output of component loadings from the pond element concentrations (A) and water quality measurements (B) from all weeks where tadpoles between Gosner stages 25 and 30 were found. A higher cos2 value indicates a higher component loading value.

31-35

Figure XLVII: PCA output of component loadings from the pond element concentrations (A) and water quality measurements (B) from all weeks where tadpoles between Gosner stages 31 and 35 were found. A higher cos2 value indicates a higher component loading value.

36-40

Figure XLVII: PCA output of component loadings from the pond element concentrations (A) and water quality measurements (B) from all weeks where tadpoles between Gosner stages 36 and 40 were found. A higher cos2 value indicates a higher component loading value.

41-46

Figure XLVIII: PCA output of component loadings from the pond element concentrations (A) and water quality measurements (B) from all weeks where tadpoles between Gosner stages 41 and 46 were found. A higher cos2 value indicates a higher component loading value.